

D2.1 Review/ Inventory of Existing (i) Laboratory Surveillance Systems and (ii) Outbreak Detection Systems or Methods of Participating Countries

UNITED FOR SURVEILLANCE IN EUROPE

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Representing 24 countries in Europe, UNITED4Surveillance gathers expertise in public health, clinical microbiology, epidemiology and data-science to support the strengthening of integrated surveillance systems for infectious disease prevention and control on national and European level

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TABLE OF CONTENT

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
2. DESCRIPTION OF TASKS	4
3. TASK 1 – DESCRIPTION OF WORK & MAIN ACHIEVEMENTS	5
3.1 BACKGROUND OF THE TASK	5
3.2 DESCRIPTION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT	6
3.2.1 Review/ Inventory of existing laboratory surveillance systems	6
3.2.2 Needs and gaps analysis laboratory-based reporting.....	7
3.3 RESULTS.....	8
3.3.1 Review/Inventory of existing laboratory surveillance systems	8
3.3.2 Needs and gaps analysis for laboratory-based reporting.....	30
3.4 EVALUATION AND CONCLUSIONS	48
4. TASK 1 – DESCRIPTION OF PILOTS.....	51
4.1 BACKGROUND	51
4.2 SUBTASK 3: OPEN-SOURCE REFERENCE DATA PILOT IN THE NETHERLANDS.....	51
4.3 SUBTASK 4: PILOT IN DENMARK	53
4.4 SUBTASK 5: PILOT IN FINLAND	56
4.5 SUBTASK 6: PILOT IN NORWAY	56
5. TASK 2 – DESCRIPTION OF WORK & MAIN ACHIEVEMENTS	59
5.1 BACKGROUND.....	59
5.2 DESCRIPTION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT	60
5.2.1 Review of outbreak detection activities	60
5.2.2 Benchmarking of outbreak detection methods.....	62
5.2.3 Tool development.....	63
5.3 RESULTS.....	64
5.3.1 Review of outbreak detection activities	64
5.3.2 Benchmarking of outbreak detection methods.....	70
5.3.3 Tool development.....	72
5.4 EVALUATION AND CONCLUSION	75
6. TASK 2 – DESCRIPTIONS OF PILOTS.....	77
6.1 DENMARK.....	77
6.2 FINLAND	78
6.3 HUNGARY	80
6.4 IRELAND	82
6.5 MALTA	84
6.6 THE NETHERLANDS.....	86

6.7 POLAND..... 87

6.8 SLOVENIA 89

7. DEVIATIONS FROM THE WORK PLAN 92

8. REFERENCES 93

9. LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS..... 96

ANNEXES..... 99

1. Executive summary

This deliverable report summarizes the work carried out under Work Package (WP) 2 “Outbreak Detection” during the first ten months for task 1 and the first twelve months for task 2 of the Joint Action UNITED4Surveillance. Additionally, the report describes work that is still planned for the remainder of the project period. WP2 is divided into two tasks: **task 1 “Improving Laboratory-Based Reporting”**, covered in sections 3 and 4, and **task 2 “Outbreak and Signal Detection”**, covered in section 5 and 6.

Section 3.3.1 provides a high-level review/inventory of existing laboratory surveillance systems of seven countries that were active partners in this subtask (Denmark, Finland, Germany, Latvia, Netherlands, Norway and Slovenia). Countries provided information on the context of infectious disease surveillance in their country, described how laboratory-based surveillance is organized and which stakeholders are involved, elaborated on the data flow, reflected on challenges, needs and gaps and gave an outlook on planned developments to improve laboratory-based reporting in their national setting.

Section 3.3.2 entails a description of results from a needs and gaps survey with respect to laboratory-based reporting across 23 countries of the UNITED4Surveillance consortium. The survey focused on general, legal, policy and organizational, technical [data and information technology (IT)], as well as financial aspects of laboratory-based surveillance. Concrete gaps in all surveyed aspects were identified that could be further explored and addressed in the future.

Section 4 describes the scope and status of national pilots that have been initiated in four countries (Denmark, Finland, Netherlands and Norway) with the aim to address previously identified gaps and thereby improve reporting of laboratory-based data. The pilots will be concluded in September 2024.

Section 5.3.1 entails a description of results from a needs and gaps survey regarding automated outbreak detection methods for routine surveillance data of infectious diseases. The survey was jointly developed by national public health institutes in Hungary, Lithuania, Spain and Germany. The survey covered questions on types of surveillance systems with existing automated outbreak detection tools including the methods and an overview of the systems with a potential for automated outbreak detection in 21 countries of the UNITED4Surveillance consortium.

Section 5.3.2 and 5.3.4 provide preliminary results of the evaluation of outbreak detection methods and the tool development process. The tool is developed by data scientists from Austria, Denmark, Finland and Germany as an open source software process on GitHub in form of an R-package that contains a R-shiny app that can be used to perform signal detection on surveillance data.

Section 6 gives a comprehensive overview of the pilot surveillance systems, in which the developed automated outbreak detection tool will be deployed from March 2024 onwards. The pilot countries include Denmark, Finland, Hungary, Ireland, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Slovenia, Latvia, Lithuania and Portugal. The identified use cases are mainly gastroenteritis and respiratory diseases.

2. Description of tasks

The mission of the Joint Action UNITED4Surveillance is to strengthen infectious disease surveillance systems at the national level, by improving integration, interoperability and digitalization of data sources. Forty partners across 24 EU/EEA countries participate in this Joint Action (annex 1).

The Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) pandemic has highlighted that timely sharing of laboratory test results is crucial for an informed response during an unfolding epidemic. Many countries experienced challenges and delays in sharing test results in a timely fashion, for instance due to lack of capacity, fragmented systems, or lack of digitalization (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, 2023a). A specific challenge is the sharing of genetic data due to its complexity.

Infectious disease outbreaks can have a considerable impact on the health and health systems of countries. The timely and accurate detection of such events can help to contain the further spread of disease and reduce harmful consequences. Especially in contexts of limited human resources or high workload, this can contribute to comprehensive surveillance and timely implementation of measures. Many countries do not yet use any methods for automatic outbreak detection or use methods that have been designed for other surveillance systems and datasets than their own. There are also no extensive evaluations of outbreak detection methods for a broad range of surveillance data so that the most accurate methods, strengths and weaknesses of tools guide the choice of the most appropriate one.

To help address these challenges, the objective of WP2 “Outbreak Detection”, is to support outbreak detection and pandemic preparedness by improving real time surveillance for a timelier coordinated response. By improving national surveillance systems, the goal is to strengthen overall surveillance in Europe.

This WP is structured in two main technical tasks, which are further subdivided in subtasks (annex 2):

- Task 1: Improving Laboratory-Based Reporting (sections 3 and 4 of this report)
- Task 2: Outbreak & Signal Detection (sections 5 and 6 of this report)

3. Task 1 – Description of work & main achievements

3.1 Background of the task

Task 1 is structured in six subtasks listed below and in annex 2 with the objectives to a) get an overview of countries' laboratory surveillance systems and make an inventory of the types of challenges countries have experienced with respect to reporting of laboratory data (subtask 1), b) discuss what a logical data model for a sequence database should ideally look like (subtask 2) and c) pilot various approaches to improve national laboratory-based reporting in four countries (subtasks 3-6; sections 4.2-4.5).

Subtask 1: Needs and gap analysis & relation to national policies:

This subtask comprises a description of existing surveillance systems of participating countries, including results from a survey on needs and gaps with respect to legal, policy & organizational, technical and financial aspects of laboratory-based reporting focusing.

Participating institutes/countries: CDPC/LV, FHI/NO, NIJZ/SI, RIVM/NL, RKI/DE, SSI/DK, THL/FI

Preliminary results of work carried out under this subtask have been presented during the Task 1 Kick-Off Workshop on 26 April 2023 in Copenhagen, Denmark that also allowed for online attendance. The objectives of this workshop were:

- *To introduce active partners of WP2/Task 1 & interested listening countries to each other.*
- *To introduce countries' laboratory surveillance systems, including needs & gaps.*
- *To present results from a survey to assess needs and gaps of laboratory-based reporting with respect to legal, policy and organizational, technical (data & IT) and financial aspects.*

Summaries and final results of this work are described in section 3.3.1 and 3.3.2 of this report.

Subtask 2: Data standards

The aim of this subtask is to develop a logical, i.e. theoretical, data model for genotyping/subtyping, covering the range of possible reporting forms and corresponding use cases from molecular detection (PCR) and complete genome sequence to individual allele sequences, as well as relevant classifications based on that. Sequence reads are excluded. The robustness of the data model will be tested using Shiga-toxin producing *E. coli* (STEC) and SARS-CoV-2, as model organism as well as potentially *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (*M. tuberculosis*), influenza and Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR).

Participating institutes/countries: FHI/NO, RIVM/NL, SSI/DK and THL/FI

Within this subtask a technical workshop was held at Statens Serum Institute on 27 April 2023 in Copenhagen/Denmark. The objectives of this workshop were:

- *To present in technical detail one or more laboratory-based surveillance data flows currently operational in active partner countries with emphasis on genotypic data. This includes scope of data elements, data reporting format, databases(s) used, entity-relationship model of stored data, data standards used and use cases for the data. In addition, advantages and disadvantages and lessons learnt - what would you do differently if you could start again – should be presented.*
- *To introduce planned country pilots under UNITED4Surveillance. (section 4 of this report)*
- *To discuss a logical, i.e., theoretical, data model for mainly genotyping/subtyping data, covering the range of possible reporting forms from molecular detection (PCR) and complete genome sequence to individual allele sequences as well as relevant classifications based on that. To discuss linking these data with clinical and epidemiological data. Sequence reads are excluded. Robustness of the data model will be tested using STEC and SARS-CoV-2 variants (potentially *M. tuberculosis*, influenza and AMR).*

The outcome of this subtask (milestone 22) is a report "Logical Data Model for a Sequence Database" that is appended in annex 3.

Subtask 3: Open-source reference data pilot in the Netherlands

Newly developed generic open-source implementation of the logical data model, also including application programming interface (API) and reference data for at least the species used for Subtask 2.

The scope of this pilot is described in section 4.2 of this report.

Subtask 4: Pilot in Denmark

The pilot project in Denmark focuses on integrating microbial properties and molecular level information in a standardized way in the existing Danish Microbiology Database (MiBa). This includes the development of an upgraded data transfer protocol.

The scope of this pilot is described in section 4.3 of this report.

Subtask 5: Pilot in Finland

The focus of the Finnish pilot is on the integration of microbial properties and molecular level information into the Finnish infectious disease surveillance system using STEC as a model pathogen.

The scope of this pilot is described in section 4.4 of this report.

Subtask 6: Pilot in Norway

Development of data management protocol for diagnostic test data on STEC in the MSIS-lab database and explore data transfer protocols for integrated surveillance with the genotypic data in the national reference laboratory database.

The scope of this pilot is described in section 4.5 of this report.

By improving laboratory-based reporting, this task is expected to contribute to specific objective 1 of UNITED4Surveillance "To support outbreak detection and pandemic preparedness by improving real time public health surveillance". This task interlinks with two other tasks of UNITED4Surveillance that both rely on the availability of timely, accurate and high-quality laboratory data: a) Task 2 "Outbreak and Signal Detection" of WP2 (section 5 and 6 of this report) and b) Task 2 "Integrate clinical information on hospitalized patients with microbiological data (typing and microbial resistance), in Member States (MS) using nation-wide register-based public health surveillance" of WP3 "Hospital surveillance / Surveillance of Severe Infectious Diseases that Lead to Hospitalization".

3.2 Description of the work carried out

This section of the deliverable report describes work carried out under Subtask 1. To review existing laboratory surveillance systems including needs and gaps, information was collected through two different methods described hereafter:

3.2.1 Review/ Inventory of existing laboratory surveillance systems

Seven countries were active partners within subtask 1 (Denmark, Finland, Germany, Latvia, Netherlands, Norway and Slovenia). Active partners were provided with a structured presentation template covering key aspects of their respective laboratory surveillance system. Presentations were given during a hybrid Kick-Off Workshop of Task 1 that took place on 26 April 2023 in Copenhagen, Denmark and online. Section 3.3.1 shows narrative

summaries of the presentations. Summaries included in this report were reviewed and supplemented by the presenters.

3.2.2 Needs and gaps analysis laboratory-based reporting

We conducted a survey to investigate the needs and gaps and types of challenges countries have been facing with respect to laboratory-based reporting (survey template in Annex 4).

Survey development and tool

To get an overview of the aspects of laboratory-based surveillance that were of particular interest to countries, we prepared the content of the survey with participants of WP2 during the Kick-Off Meeting of UNITED4Surveillance on 15 February 2023. A live poll was used to collect input on legal, policy and organizational, technical (data & IT) and financial aspects. Subsequently, a first draft was developed and presented to participating countries on 21 February 2023. Countries had the opportunity to provide feedback orally and in writing. To build on previous work and ensure alignment, we also reviewed the latest “Bi-annual survey from the European Union Laboratory Capability (EULabCap) Monitoring” conducted by the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, 2020) and the “Survey on Mapping Digitalization and Integration of Surveillance Systems Across Europe” commissioned by the European Commission (EC). The finalized survey was implemented in the EUSurvey platform.

Scope of the survey

The scope of the survey encompassed the process from data acquisition at the local level, i.e. in clinical microbiology laboratories, to data storage, data cleaning and linking laboratory data to other data sources at the national level, i.e. within the National Institute for Public Health. Both notifiable and non-notifiable diseases were included in the survey. For notifiable diseases, we used diseases listed under the European Union (EU) case definitions by the ECDC (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, 2018). To assess laboratory-based surveillance capacities in participating countries, we used pathogens listed in the ECDC strategic framework for the integration of molecular and genomic typing into European surveillance and multi-country outbreak investigations (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, 2019) and supplemented the list with SARS-CoV-2. This corresponded to a total of 21 pathogens.

The survey consisted of 30 main questions in mainly single or multiple-choice format, followed by optional sub-questions in free text format to provide more details (Annex 4). Of the main questions, 26 were mandatory. The survey structure entailed the five following sections: 1) general, 2) legal, 3) policy and organizational, 4) technical (data and IT) and 5) financial aspects of the laboratory surveillance systems in participating countries.

Definitions used

To ensure a common understanding of the terms used in the survey, we provided the following definitions to participants:

- National Institute for Public Health (NIPH): National authority or agency responsible for public health surveillance of infectious diseases
- Local laboratories: Clinical laboratories that perform diagnostics of infectious diseases.
- Lab surveillance (data): Samples and/or data on samples taken from human subjects stored by local laboratories that can be used for the purpose of public health surveillance of communicable diseases. This contains data on laboratory tests as well as selected clinical or epidemiological data as available.
- National reference laboratory (NRL) not at NIPH: National reference laboratory that is not part of the NIPH and performs additional diagnostics of infectious diseases that are not normally performed by local laboratories. NRLs that are part of the NIPH are not considered as a separate category, but instead considered as the NIPH itself.

- Lab-surveillance data sharing: In this context, “Lab-surveillance data sharing” refers to the sharing of lab surveillance data by local laboratories with the NIPH, either directly or indirectly via e.g. a local or regional public health authority or national reference laboratory (in case the latter is not at the NIPH).
- GDPR – General Data Protection Regulation (“General Data Protection Regulation,” 2016).

Data collection, validation and analysis

On 13 March 2023, the survey was distributed to one selected country contact point of all 25 countries that were part of the consortium of UNITED4Surveillance at the time of circulation. The country contact point was requested to forward the survey to another colleague, if they felt that another person was better suited to coordinate and fill in the survey. For awareness and potential facilitation, ECDC also forwarded the survey invitation to National Focal Points (NFPs) for Surveillance and NFPs for Microbiology of invited countries. The initial deadline was set to 2 April 2023, followed by an extension until 12 April.

Survey responses were validated through validation rules and personal follow-up of the survey organizers with participants to clarify inconsistencies in responses. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize results (in Excel and R, version 4.3.1). Figures were created in Python using the pandas 1.5.2, matplotlib 3.6.2 and seaborn 0.12.2 Python open-source packages.

Preliminary survey results from 23 countries were presented during the above-mentioned Kick-Off Workshop of Task 1 on 26 April 2023. Following the workshop, a second data validation round was conducted between 3-10 May 2023 and based on feedback received data were re-analysed.

3.3 Results

3.3.1 *Review/Inventory of existing laboratory surveillance systems*

Denmark

Context

The following key stakeholders are involved in infectious disease preparedness and response in Denmark: The **Ministry of the Interior and Health (MoIH)** is responsible for promoting and strengthening the cohesion of health and welfare in Denmark.

The following authorities and institutes operate under the auspices of the MoIH:

The **Danish Health Authority** constitutes the supreme health authority and is responsible for national health emergency preparedness, risk management and the development of guidelines. The **Danish Patient Safety Authority** conducts local risk and outbreak management and performs contact tracing. The **SSI**, as the national public health institute, is responsible for conducting surveillance, risk assessment, outbreak investigations, research and providing advice to authorities. The core responsibilities of the **Danish Medicines Agency** are drug approval, monitoring side effects and ensuring sufficient drug supply. The **Danish Health Data Authority** is responsible for standardization and coherence of the Danish IT infrastructure, steering of national level IT projects and providing data support. For zoonotic diseases requiring a One Health approach, the **Ministry of Food Agriculture of Fisheries** and the subordinate **Danish Veterinary and Food Administration** are additional key stakeholders.

The SSI is organized in four technical pillars: 1) Epidemiological Infectious Disease Preparedness, 2) Diagnostic Infectious Disease Preparedness, 3) Biobank, Digital Infrastructure and High-Capacity Diagnostics and 4) the Centre for Vaccine Research. An additional separate entity, the Centre for Biosecurity and Biopreparedness, is positioned under the management board. Routine surveillance activities primarily fall under pillar 1 and 2.

Organization of laboratory-based surveillance

Since the year 2000, laboratory-based surveillance and individual clinical notifications have been conducted in Denmark. In the initial years, laboratory-based surveillance was paper-based. In 2008, the Danish Ministry of Health approved the development of the Danish Microbiology Database (MiBa) and later in 2011 also the Hospital Acquired Infections Database (HAIBA). In 2010, MiBa was launched which allowed electronic reporting of laboratory-test results from Clinical Microbiology Laboratories (CMLs) to SSI. In 2015, HAIBA was launched. HAIBA is a national automated surveillance system for hospital-acquired infections that automatically links microbiology data from MiBa and data from the Danish National Patient Register. HAIBA monitors five indicators: 1) urinary tract infections, 2) bacteremia, 3) *Clostridioides difficile* infections and surgical site infections after 4) hip & 5) knee replacements. As of 2020, MiBa became the cornerstone of the COVID-19 surveillance system in Denmark. In the same year, Test Centre Denmark (Statens Serum Institut, 2023c) was launched to respond during the increased need for testing during the SARS-CoV-2 epidemic.

MiBa is hosted and managed by the interdisciplinary Department of Data Integration and Analysis (DIAS) at SSI, which falls under technical pillar 1 mentioned above. The objectives of MiBa are:

- To establish a real-time surveillance system that receives microbiology results electronically
- To ensure flexible & complete data to reduce manual data entry mistakes
- To strengthen patient treatment, by providing nationwide access to lab-reports for health care personnel and patients
- To facilitate data linkage with other national databases/ registers

Denmark is organized in five regions. Across the regions, there are ten CMLs. SSI hosts various National Reference Laboratories. In 2020, the Danish Veterinary Consortium, consisting of SSI and the University of Copenhagen, was established to – among others – conduct surveillance and diagnostics for infectious diseases affecting livestock, including zoonoses, under the umbrella of One Health (University of Copenhagen, 2023).

The ten CMLs are strongly involved in the managing and further developing of MiBa. They are represented in a steering committee, a board of representatives and a number of working groups. The ten CMLs report laboratory results to MiBa. For SARS-CoV-2, Test Centre Denmark and private test providers also reported to MiBa.

Reporting flow for laboratory-based surveillance

Figure 1 shows the reporting flow for laboratory-based surveillance in Denmark. In short, physicians make an electronic requisition via the system WebReq and samples are sent to the CMLs, laboratories at SSI or Test Center Denmark (in case of SARS-CoV-2 during the epidemic) for laboratory analyses. Once the laboratory results are ready, they are transferred real-time via the Danish Health Data Network to the requesting physician and a copy gets sent to and stored in MiBa, which – after further processing – can be used for (automated) surveillance.

Figure 1. Reporting Flow for Laboratory-Based Surveillance in Denmark

Challenges

Legal

- Discrepancies in rules and judgements in terms of aggregation/ anonymization of data hamper data sharing across authorities.
- Cross-regional data sharing challenging due to data protection reasons.
- Balance between Act on Public Disclosure in Administration and Data Protection Law is skewed. I.e. less detailed data for surveillance purposes can be shared compared to the level of detail that SSI is obliged to deliver to citizens requesting them.

Technical

- Coherence and dependencies
 - The automated surveillance system draws on linking real-time laboratory results from MiBa with various other national registers, which e.g. have varying timeliness leading to technical challenges.
- Complexity
 - Since multiple stakeholders are involved in implementing technical changes, this can be a complex and time-consuming process.

Financial

- The COVID-19 pandemic bolstered funding. However, the future funding situation is less clear.

Human resources

- Acquisition, training & retaining of employees:
 - The maintenance and further development of the automated surveillance system requires professionals from different backgrounds, particularly IT and data analytics specialists, which are in high demand in all lines of industries and therefore scarce.
 - Due to the complexity of the system and the necessity of deep knowledge of the data, it takes a significant time investment to train newly hired staff.
 - Similarly, as National Institute for Public Health, it is challenging to compete with salaries offered to IT and legal specialists by the private sector.
- Diverse backgrounds
 - Since employees involved in the automated surveillance system come from different backgrounds, close collaboration, translation and bridge-building is required to ensure interdisciplinary understanding/ cross-learning.

Needs and gaps

- Limited clinical & epidemiological data shared together with lab-results:
- The clinical notification system, "*Meldesystemet for infektionssygdomme*" (MIS), is a separate system and it is planned to link MIS-data and MiBa-data. Codes for laboratory-reporting
 - The plan is to replace the use of local codes with national and international classifications and terminologies.
- Lack of data from primary care/ municipality settings. Based on the Danish strategy to shift as much health care as possible to primary care/home care, data from hospital care will become less representative leading to the following gaps:
 - Lack of data on diagnoses (diagnosis codes)
 - Diagnostic tests performed in primary case

Planned developments

SSI will focus on further digitalization and automation over the coming years to 1) strengthen surveillance and make surveillance more robust, 2) meet the future requirements for infectious disease preparedness and 3) meet international and national requirements for monitoring and reporting.

The following specific projects are planned or in progress:

- **Legal projects:**
 - Revision of the Danish Health Act
- **Improve / expand in-data**
 - Integrate the Laboratory Database (LABA) into MiBa to also include biochemical and immunological results, in addition to microbiology results
 - Integration of updated national transfer protocol "*XRPT06 M32*" in MiBa to allow standardized reporting of microbial properties and molecular level information (see section 4.3)
 - Integrate Whole genome sequencing (WGS) data into MiBa
- **Improve data structure and make MiBa data ready for automation**
 - Develop national classifications for microbiology results
 - Increase functionality in Keys to Infectious Disease System (KIDS phase 3), a system that standardizes raw data from MiBa so that it can be used for automated surveillance
 - Develop case definitions in KIDS for all notifiable diseases
 - Broader/further implementation of national sample-identifiers on all laboratory-samples across all medical laboratory specialties
- **Digital transformation program**
 - The COVID-19 epidemic led to new use of data by internal and external stakeholders. The pandemic bolstered funding, supporting final implementation of ongoing projects e.g. the digitalization of clinical notifications and expansion of MiBa with antimicrobial resistance data, WGS and LABA. Similarly, the One Health focus, as one of the strategic pillars of SSI, opens new opportunities.
 - The digital transformation program consists of five pillars:
 - 1) New use of data and future-oriented solutions
 - 2) Robust, automated surveillance
 - 3) Visualization and publication
 - 4) Signal detection (among others carried out in this work package; see section 5)
 - 5) Governance of preparedness

Finland

Context

Key stakeholders in infectious disease control in Finland are organized at the national and regional level. National stakeholders comprise the Ministry of Social Affairs and Health, the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL, i.e. the Finnish National Institute for Public Health), the Finnish Institute of Occupational Health (TTL) and the Finnish Food Safety Authority. At the regional level, Finland is organized in seven Regional State Administrative Regions, 24 Wellbeing Services Counties (before 2023 called Healthcare Districts), ~20 Clinical Microbiology Laboratories (CML) (both public and private) and 309 municipalities.

THL serves as an expert institute of infectious disease control, monitors the status of infectious diseases, provides advice and guidelines in the health field, supports regional health services and conducts research on and develops diagnostics for infectious diseases. THL has 1300 employees and is organized in three horizontal technical themes: 1) Public Health and Welfare, 2) Health Security and 3) Government Services. Under theme 2, two units "Infectious Disease Control and Vaccinations" and "Expert Microbiology", comprising about 200 employees, are involved in laboratory-based surveillance in Finland.

Organization of laboratory-based surveillance

The National Infectious Disease Register (NIDR) is operational since 1995 and has been continuously developed since. In 2004, NIDR underwent major changes including the implementation of social security number (a number which specified an individual person) and mandatory sample referral requiring clinical microbiology laboratories to send samples or isolates to National Reference Laboratories. NIDR also had to be adapted in line with the transition to advanced laboratory methods, e.g. from using culture and phenotyping-based methods to polymerase-chain reaction (PCR)-based diagnostics and eventually WGS, which has been in use as of 2016.

Laboratory-based surveillance in Finland is organized between CMLs and National Reference Laboratories (NRL). CMLs are responsible for reporting diagnostic test results to NIDR and for sending microbial strains and samples to NRLs. The NRLs are part of THL and are responsible for examining samples, perform further typing of isolates and monitoring trends.

The laboratory-based surveillance comprises the following systems:

NIDR

NIDR constitutes the main tool for collecting laboratory-based surveillance data in Finland. It comprises laboratory-based data combined with clinical and (limited) epidemiological data. Laboratory surveillance results consist of analysis results provided by both clinical laboratories and reference laboratories in THL. THL maintains NIDR based on the Communicable Diseases Act (Sosiaali- ja terveystieteiden ministeriö, 2016) and Decree (Sosiaali- ja terveystieteiden ministeriö, 2017).

Approximately 100,000 cases of infectious diseases are reported to the NIDR each year. Data are collected to the register using communicable disease notifications filed by physicians and laboratories. The register data are used for the prevention of infectious diseases, monitoring trends and research (e.g. register linkage studies). The notifiable diseases are categorized in three categories: 1) generally hazardous communicable diseases, 2) communicable diseases to be monitored and 3) other notifiable diseases. All microbes detected in blood and cerebrospinal fluid are also notifiable. All notifiable diseases are listed in the Government Decree on Communicable Diseases (Sosiaali- ja terveystieteiden ministeriö, 2017).

Disease-specific monitoring systems

Disease-specific monitoring systems comprise the Influenza and other respiratory virus surveillance system (sentinel), the Norovirus surveillance system and the Rotavirus surveillance system.

Surveillance of Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR): Finnish Study Group for Antimicrobial Resistance (FiRe)

FiRe is a collaborative body based on voluntariness. The group includes Finnish clinical microbiology laboratories and THL. FiRe was established in 1992 and one of its first objectives was to harmonise the methods used for determining drug susceptibility of diagnostic bacterial findings in Finland. In 2011, all FiRe laboratories transitioned to using the European EUCAST standard. The FiRe group produces annually a Finres report (Terveyden ja hyvinvoinnin laitos, 2021) which comprehensively describes the bacterial resistance situation and its development in Finland for each past ten years. The report brings together antimicrobial sensitivity data routinely produced by clinical microbiology laboratories and THL's Mycobacterial Laboratory every year. The resistance monitoring data in the Finres report mainly consists of the resistance data of bacteria isolated from clinical infections.

Surveillance of Healthcare-Associated Infections: Finnish Hospital Infection Programme (SIRO)

SIRO develops monitoring of infections and collects information on their occurrence in participating hospitals. Hospitals participating in the program can compare their own prevalence rates with those of other hospitals. The aims of the SIRO program are: prevention of treatment-related infections, development of monitoring and feedback, creation of common definitions and methods for monitoring, providing prevalence figures for use by hospitals, common control instructions and recommendations, hospital epidemic investigations, training and course activities, and research. This surveillance monitors e.g., surgical site infections, *Clostridium difficile*, nosocomial bloodstream infections.

Wastewater monitoring

Wastewater monitoring is operational for coronavirus and poliovirus in Finland. For coronavirus monitoring the amount of virus is examined by measuring RNA in untreated wastewater. Monitoring covers approximately 44 % of wastewater produced by the Finnish population. The results are reported weekly on THL web page (Terveyden ja hyvinvoinnin laitos, 2023a). Also, proportions of different coronavirus variants are monitored by genome sequencing in Finland (Terveyden ja hyvinvoinnin laitos, 2023b).

Reporting flow for laboratory-based surveillance

Figure 2 shows the reporting flow into NIDR. Green arrows indicate the flow of data, which end up at National Infectious Disease Register. Red arrows indicate feedback from THL to data providers, such as isolate-specific test results from the reference laboratory to clinical laboratory, reported case-based or aggregated data specific to Wellbeing Service Counties or requests for additional information to notifications. The blue arrow indicates data flow from THL Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS) to the National Infectious Disease Register.

Figure 2. Data flow into the National Infectious Disease Register (NIDR) and linkage with other registers in Finland

Challenges

Influenza and other respiratory virus surveillance system requires development: Sending respiratory virus specimen to reference laboratories or any other laboratory is only possible if informed consent is given. However, this procedure is considered laborious, which leads to limited sending of samples and results in limited surveillance of respiratory pathogens. To address this challenge, the current legislation will be reviewed, but changes may be difficult to achieve.

Data sharing: At THL, samples receive microbe identification (ID) codes upon arrival at the NRL. A THL decision from June 2020 has outlined that microbe identification codes are not personal data and therefore do not fall under the GDPR. This allows THL to use the same microbe identification (ID) codes in communication when sharing e.g. sequence data outside THL. The identifier is not reported back to clinical laboratories to prevent that the identifier and sequence are combined and deposited in a public database.

Needs and gaps

For several pathogens, more laboratory results are available than what are currently reported to THL (i.e. NIDR) by CMLs and by THL (i.e. NRL) back to CMLs, e.g., typing results for Shiga-toxin-producing *E. Coli* (STEC) and Salmonella. In addition, no structural collection of epidemiological data (e.g. symptoms, farm contact etc.) is currently done.

To address these gaps, electronic send-reply communication via the Health Level 7 standard (Health Level Seven International, 2023b) will be implemented, which allows more comprehensive notification of laboratory results from CMLs to the national level (NIDR). This allows for more information to be transferred from NIDR to the LIMS of THL-based NRLs. In LIMS, the "Epidemic view" could be used for structural collection of epidemiological data and be combined with laboratory data. This will be a new way of organizing and sharing data between THL microbiologists and epidemiologist, both having access to information needed in outbreak investigations. Previously this kind of data was organized in excel format.

Planned developments

Plans to update THL's surveillance strategy

This update is envisaged to mirror ECDC's strategy (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, 2018, 2023b) map the needs for change and comprise an inventory of areas to which limited resources will be allocated to.

Technical renovation of NIDR

The entire technical infrastructure of NIDR was renovated and set in production since 3rd October 2023. No changes in contents were included at this phase. NIDR is now standardized with other forms of THL data production and registers by using the same tools and platforms as appropriate. Renovation included unifying servers (PostgreSQL (The PostgreSQL Global Development Group, 2023) servers) and xml-versions, and improved data security, timeliness as well as register linkages. Also, further development and troubleshooting was reorganized. Feedback from NIDR users is currently collected. Next developments will focus on contents of the NIDR. These are largely still under discussion.

Development of a new LIMS system at THL

THL is currently transitioning from an in-house to a commercial LIMS system (LabVantage 8.8 (LabVantage Solutions, 2023)). With the new system, as mentioned above, the HL7 standard will replace paper-based referral forms and allows using the "Epidemic View" for structural collection of epidemiological and combination with laboratory data. The new system is expected to be in production in Quarter 3, 2024.

Germany

Context

In Germany, the following key stakeholders are involved in applied laboratory surveillance: the Robert Koch Institute (RKI), i.e. the National Institute for Public Health in Germany, state public health authorities (which provide advice to local public health authorities), local public health authorities (which receive infectious disease notifications and conduct surveillance at the local level), and laboratories (which notify infectious diseases according to the Infection Protection Act) (§7, §9, § 10 ;("Infektionsschutzgesetz - IfSG," 2000). More than 1000 laboratories provide diagnostics, supported and advised by National Reference Laboratories (NRL) or Consiliary Laboratories (CL) (Laude et al., 2012b). The RKI and the 16 state public health authorities are subordinate to the respective health ministries and advise them.

RKI is responsible for conducting surveillance at the national level and advises health authorities on state and local levels. Within RKI, the Department for Infectious Diseases is responsible for infectious disease surveillance systems and employs experts with pathogen-specific expertise.

The Infection Protection Act constitutes a federal law that regulates infectious disease surveillance in Germany. It entered into force in 2001 and has been periodically revised since. Since 2001, RKI provides a free software *SurvNet@RKI* for the public health authorities, a software that allows the transmission of case information from the local public health authorities, via the state public health authorities to the RKI (Faensen et al., 2006). Since 2020, also the notification from the laboratories to the local public health authorities was digitalized by implementing the German Electronic Reporting and Information System for Infection Control (*Deutsches Elektronisches Melde- und Informationssystem für den Infektionsschutz; DEMIS*), first covering the electronic reporting of SARS-CoV-2 notifications from laboratories to the local health authorities during the pandemic (Diercke et al., 2021) and since 2022 the notifications of other notifiable pathogens (Figure 3). Starting in 2024 DEMIS will be used to transmit whole genome sequence data to the RKI to implement an integrated genomic surveillance (IGS) system. DEMIS uses the Health Level 7 (HL7) Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) standard for the electronic exchange of healthcare information (Health Level Seven International, 2023a). For the coding of pathogens, material and laboratory methods in DEMIS, the international standards Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes (LOINC) (Regenstrief Institute, 2023) and the Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine Clinical Terms (SNOMED) are used (SNOMED International, 2023).

Figure 3. Overview of the German Electronic Reporting and Information System for Infection Control (DEMIS) Since 2022, notification of pathogen detection is mandatory via DEMIS. Laboratories primarily use the DEMIS interface for notifications.

Organization of laboratory-based surveillance

Figure 4 shows the organization of the laboratory-based surveillance in Germany. Depending on the pathogen, defined in the Infection Protection Act, §§ 9 and 10 IfSG, laboratories report results either directly to the national level (RKI), or indirectly via the local public health authorities.

The NRLs, complemented by CLs, are considered national centres of excellence in the field of laboratory science for a particular pathogen or group of pathogens (Laude et al., 2012a). Essential evaluation criteria for the selection process are focused on public health needs, successful network activities, attestable quality assurance, publications as well as a positive appraisal of the further development of diagnostic procedures.

The RKI invites tenders for the assignment of an NRL and CL, obtains expert opinions, and the Scientific Advisory Board for Public Health Microbiology makes its recommendation. The RKI then decides on a laboratory, proposes this to the Ministry of Health, which appoints the laboratory. Currently, 21 NRLs and 39 CLs are appointed. Out of these, 5 NRLs and 13 CLs are situated at the RKI.

Laboratory notifications
 §7 (1): e.g. Measles virus, Sars-CoV-2
 §7 (3): e.g. HIV, *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*

Physician notifications
 §6

Figure 4. Organization of Laboratory-Based Surveillance in Germany

Reporting flow for laboratory-based surveillance

Figure 5 shows the reporting flow for laboratory-based surveillance in Germany. Laboratories report to local public health authorities via DEMIS. Laboratory notifications only contain results and sample information. Information exchange between laboratories and NRLs is paper-based. As of 2024, NRLs share IGS data directly with RKI via DEMIS.

Upon reception of notifications, local public health authorities link notifications from laboratories and physicians, gather additional information, if necessary, perform data cleaning and store the data. Local public health authorities subsequently share information with RKI at the national level via SurvNet@RKI. RKI is responsible for further data cleaning, linkage to sequence data and data storage.

Figure 5. Reporting flow for laboratory-based surveillance in Germany. (IGS, integrated genomic surveillance)

Challenges

- The implementation of the new electronic notification system (DEMIS) for laboratories and physicians resulted in changes and challenges in reporting in terms of changes of routine processes (what and when to report), challenges in implementing the interface between Laboratory/ Hospital information system and DEMIS according to the specifications and also requires changes in routines at local public health authority level and implementation of quality assurance measures at national public health institute level.
- Limited human resources, both at the local and national level, to manage the new routines and requirements hamper the acceptance of the new reporting system and the implementation of other surveillance components.
- Furthermore, development and synchronization with other digitalization processes in Germany (e.g. electronic medical records) are challenging.
- Strict regulations on data protection: Since data that is shared between laboratories and local public health authorities fall under special categories of personal data the storage of data is strictly regulated. This might lead to challenges with data quality and matching with other data sources is not possible.

Planned developments

Future plans will focus on further expanding DEMIS to include physician’s notification according to § 6 IfSG, integrated genomic surveillance, surveillance of outbreaks and different surveillance tools, like acute respiratory sentinel surveillance or antibiotic resistance surveillance.

Latvia

Context

Key stakeholders for infectious disease surveillance in Latvia involve the Ministry of Health, Clinical Laboratories, National Reference Laboratories, Clinicians, Hospitals, Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (CDPC) of Latvia, the food and veterinary service, the National Health Service and municipalities.

The CDPC was established in 2012 and is subordinate to the Ministry of Health. CDPC took over functions of nine institutions in the field of communicable and non-communicable diseases. CDPC’s mission is to implement national public health policy in the field of epidemiological safety, disease prevention and health promotion. CDPC is organized in four departments: 1) the Research and Health Statistics Department, 2) the Health

Promotion Department, 3) the Human Resources Department 4) and the Infectious Disease, Risk Analysis and Prevention Department. Within the latter department the Infectious Disease Surveillance and Immunization unit is responsible for infectious disease surveillance in Latvia. In addition, CDPC has eight regional units, which are responsible for notifiable infection diseases investigation, local outbreak investigation, outbreak management, communication with local media, GPs, hospitals, labs.

Organization of laboratory-based surveillance

Laboratory-based surveillance in Latvia is based on the national legislation Cabinet Regulation Nr. 7 (Cabinet of Ministers, 1999). The regulation lays out which infectious diseases are notifiable, as well as methods and materials to be used for surveillance. Laboratory-based surveillance is nation-wide and involves all laboratories (clinical laboratories, one National Reference Laboratory and private laboratories). The National Reference Laboratory is hosted by the biggest Latvian hospital, Riga East Clinical University Hospital. The functions of the National Reference Laboratory are described in the Cabinet Regulation Nr. 125 section III – Rights and Obligations of the Reference Laboratory ("Regulation No. 125 Regarding the Procedures for Granting and Cancellation of the Status of the National Reference Laboratory in the Field of Epidemiological Safety or Suspension of the Operation Thereof, and also Regarding the Rights and Obligations of the National Reference Laboratory," 2017).

Hospital and private laboratories are required to send samples and/or isolates of certain pathogens to reference laboratories for confirmation and/or send samples and/or isolates for analysis if specialized equipment is required. For example, after isolation of *Salmonella*, *Shigella*, *Yersinia*, *Campylobacter*, *Listeria*, *STEC* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*¹ from a culture based on human sample material, as well as isolating the abovementioned agents from any sample taken within the scope of epidemiological investigation or epidemiological monitoring, the microbiology laboratory must perform further typing, e.g. the serotype for *Salmonella*, *Shigella*, *Yersinia*, *Listeria*, *STEC* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* cultures and cultures of *Campylobacter* species. If there are no technical possibilities of determining the serotype or species of the agent at the microbiology laboratory, the culture of the isolated agent must be sent for detailed investigation to the National Reference Laboratory.

Reporting flow for laboratory-based surveillance

According to the national legislation, all laboratories should notify all detected pathogens that are mentioned in the Cabinet Regulation Nr 7 Annex 3 to one of the regional CDPCs. When a notifiable pathogen is detected, laboratories should send an urgent reporting form ("Steidzamais paziņojums par infekcijas slimību, infekcijas slimības izraisītāja konstatēšanu, rezistentu mikroorganismu izdalīšanu un vakcinācijas izraisītu komplikāciju (blakusparādību) - 24.pielikums noteikumiem Nr.265," 2006) by fax, by post, by courier or electronically (e-mail, electronical notification system) to the CDPC regional units, as well as inform the regional CDPC by phone within a certain time period, depending on the reporting requirements and the category the detected pathogen falls under, as specified in the Cabinet Regulation.

Figure 6 shows the reporting flow of laboratory-based surveillance in Latvia with *Streptococcus pneumoniae* as an example. Upon pathogen detection, the hospital laboratories report the finding to one of the eight regional CDPC through post, fax, email or by phone. The regional CDPC collects additional epidemiological information, links laboratory and epidemiological information and shares the information with the national CDPC through the State Infectious Disease Surveillance and Monitoring system (VISUMS). The national CDPC collects all received information in one database, verifies the data, requests correction if needed, prepares surveillance reports and is responsible for international data sharing with the ECDC and WHO.

¹ In case of *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, isolates need to be submitted if retrieved from cerebrospinal fluid or other usually sterile clinical material.

As mentioned above, in case of lack of equipment for serotyping or in case of detection of specific pathogens, which should be sent for confirmation, regional hospital laboratories also share isolates with the NRL for confirmation and further characterization, e.g. serotyping, antibiotic susceptibility testing etc. Subsequently, NRLs share additional laboratory results with the regional CDPCs and the requesting laboratories through post, fax, e-mail, courier or by phone.

Figure 6. Reporting flow for laboratory-based surveillance in Latvia using *Streptococcus pneumoniae* as an example.

Challenges

Technical challenges

- Insufficiently developed IT system
- Lack of an API between systems

Financial challenges

- Lack of financing for developing IT system and API

Underreporting

- Not all detected notifiable pathogens are currently reported to the CDPC

Human resources

- Lack of human resources in the laboratories to provide notifications, which are paper-based.

Needs and gaps

A technical challenge is that there is currently no automated connection between the laboratory and epidemiological system, therefore data integration relies on manual linkage and manual data sharing. Similarly, there is no automated connection between the hospital laboratory systems and the NRLs. To address the latter challenge, it is planned to develop an API between hospital, private and reference laboratories to phase out paper-based reporting.

Planned developments

- Future work will concentrate on improving the mode of reporting of laboratory results by developing web-based reporting forms, as well as machine-to-machine reporting for notification from the laboratories and clinicians to the regional CDPC.
- Developing a new epidemiological surveillance system. Development of the first part (basic for COVID-19) is finished. It is planned to start working in the new system from 1 December 2023 with COVID-19. Development of the remaining functionality is planned from 2025.

Netherlands

Context

Key stakeholders of infectious disease surveillance in the Netherlands include the Ministry of Health, the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (*Rijksinstituut Voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu, RIVM*), 25 Municipal Health Services (MHS) and 60 MMLs. For foodborne and zoonotic diseases, additional stakeholders include the Netherlands Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority under the Ministry of Agriculture Nature and Food Quality, the Royal GD (an organization focused on animal health and production) and the research institute Wageningen Bioveterinary Research.

The RIVM is grouped into three domains: 1) Centre for Infectious Disease Control, 2) Environment and Safety and 3) Public Health and Health Services. The Centre for Infectious Disease control is further subdivided in five centers of which 2 and 3 play a role in infectious disease surveillance: 1) National Coordination Centre for Communicable Disease Control, 2) Infectious Diseases, Epidemiology and Surveillance, 3) Infectious Disease Research, Diagnostics and Laboratory Surveillance, 4) Zoonoses and Environmental Microbiology and 5) Immunology of Infectious Diseases and Vaccines.

Organization of laboratory-based surveillance

For 19 (groups of) reportable infectious diseases reference laboratory tasks have been established. These reference tasks are executed by seven MML's and the RIVM. Reference laboratories outside of RIVM report their surveillance data to RIVM. At present, the organization of laboratory surveillance is different per pathogen. MMLs either send (PCR) positive samples to RIVM for sequencing or perform their own sequencing and send the resulting sequences to the RIVM. Data are sent via paper forms, as files by email, via batch upload tools, via webforms, machine to machine via HL7 messages or uploaded to a File Transfer Protocol (FTP) server. At the moment, the RIVM uses many different databases for the surveillance of infectious diseases (Table 1).

Table 1. Examples of Databases Used for the Surveillance of Infectious Diseases in the Netherlands

Database	Purpose & functionalities
Osiris	Internal database for notifiable infectious diseases reported to the RIVM by the MHSs (Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu, 2023b). Notifications are entered via webforms.
Molecular platform	Online platform for sharing sequence data. This entails databases and typing tools per pathogen and laboratory network (both national and international) and provides tools for analysis and visualization for contributing laboratories. Data can be reported via webform or via a batch upload functionality as comma-separated values (csv) file and FASTA file.
Nonacris	Internal database developed in-house for storing SARS-CoV-2 sequences from all sequencing laboratories. A connected dashboard is available within RIVM for analysis of the data. A local version of Nextstrain (Callisto-web) is used to analyze the sequences and draft trees and geographical maps of the data for online display for MML's and MHS's. MML's contribute by sending their data via email.
BioNumerics	Internal database for storing and analyzing genetic profiles and sequences of many pathogens for which RIVM performs sequencing.
ISIS-AR	ISIS-AR stands for "Infectious Disease Surveillance Information System – Antimicrobial Resistance" (<i>Infectieziekten Surveillance Informatie Systeem-Antibiotica Resistentie</i>) (Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu, 2021). This constitutes an internal database in which MML's report their antimicrobial resistance data. The

	MML's send their data via HL7. There is also an online part: ISIS-Web, with visualizations of the data for the MML's.
Type-Ned	Type-Ned stands for "Typing Network Netherlands" (<i>Typeringsnetwerk Nederland</i>) (Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu, 2022). On this online platform, laboratories can register Methicillin-Resistant Staphylococcus Aureus (MRSA) and Carbapenemase Producing Enterobacteriaceae (CPE) isolates they want to send in for sequencing at RIVM and where they can look up the results

[Reporting flow for laboratory-based surveillance](#)

Depending on the pathogen (group), there are different reporting flows for laboratory-based surveillance in the Netherlands. For the surveillance of phenotypic AMR data, MMLs used to send a monthly extract from their LIMS data to RIVM via email. More and more laboratories are now transitioning to machine-to-machine reporting via HL7.

For MRSA and CPE isolates are sent to the RIVM for sequencing. Before sending the isolate, the laboratories register the isolate, supplemented with a set of clinical and epidemiological data, in a webform in the Type-Ned system. The Type-Ned system generates a barcode sticker which is put on the isolate before it is sent by the MML. Results of the sequencing analysis can be viewed by the MML after logging in into the Type-Ned system.

For the virologic weekly reports, a representative selection of 20 MMLs report positive detections of viruses to the RIVM via e-mail. The reports contain around 40 different viruses, all viruses for which the labs perform diagnostic tests. These are aggregated reports of numbers of possible diagnoses per week, without information on the method of testing or information about the patients. A weekly overview of the collected data is available via the RIVM website.

For the sentinel surveillance of respiratory viruses, general practitioners (GPs) that participate in the sentinel surveillance, organized by the Netherlands Institute for Health Services Research (Nivel), send respiratory samples to the RIVM for analysis every week. The samples are tested for respiratory viruses and, among others, samples positive for SARS-CoV2 and Influenza viruses are sequenced. Results are reported back to Nivel and also used in the national and international molecular laboratory surveillance by RIVM.

For the surveillance of foodborne bacterial diseases, raw data derived from Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) are shared with RIVM via a FTP server.

For the laboratory surveillance of several pathogens the Molecular Platform (MPF) software is used. There is a MPF database for enteroviruses and parechoviruses, in which Dutch laboratories share sequences and a set of contextual data on enteroviruses and parechoviruses for surveillance. Another MPF database has been set up for the sharing of swine influenza viruses, for a pilot in which samples are collected from pig farms in the Netherlands in order to get insight into the circulating variants. Several international laboratory networks also use the MPF to share sequences. There are sequence databases for norovirus, hepatitis A virus and hepatitis E virus.

For a number of pathogens, the laboratory surveillance only uses sequences generated by the RIVM. Here the data storage and analysis take place in in-house tools. For most pathogens the commercial BioNumerics program is used for this, but, for example for the molecular surveillance of TB, a dedicated database and analysis tool has been developed in RIVM.

For SARS-CoV-2, various reporting flows have been implemented: 1) a self-sampling program for SARS-CoV-2 among the general population for which RIVM performs sequencing, 2) a sequencing network consisting of several laboratories, both MML's and private labs, that send in samples or report sequencing data to RIVM via e-mail and 3) SARS-CoV-2 cases that are reported by the Municipal Health Services to the RIVM via machine-to-machine connection.

Figure 7 shows the reporting flow for laboratory-based surveillance for SARS-CoV-2 in the Netherlands as an example. Among the MMLs, a part of the laboratories sends PCR-positive samples to the RIVM for sequencing, whereas other laboratories sequence the samples themselves and report the sequences. All data (Excel files and sequence files) are sent to the RIVM via webmail and entered in the Nonacris database via a set of scripts. All sequences are typed by two typing tools, to determine the variant before passing data on to Nonacris to secure internationally comparable variant assignment: 1) Pangolin (Institute of Evolutionary Biology, University of Edinburgh; O'Toole et al., 2021) and 2) NextClade (NeherLab, Biozentrum, University of Basel, Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics, (Aksamentov et al., 2021). RIVM also shares information on SARS-CoV-2 variants with the MMLs and the MHSs via e-mail. MHSs report positive cases to the Osiris database. The Nonacris database and the Osiris database communicate via scripts to exchange and link information on detected variants and sequenced cases. Sequence information from Nonacris gets passed through Callisto worker, an in-house version of Nextstrain (Hadfield et al., 2018), which performs a phylogenetic analysis of all sequences in the database and produces aggregated online visualization in form of phylogenetic trees and maps in the Callisto web interface that is accessible for MMLs and MHSs through dedicated logins.

Figure 7. Reporting Flow for Laboratory-Based Surveillance for SARS-CoV-2 in the Netherlands

Challenges

Technical challenges: As mentioned above, the laboratory surveillance, both the approach and the technical solution, is different for most (groups of) pathogens. For each data set, different choices have been made in the names of data fields, in the software uses and also in the approach of the underlying legal contracts. As several of the databases at RIVM are reaching end-of-life, plans need to be made to replace them.

Legal challenges: A part of the underlying data sharing agreements underlying these laboratory surveillance initiatives have been implemented in the Netherlands before the GDPR applied in 2018 and need to be updated.

For updating these contracts, as well as for formulating agreements for new initiatives, activities are sometimes hampered by a very strict interpretation of the GDPR and interpretations of the GDPR might differ by legal advisor. The Dutch law lacks a clear description of legal grounds for sharing sequence data and drafting an agreement for new data sharing activities is time-consuming.

Planned developments

To address the challenge of the fragmented surveillance landscape, there is an ongoing process to design a more coherent surveillance structure, which includes drafting a framework agreement with stakeholders and building a generic IT infrastructure, which will make use of (inter)national standards where possible. In particular, a new platform for laboratory-based surveillance, LabSentiNL (pronounced *labsentinel*) is being developed. This platform will be able to store laboratory result data, as well as clinical and epidemiological data as needed in a standardized form and make them available again to stakeholders in relevant formats through a web interface and appropriate access rights. The preparatory phase for this platform has been published in the report (Backx et al., 2023).

To address the challenges on lacking legislation for the sharing of sequence data, an initiative to complement the applicable law (Dutch Public Health Act, ("Wijziging van de Wet publieke gezondheid in verband met de bestrijding van de epidemie van infectieziekten behorend tot groep A1 of een directe dreiging daarvan," 2022) is ongoing.

Norway

Context

Key stakeholders of infectious disease surveillance in Norway are the Ministry of Health, the Directorate of Health, the Norwegian Institute of Public Health (**NIPH**; *Folkehelseinstituttet*, FHI), Medical Microbiology Laboratories (MMLs) and their hosting institutions, as well as local authorities on a county and municipality level and international surveillance partners.

At the NIPH, the Division of Infection Control is responsible for the surveillance of infectious diseases in Norway. Within the Division, the laboratory departments for bacteriology and virology host most of the country's NRLs. The Division also consists of a cluster of four infectious disease control departments: 1) Infection Control and Vaccines, 2) Infectious Disease Registries, 3) Method Development and Analytics, 4) Infectious Disease Control and Preparedness. The Division is the host, and its units and teams are the primary users of the Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases registry (MSIS; (Norwegian Institute of Public Health, 2022) that collects data on notifiable infectious diseases, as well as the associated MSIS Laboratory Database, which collects data on testing outcomes in real-time from Norwegian Medical Microbiology Laboratories (MMLs).

Organization of laboratory-based surveillance

Key stakeholders involved in laboratory-based surveillance in Norway are primary laboratories and NRLs. Primary laboratories include 19 public hospital-based MMLs and two major private laboratories. Of the 42 NRL functions in Norway, 28 are based at the NIPH. In general, NRLs have varying levels of involvement in infectious disease surveillance, i.e., *performing* vs. *contributing to* the surveillance. Depending on the pathogen/disease group they cover, some NRLs mostly do patient-oriented reference diagnostics and provide data that are aggregated and analysed by other departments, while other NRLs are to a large extent doing population-oriented testing and are more directly involved in the population-based analysis. For example, the sentinel system for respiratory viruses is operated by the Department of Virology since the early 1980s. Sample referral occurs directly from primary laboratories at the local level to NRLs at the national level. NRLs at the NIPH store laboratory-reported data in their LIMS system (LabWare; (LabWare, 2023)), as well as in various bioinformatics softwares and file archives, e.g. BioNumerics and SeqSphere.

At the MMLs, – except for the sentinel surveillance system for respiratory viruses – laboratory testing is generally patient-oriented and aimed at pathogen detection that serves primary diagnostic purposes. In general, NRLs are responsible for more in-depth analyses on positive samples or isolates submitted by the MMLs for surveillance and public health purposes, although NRLs also provide some testing for clinical needs. MMLs are legally obliged (MSIS-act § 2-4a; (Helse- og omsorgsdepartementet, 2003) to forward positive specimens or isolates to NRLs according to their specification.

Reporting flow for laboratory-based surveillance

Figure 8a shows a schematic representation of the laboratory-based surveillance system in Norway. The laboratory-based surveillance consists of two to three types of flows that co-exist, depending on the pathogen (Figure 8b):

1. Main flow of (all) diagnostic test results from all laboratories to the MSIS Laboratory Database
 - a. This is a highly automated process and captures reported test results, but no other information such as testing indication, clinical data etc. For SARS-CoV-2, the results include data on variants.
2. Primary laboratories share subsets of specimens together with metadata with NRLs
 - a. The NRL specifies the subsets that are required depending on the disease. Sample referral generally is paper-based and involves a low level of digitalization (Figure 8c).
 - b. Where data accompanying the specimens received by the NRL are incomplete, some data can be supplemented from the MSIS Laboratory Database.
 - c. Some (but not all) results generated by the NRL feed back into the MSIS Laboratory Database. Results of analyses that do not enter the database may, for example, be those that comprise groups of specimens or sophisticated analyses that don't fit well within the structure and scope of the database and where the intended user of the outcome is not the sender of the specimen.
3. Dedicated surveillance schemes, e.g. sentinel system for influenza and other respiratory viruses
 - a. This entails some innovative and highly digitalized solutions with an external frontline MML performing the primary testing with the comprehensive sentinel clinical/epidemiological data flowing automatically from the physician to the NIPH NRL, as well as the referral of all positive specimens to the NRL.

For digital sharing of laboratory-based surveillance data in Norway, Electronic Business using eXtensible Markup Language (ebXML; (OASIS, 2023)), the Nomenclature for Properties and Units (NPU) coding system (NPU Terminology, 2023), as well as national and local codes are used (Figure 8c).

Figure 8a. Laboratory-Based Surveillance Data Flow in Norway

Figure 8b. Reporting Flow from Laboratories to the Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases (MSIS) based at the NIPH (dotted square). Dotted arrow: Some laboratories send the copy of test results only to the MSIS laboratory database, and if they contain notifiable findings, they are forwarded to the MSIS register.

Figure 8c. IT infrastructure for Laboratory-Based Surveillance in Norway

Challenges, needs & gaps

Legal: Issues regarding the legal basis for data sharing and data linkage and discrepant interpretation among stakeholders of laws and regulations on data security/ privacy issues (e.g. GDPR) in Norway.

Structural: Data located at different places, resulting in fragmentation of the system. There is often also unclarity about the legality of sharing data.

Financial & human resources: These challenges are based on a significant drop in NIPH funding.

Technical: For SARS-CoV-2, a highly diverse and dynamic terminology for variants has resulted in some surveillance data flows to lag with non-updated variant attribution. In addition, cumbersome specimen/metadata transfer between laboratories is challenging.

Accessibility of MSIS Laboratory Database: The MSIS Laboratory Database is legally mandated under the remit of MSIS, and access to data is subjected to data protection regulations. In most cases, data from health registers are considered indirectly identifiable data, if not presented in an aggregated table form. Thus, a legal basis is needed for the use of case-based data from MSIS and NRL for an integrated and effective real-time surveillance.

Needs and gaps

- Loss of funding negatively affects resources and personnel involved in laboratory-based surveillance.
- Incompleteness of metadata: This comprises metadata that 1) accompanies samples to the NRL, 2) get reported to MSIS Laboratory Database and 3) get notified in MSIS. To address this gap, the transfer process of sharing samples/ isolates together with metadata to NRLs should be facilitated, and when needed be complemented with corresponding data in the MSIS Laboratory Database.

Planned developments

- 1) Invest in further integration of surveillance based on the progress made so far.
- 2) Expanding the digitalization of surveillance towards other pathogen groups (i.e. pilot under UNITED4Surveillance focused on STEC; see section 4.5)
- 3) Further development of functionalities for more advanced pathogen investigations, e.g. genetic characteristics. This could be done within or outside of current data structures.
- 4) Continuing ongoing work on national harmonized requesting/reporting for specimens that will facilitate efficient sample referral to NRLs.

Slovenia

Context

The following key stakeholders are involved in infectious disease surveillance in Slovenia: The **Ministry of Health** is responsible for providing legislation for surveillance of communicable diseases and provides funding to the **National Institute of Public Health (NIPH; Nacionalni Inštitut za javno zdravje, NIJZ)** for certain public health tasks (i.e. data analyses, risk assessments, Emergency Operations Centre (EOC)). The NIJZ consists of nine regional units and the Centre for Communicable Diseases (CDC), but there are no microbiological laboratories within this institution. The regional units are responsible for review and entry of case reporting forms for communicable diseases in the national databases, epidemiological investigation of cases, contact tracing, outbreak investigation, 24/7 preparedness and conduct risk assessments with advice on preventive measures on regional level. The CDC is responsible for the management of national databases for communicable diseases, conducting

data analysis, preparing reports, providing 24/7 preparedness through the NFP for the International Health Regulations (IHR) and the Early Warning and Response System (EWRS), conducts risk assessment and offers advice on preventive measures for the national level. The **University Clinic Golnik** is the main stakeholder for tuberculosis (TB) in Slovenia, and is responsible for treatment of patients, contact tracing, outbreak investigation, management of the national TB database and operating the laboratory for mycobacteria. **Medical doctors** are responsible for reporting communicable disease cases and outbreaks to regional units of NIJZ, with exception of Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV)/ Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS, which is directly reported to the national level, i.e. the CDC, NIJZ. **Microbiology laboratories** develop or implement and maintain methods for microbiological diagnostics, detect, confirm and report pathogens of communicable diseases and perform additional testing for public health purposes. For zoonotic diseases, **veterinary services** are responsible for reporting of all cases and deaths in animals to the regional units of NIJZ. The **Health Insurance Institution of Slovenia** provides funding for the epidemiological investigation of cases, outbreak investigation, 24/7 preparedness, management of databases to the NIJZ and microbiology testing for clinical and public health purposes to microbiology laboratories.

The following legal documents are applicable for the surveillance of infectious diseases in Slovenia:

The Communicable Diseases Act (CD) (OJ 69/1995) ("Communicable Diseases Act," 1995). This act specifies which infectious diseases are notifiable by law and lays out mandatory reporting of infectious disease outbreaks.

Rules for Reporting of CD and Specific Measures for Their Prevention and Control (OJ 16/1999) ("Rules for Reporting of Communicable Diseases and Specific Measures for Their Prevention and Control," 1999). The target audience of this document are medical doctors and medical microbiology laboratories. These rules specify the time frame within which infectious diseases should be notified. The time frame is based on four infectious disease groups, a list of variables that should be reported, the mode of reporting through case-based reporting forms and the recipient of infectious disease notifications, i.e. the Regional Units of the NIPH.

The Healthcare Databases Act (OJ 65/2000) ("Healthcare Databases Act," 2000). This act lays out a list of variables of existing databases, e.g. the general Database on Communicable Diseases. This act also determines separate databases for HIV/ AIDS/ death due to AIDS, Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STDs) and TB patient registry. The purpose of these databases is to monitor the occurrence of infectious diseases, their characteristics and the evaluation of implemented public health measures. All health institutions and other legal and physical entities in the health sector are obliged to provide data (reports of communicable diseases) on an ongoing basis. The manager of three databases in the field of communicable diseases is NIJZ. The manager of the TB patient registry data is University Clinic Golnik.

[Organization of laboratory-based surveillance](#)

The following key stakeholders are involved in laboratory-based surveillance in Slovenia and are licensed by the Ministry of Health to perform clinical microbiological testing: The **National Laboratory of Health, Environment and Food (NLZOH)** is the largest Slovenian public health laboratory responsible for diagnostic and public health microbiological activities, chemical and microbiological testing of various types of samples, environmental protection issues and research. It entails seven departments for Medical Microbiology in different Slovenian regions (Maribor, Celje, Novo mesto, Koper, Nova Gorica, Kranj, Murska Sobota) and one department for Public Health Microbiology. The **Institute of Microbiology and Immunology of the Faculty of Medicine Ljubljana** is the central Slovenian institution for clinical microbiological and immunological activities, research and teaching. The institute hosts a biosafety level 3 (BSL-3) laboratory with advanced molecular diagnostics and offers the widest range of different microbiological diagnostic methods in Slovenia. The **University Clinic Golnik** is the central laboratory for mycobacteria and performs diagnostics of and surveillance for TB. There are three

CMLs in Slovenia, 1) the University Clinical Centre Ljubljana, 2) the General Hospital Franca Derganca Nova Gorica and 3) the Slovenj Gradec General Hospital. Finally, the **Institute for Transfusion Medicine** performs serology testing for communicable diseases that are transmissible via blood transfusion.

Reporting flow for laboratory-based surveillance

Figure 9 shows the reporting surveillance flow for infectious diseases, including mode of reporting for laboratory-based surveillance and physician-based surveillance in Slovenia. According to the Communicable Diseases Act ("Communicable Diseases Act," 1995), all providers of healthcare in Slovenia (medical doctors, microbiological laboratories, etc.) are obliged to report communicable diseases to the NIJZ. Communicable diseases are reported on paper forms. Some providers, however, report communicable diseases and their pathogens on paper outputs from their information systems. Medical doctors (clinicians) use codes from International Classification of Diseases (ICD) for reporting. Microbiology laboratories report pathogens of communicable diseases, some of their information systems already contain algorithms (based on three parameters – pathogen, sample, test) which determine the reporting to the NIJZ. Reports of communicable diseases and their pathogens are systematically collected by NIJZ regional units, which are entered into the national Communicable Diseases Database using the interface of the national computer program Survival. Reports on HIV/ AIDS and STDs are collected separately from other communicable diseases, with a different set of variables on paper forms. Reports of STDs are systematically collected by NIJZ regional units and entered in the national STDs Database (in Slovenian *SPO – Spolno prenosljive okužbe*) using the interface of the computer program EpiInfo. Reports on HIV/ AIDS are collected directly at the CDC NIJZ, where they are directly entered into the national database. CDC NIJZ also receives additional data on pathogens of communicable diseases from microbiology laboratories (genotyping, serotyping, sequences, antimicrobial resistance (AMR), etc.) The CDC at NIJZ coordinates systems for surveillance of communicable diseases and collects data at national level. The data is analyzed, evaluated, monthly reports and annual reports are prepared on the trends of communicable diseases and their epidemiological characteristics. The data are also prepared for different stakeholders and for reporting to international institutions (i.e. The European Surveillance System (TESSy), ECDC).

Figure 9. Reporting Flow for Laboratory-Based Surveillance of Communicable Diseases (CD), Including Physician-Based Surveillance in Slovenia

Figure 10 shows the surveillance flow specifically for Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19), for which automated data transfers have been established within the infrastructure of eHealth. eHealth is a nationally coordinated health information system that, by operating on a unified information and communication infrastructure, enables the processing of health and other data and the provision of eHealth services. The results of Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) tests from all microbiology laboratories, and the results of Rapid Antigen Tests (RAT) from all health care providers, are forwarded to the Central Registry of Patient Data in real-time. CDC NIJZ obtains the data on confirmed COVID-19 cases in near real-time from the Central Registry of Patient Data using automatic algorithm described in the figure 10 and stores the data in the COVID-19 database, which is part of the general Communicable Diseases Database. During the COVID-19 epidemic in Slovenia, these data on confirmed cases were used by the epidemiological service at the regional units of the NIJZ for epidemiological investigation and response. When the COVID-19 epidemic was at its highest intensity, this data was also crucial for the operation of the National Call Center for contact tracing. With such a system, at NIJZ has been able to provide timely and high-quality data on the epidemiology of COVID-19 to all relevant stakeholders in accordance with their responsibilities both nationally and international (ECDC, etc.).

Figure 10. Surveillance flow for COVID-19 in Slovenia

Challenges

The following challenges have been identified in Slovenia:

Legal challenges: The national legislation on surveillance of communicable diseases is outdated, which could hamper the development of a modern digitalized system for monitoring infectious diseases following the example of COVID-19. Furthermore, it is not clearly defined in the legislation that the laboratories should report a patient identifier number when reporting all test results for pathogens of communicable diseases (e.g. either the uniform citizen registration number or the health insurance number) and that the data should be reported in a structured electronic form. Furthermore, there is no clear obligation for laboratories to report the results of additional SARS testing of pathogens that are important for public health (e.g. genotyping, sequencing, AMR, etc.) besides the test result.

Technical challenges: Medical doctors and microbiology laboratories still use paper-based case reporting forms for the reporting of infectious diseases to the NIPH, which affects timeliness of reporting. An exception is the reporting of COVID-19 (Figure 10), for which automated reporting has been implemented. An additional challenge is that data integration (including linking of clinical, laboratory and epidemiological information), data validation and quality assurance for surveillance of infectious diseases is still performed manually at the CDC, NIJZ. Also, the IT infrastructure for laboratory data management, especially in the national public health laboratories, is currently insufficient. Finally, the lack of uniform national code books for pathogens and microbiological tests implemented in information systems of laboratories hampers uniform reporting.

Human resources: There is a lack of human resources both at the NIJZ, especially in epidemiology, public health microbiology and IT, as well as in microbiology laboratories.

Needs and gaps

The following needs and gaps have been identified in Slovenia:

- To update national legislation on surveillance of communicable diseases with a clearly defined legal basis specifically for laboratory-based surveillance. This includes a specification on which patient identifiers to use, the need for implementing uniform national or international code books and will include guidance on the reporting of results from additional testing with public health importance.
- To establish an electronic reporting system for communicable diseases from medical doctors and microbiology laboratories to the NIJZ within the infrastructure of eHealth.
- To develop an electronic data management system for integration of clinical, laboratory and epidemiological data at NIJZ for rapid data analysis and outbreak detection.
- To develop specific definitions or algorithms (for example algorithm for confirmed COVID-19 cases presented on Figure 10) for laboratory-based surveillance (for individual communicable diseases pathogens, by microbiological tests and samples)
- To establish designated and accredited official public health reference laboratories for priority diseases and consider central funding for their human and technical resources.
- To participate in trainings focused on laboratory-based surveillance at the EU level.

Planned developments

The **Health Information System Act** has been submitted in preparation by the Ministry of Health. This act will determine the central organization of informatics in healthcare. The medical personal data will be collected in one place, recorded according to uniform standards, properly secured. A consistent and efficient framework for the secondary use of medical data will be established through this Act.

The Ministry of Health plans to **revise the Communicable Diseases Act** ("Communicable Diseases Act," 1995), which provides the legal basis for the surveillance of infectious diseases in Slovenia.

The NIJZ will strive to digitalize the surveillance of other communicable diseases, according to the system established for the surveillance of COVID-19.

3.3.2 Needs and gaps analysis for laboratory-based reporting

The following sections describe results according to the structure of the survey "Needs and Gaps Analysis Laboratory-Based Reporting" (Annex 4): 1) general, 2) legal, 3) policy and organizational, 4) technical [data and IT] and 5) financial aspects of the laboratory surveillance systems in participating countries. More detailed original country responses to free text questions are listed in annex 5.

General aspects

Survey respondents & response rate

Of the 25 countries of the UNITED4Surveillance consortium that were invited to participate in this survey, 23 countries responded within the deadline of 12 April and one country – that did not have the resources to respond at the time – responded on 19 July 2023. Of the 24 countries that responded, one country retracted their data. This report therefore includes results from 23 countries (response rate 92%; Figure 11).

The survey respondents worked at the following organizations: 20 (87%) at the National Institute of Public Health, one (4%) at the Ministry of Health [Spain (ES)], one (4%) at a National Reference Laboratory [Luxembourg (LU)] and one at the National Public Health Center under the MoH together with the NRL [Lithuania (LT)].

Figure 11. Map of Countries of the UNITED4Surveillance Consortium that were Invited to Participate in the Survey. Countries shaded in blue, including MT and LU, participated in the survey and consented to including their data in this report (n=23) and countries marked in orange did not participate or did not consent to have their data included in this report (HU, CY).

Notifiable diseases

Of the 58 diseases we surveyed (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, 2018), 21 (36%) were notifiable at the national level in all 23 countries. The median number of notifiable diseases across all countries was 58 (Figure 12). Eight diseases were least often notifiable, i.e. were notifiable in only 16 (70%) to 19 (83%) countries, respectively. These spanned infections with arthropod-borne pathogens, congenitally acquired infections, influenza and parasitic diseases (Figure 12).

In twelve countries (52%), all 58 diseases were notifiable (Figure 13). Seven countries (30%) reported a difference of less than five with the list of 58 diseases. Four countries (17%) formed exceptions where markedly fewer diseases were notifiable, i.e. in the Netherlands (NL) 45 (76%) of the 58 diseases were notifiable, in Austria (AT) 43 (73%), in Belgium (BE) 36 (61%) and in France (FR) 32 (54%), respectively. Twenty-two countries provided

additional information as to which diseases – other than the 58 surveyed – are notifiable in their country (Annex 5, section 4.1).

Figure 12. Number of Countries in which the Listed Diseases (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, 2018) are Notifiable at the National Level

Figure 13. Overview of Notifiable Diseases at the National Level by Country
 Dark blue shading indicates that the respective disease is notifiable at the national level in the respective country and light blue shading that it is not. Bar charts on the top and to the right side indicate the percentage of the respective disease or country. Abbreviations: dis., disease; SARS; Severe acute respiratory syndrome; Q fever; query fever; STEC/VTEC, Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli*/ Verocytotoxin-producing *E. coli*; vCJD, Variant Creutzfeldt-Jakob Disease

Subtyping/Phenotyping capacity at the national level

Of the 21 surveyed pathogens (based on (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, 2019) & supplemented with SARS-CoV-2), the median number of pathogens, for which subtyping/phenotyping is performed at the national level across all countries was 19 (90%). Eighteen countries knew the status of laboratory-based surveillance for all surveyed pathogens. Of these, five countries (28%) perform subtyping/phenotyping for all 21 pathogens. Five countries (22%) reported “unknown” in ten instances (Figure 14).

All 23 countries perform subtyping for influenza virus and SARS-CoV-2. Croatia (HR) and Malta (MT) least often perform subtyping/phenotyping at the national level compared to other countries, with subtyping/phenotyping in place for three (14%) and nine (42%) pathogens, respectively. Of the 23 countries, 16 reported additional information (Annex 5 section 5.1).

Figure 14. Overview of Pathogens for which Subtyping/Phenotyping is performed at the National Level by Country. Blue shading indicates that there is subtyping/phenotyping capacity, light blue shading that there is not and white that the status of laboratory-based surveillance for this pathogen is unknown. Bar charts on the top and to the right side indicate the percentage of the respective pathogens or countries.

Legal aspects

Legal constraints and challenges with respect to sharing of laboratory-based surveillance data

With respect to sharing of laboratory surveillance data, countries reported the extent of legal constraints or challenges (e.g. data cannot be shared or is very difficult to share) as follows (Figure 15): nine countries (39%) experience challenges to some extent, six countries (26%) to little extent, four countries (17%) to no extent, two countries to a large extent (9%) and one country to a very large extent (4%), respectively. One country reported unknown (4%).

Fifteen countries (68%) elaborated further on the legal constraints and challenges. Challenges that were most often reported revolved around data linkage and data sharing, and a lack of or unclear legal mandate of the NIPH to receive laboratory surveillance data (Annex 5, section 6.1).

Figure 15. Overview of the Extent of Legal Constraints or Challenges with Respect to Sharing of Laboratory Surveillance Data Experienced by Country
Dark blue shading indicates the country response.

Legal basis for processing laboratory-based surveillance data

The number of legal bases – as laid out in the GDPR, Article 6.1 (“General Data Protection Regulation,” 2016) – under which the NIPH processes laboratory surveillance data (including directly identifiable or pseudonymized personal data) varies across the countries (Figure 16). Countries reported a median number of one legal base. The maximum number of legal bases was three (excluding “Other”) and was reported by five countries (ES, FR, LX, MT and SI).

“Compliance with a legal obligation” (Article 6.1.c) and “Performance of a task carried out in the public interest” (Article 6.1.e) most often applied and were mentioned by 15 and 14 countries, respectively. “Protection of the vital interests of the data subject or another natural person” (Article 6.1.d) applied in five, “Informed consent” (Article 6.1.a) in four and “Other” in two countries (LV, MT). No country selected “Not applicable”, which was defined as “The GDPR does not apply, we only process anonymous data. As such, directly identifiable information (e.g. name or national identifier) or other identifiers (e.g. sample identifier) are not provided to us.”.

Figure 16. Overview of the Legal Basis for Processing Laboratory-Based Surveillance Data according the GDPR, Article 6.1, by Country
Dark blue shading indicates the country response(s). Bar charts on the top and to the right side indicate the percentage of countries or legal base(s) that apply.

Laboratory-based surveillance and data elements shared along with laboratory test result

Figure 17 shows the pathogens for which laboratory-based surveillance has been implemented in the 23 countries. Seven countries (30%; DK, FR, IE, LU, MT, NO and RO) have implemented laboratory-based surveillance for all listed pathogens. Influenza and SARS-CoV-2 are the only pathogens for which laboratory-based surveillance is implemented in all countries. Laboratory-based surveillance is least often implemented, i.e. is

implemented in 16/23 countries (70%), for *Clostridioides difficile*, Outbreaks of emerging multidrug resistant pathogens/clones/plasmids (Outbreaks-MDR), Outbreaks of newly emerging pathogens/new modes of transmission of known healthcare- associated pathogens (Outbreaks – new transmissions), West Nile Virus and Resistant HIV-transmitted drug resistance (Resistant HIV).

We surveyed which additional data local laboratories share with the NIPH along with the laboratory test result (i.e. additional laboratory data and clinical/epidemiological data). Across all 23 countries and 21 pathogens for which subtyping/phenotyping is performed, the most often reported data elements were date of birth (n=372), date of sampling (n=363) and sample identifier (n=342) (Figure 18). The second group of most often reported data elements were name, national identifier and residence postal code which are reported comparably often, ranging from 266 for residence postal code to 275 for national identifier. Clinical/epidemiological data was reported less often, ranging from 37 for vaccination status (albeit not applicable for some pathogens) to 124 for travel history (Figure 18).

Nineteen countries filled in the free text question providing additional information. Additional data elements that countries reported include further details on laboratory test data (e.g. test result/outcome, diagnostic method, sample material, sample type, and specimen site), patient demographics (e.g. gender and age), and data on hospitalization (e.g. hospital unit) (Annex 5, section 8.1).

Figure 17. Overview of Pathogens for Which Laboratory-based Surveillance is Implemented by Country
 Dark blue shading indicates that laboratory-based surveillance is implemented, light blue shading that it is not (n=58). Bar charts on the top and to the right side indicate the percentage of countries or pathogens.

Figure 18. Overview of Data Elements Reported Along with Laboratory Test Results across 23 Countries and 21 Pathogens Listed Above

[Data linkage of laboratory-based surveillance data](#)

Of the 23 countries, 18 reported (78%) that their NIPH is legally allowed and able to link laboratory surveillance data with surveillance data from other sources, e.g. notifications by physicians etc. Two countries (9%) are not allowed (HR, NL) and one country (4%) is allowed but not able to (ES). Two countries (9%) reported “not applicable” (BE and PL) and provided the following additional information as shown in Annex 5, section 9.1.

[Assessment of the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects](#)

With respect to the assessment of the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects that is part of a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA, GDPR Article 35.7.c, ("General Data Protection Regulation," 2016), eleven countries (48%) reported that the NIPH in general assesses the risk of identification of a person based on the laboratory surveillance data provided to the NIPH. Four countries (17%) answered that the risk is assessed per disease, four countries (17%) do not assess the risk and for four countries (17%) the status was unknown (Figure 19).

Additional information as to how the risk was assessed was reported by 15 countries (79%) (Annex 5, section 10.1).

Figure 19. Overview of whether the NIPH conducts an assessment of the Risk of Identification of a Person based on Laboratory Surveillance Data shared with the NIPH

Dark blue shading indicates the country response. Bar charts to the right side indicate the percentage of the answer option across all countries.

Availability of legal expertise at NIPH

With regards to the availability of legal expertise to provide assistance with setting up and maintaining laboratory-based surveillance at the NIPH, eleven countries (48%) reported that they had sufficient support, eight limited support (35%), three no support (13%) and for one country the status was unknown (4%) (Figure 20).

Of the countries with limited or no support (n=11), ten countries (91%) provided additional details and highlighted e.g. limited human resources and/or a lack of specialized legal expertise. Two countries stated that the responsibility lies elsewhere (i.e. Directorate of Health or the Ministry of Health; Annex 5, section 11.1).

Figure 20. Overview of the Availability of Legal Expertise to Assist with Setting Up and Maintaining Laboratory-Based Surveillance at the NIPH

Dark blue shading indicates the country response. Bar charts to the right side indicate the percentage of the answer option across all countries.

Facilitating and hampering role of national and international legislation

Of the 23 countries, 17 (74%) provided examples of how national or international legislation either hampers or facilitates laboratory-based surveillance at the national level, and how any hampering issues have been potentially overcome. (Inter)national legislation was both reported to facilitate and hamper laboratory-based surveillance. Among the former, having clear national legislation (e.g. legislation that lays out scope and obligatory roles of stakeholders involved in laboratory-based surveillance, defines how personal data can be processed and which diseases are notifiable, etc.) was reported as a major facilitator. Among the hampering aspects, examples included requiring informed consent before samples can be shared, lack of regulations on sharing of WGS data between laboratories and the national surveillance system, the GDPR precluding sharing of sequence data, the need for bioethics permissions to set up temporary surveillance systems, legal unclearities for laboratory-based surveillance when transitioning between laws, lack of regulation that lays out that laboratories are required to provide personal identifiers or regulation that only requires reporting of aggregated data, which precludes data linkage etc. (Annex 5, section 12).

Provisions in national law for data processing

Of the 23 countries, 13 (57%) reported to have provisions in the national law that further specify how personal data can be processed in the interest of public health, as described in e.g. GDPR Article 6.2 or Article 9.2.i ("General Data Protection Regulation," 2016). Two countries (9%) had no such provisions and for eight countries the status was unknown (35%) (Figure 21).

Figure 21. Overview of Countries that have Provisions in the National Law That Further Specify How Personal Data can be Processed in the Interest of Public Health
Dark blue shading indicates the country response. Bar charts to the right side indicate the percentage of the answer option across all countries.

Need for change or adaptation of the GDPR to facilitate laboratory-based surveillance

We asked countries for their opinion regarding which aspects of the GDPR, if any, would need to be changed or adapted to facilitate performing lab surveillance and ten (43%) filled in this free text question. Original responses are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Overview of Original Country Responses in Terms of Which Aspects of the GDPR Would Need to be Changed or Adapted to Facilitate Performing Laboratory-Based Surveillance

Country responses	
1	There is a potential for improving the national regulatory framework for surveillance, more than a need for a change in GDPR. This to enable reuse of data from different health registries and other sources. This can reduce burden of manual reporting, increase timeliness, and improve quality of surveillance data.
2	In our opinion, the EHDS Regulation should include laboratory surveillance data as part of the data shared for secondary use and facilitate their exchange.
3	In practice, the pseudonymization of lab surveillance data makes identification of a person impossible except in rare cases through statistical disclosure. When measures are taken to also prevent statistical disclosure, the pseudonymised, or doubly pseudonymized data, could be considered by law to be in effect anonymous data.
4	It is imported to have the national legislation to process the data
5	No, we find that it is written sufficiently.
6	Our institute has outlined that microbe identification codes (provided in our institute upon arrival of the sample) are not personal data. This allows us to use same strain IDs in communication when sharing e.g. sequence data outside. However, this ID is not reported back to clinical laboratories.
7	Personal data should be transferable to appointed organization (if different to NIPH)
8	Practical clarity around some terms/definitions e.g. when can we consider data as pseudonymized] The answer is not always clear with different interpretations and rules in different countries as a result.
9	Reinforce that public health need data linkage with clinical notification: this has to be guaranteed also by putting adequate resources in resolving all the regulatory aspects.
10	n.a.

Policy and organizational aspects

Organizational units at NIPH involved in laboratory-based surveillance at the NIPH

The number of organizational units directly involved in laboratory-based surveillance varied between countries (Figure 22). The number of units including “Other” ranged from one to seven, with a median number of three. The top three units that were mentioned by countries were epidemiology (n=19; 83%), laboratory/microbiology (n=15; 65%) and IT (n=11; 48%). Five countries reported additional information (Annex 5, section 15.1).

Figure 22. Overview of Organizational Units Involved in Laboratory-Based Surveillance by Country
Dark blue shading indicates the country response. Bar charts on the top and to the right side indicate the percentage of the answer options within and across countries.

Provision of training on laboratory-based surveillance

Of the 23 countries, seven (30%) provide dedicated training (e.g. on scientific aspects, data management, communication, infrastructure etc.) for the units/teams mentioned in the previous question, 12 (52%) indicated that they do not, and four countries (17%) reported unknown (Figure 23).

Seven countries provided additional information. Of the seven countries that report that they provide training, six (86%) elaborated on how training is organized and/or for which aspects teams are trained (Annex 5, section 16.1).

Figure 23. Overview of Countries that Provide Dedicated Training for Units Involved in Laboratory-Based Surveillance
Dark blue shading indicates the country response. Bar charts to the right side indicate the percentage of the answer options across countries.

Difficulty meeting training needs for laboratory-based surveillance

More than half the countries (n=13; 57%) responded that they experience difficulties to some (n=7; 30%) or a large extent (n=6; 26%) to meet training needs for laboratory-based surveillance (e.g. on scientific aspects, data management, communication, infrastructure) at the NIPH. Croatia reported experiencing challenges to a very large extent.

Of the 14 countries that experience difficulties ranging from “some” to “to a very large extent”, 13 (93%) described their challenges in more detail (Annex 5, section 17.1).

Figure 24. Overview of the Extent to Which Countries Experience Difficulties in Meeting Training Needs for Laboratory-Based Surveillance at the NIPH

Dark blue shading indicates the country response. Bar charts to the right side indicate the percentage of the answer options across countries.

Specific measures taken to attract and retain talent

Fourteen countries (61%) provided information on specific measures that they take to attract and retain talent in the area of laboratory-based surveillance, particularly professionals with a data science or IT background. Responses can be summarized as follows: creating an attractive working environment, encouragement to participate in international projects, offering further training and development within bioinformatics, offering stable contracts and flexible working conditions (e.g. the option to work from home), as well as providing stimulating and motivating assignments.

Technical aspects (Data and IT)

Data standards used for laboratory-based surveillance

Of the (international) data standards surveyed (Table 3), more than half the countries (n=13; 57%) reported using other standards, including national ones, followed by the ICD reported by eleven countries (48%). The median number of data standards used in countries is two, with a range from one to six (Figure 25).

Of the 13 countries that reported “Other, including national standards”, eleven (85%) provided more details as shown in Annex 5, section 19.1.

Table 3. Overview of (International) Data Standards Used in Countries

Data Standard	Number of Countries
Other, including national standards	13
International Classification of Diseases (ICD)	11
Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes (LOINC)	8
Systematised Nomenclature of Medicine – Clinical Terms (SNOMED-CT)	7
Health Level 7 (HL7) - Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR)	6
Health Level 7 (HL7) - Previous versions	6
Unified Code for Units of Measure (UCUM)	3
Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) classification for medicinal products	1

Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium – Study Data Tabulation Model (CDISC SDTM) 0

Figure 25. Overview of the Combination of (International) Data Standards Used in Countries
 Dark blue shading indicates the country response(s). Bar charts on the top and to the right side indicate the percentage of the answer options within and across countries.

[Technical assistance of local laboratories by NIPH to provide laboratory-based surveillance data](#)

Of the 23 countries, eight (35%) indicated that they generally technically assist local laboratories with providing laboratory-based surveillance data, three countries (13%) provide assistance for some diseases, four (17%) provide very limited support and eight (35%) provide no support, respectively (Figure 26).

Fifteen countries provided additional information on how the NIPH provides technical assistance. Of the 15 countries that provide technical assistance to local laboratories ranging from “Yes, in general” to “Yes, but very limited”, 13 countries (87%) provided additional information (Annex 5, section 20.1).

Figure 26. Overview of the Extent of Technical Assistance Local Laboratories Receive from NIPH with Providing Laboratory-Based Surveillance Data
 Dark blue shading indicates the country response(s). Bar charts on the top and to the right side indicate the percentage of the answer options within and across countries.

Reporting route of laboratory-based surveillance data

For the 21 pathogens mentioned above, local laboratories in the 23 countries most often reported directly to the NIPH (48%), followed by the local or regional public health authority (24%) and the NRL (not located at the NIPH) (16%). For 9%, no laboratory-based surveillance is conducted in countries, and the reporting route is therefore not applicable. In 3% of the cases the reporting route is unknown.

Reporting routes varied between countries and pathogens. The median number of authorities/institutes that the local laboratories directly report to was two. Across all 21 pathogens, six countries report to one institute/authority, 15 countries to two, and two countries to three institutes/authorities, respectively (Figure 27).

Fourteen countries (61%) provided additional information about how laboratory-based surveillance data are reported (Annex 5, section 21.1).

Figure 27. Overview of Institutes/Authorities that Local Laboratories Directly Report Laboratory-Based Surveillance Data. The intensity of the colour shading reflects the number of pathogens that are reported via the respective route. The darkest shade indicates that all 21 pathogens are reported via the respective route. Pathogens, for which no laboratory-based surveillance is conducted are not included in the count. Bar charts on the top and to the right side indicate the percentage of pathogens across countries.

Reporting format of laboratory-based surveillance data

Countries could select multiple answer options per pathogen. The top three formats local laboratories in the 23 countries use to report on the 21 pathogens to the institute/authority mentioned in the previous section were 1) paper forms (n=177), machine-to-machine upload (n=157) and web form entry or upload (n=153). Other reporting formats were used to a lesser extent, i.e. data file sent via e-mail (e.g. Excel or CSV file with structured tabular data) (n=78), free text via mail (n=18) and other (n=31). Unknown was selected 56 times.

Ten countries provided additional information on reporting format. Of the four countries that selected "Other", three (75%) provided additional information (Annex 5, section 22.1).

Three countries use the same reporting format for all 21 pathogens (BE, LU and MT), whereas there was more variation in reporting formats among countries and pathogens (Figure 28a & 28b).

Figure 28a. Overview of Formats used by Local Laboratories to Report Laboratory-Based Surveillance Data of 21 Pathogens to the Institute/ Authority mentioned in the previous section by Country
 The intensity of the colour shading reflects the number of pathogens that are reported via the respective format. The darkest shade indicates that all 21 pathogens are reported via the same format. Pathogens, for which no laboratory-based surveillance is conducted are not included in the count. Bar charts on the top and to the right side indicate the percentage of pathogens across countries and reporting format.

Figure 28b. Overview of Formats used by Local Laboratories to Report Laboratory-Based Surveillance Data of 21 Pathogens to the Institute/ Authority Mentioned in the Previous Section by Pathogen
 The intensity of the colour shading reflects the number of countries that report via the respective format. Countries which do not perform laboratory-based surveillance for certain pathogens are not included in the count. Bar charts on the top and to the right side indicate the percentage of countries that report a pathogen in the respective format.

Timeliness of reporting laboratory-based surveillance data to the NIPH

We surveyed how timely the NIPH in the 23 countries receive laboratory-based surveillance data for the majority (>90%) of the samples after the laboratory has it stored in their systems. We excluded “Outbreaks-MDR” and “Outbreaks – new transmissions” from this question. The question therefore covered the remaining 19 pathogens. Countries could provide one answer option per pathogen.

A maximum delay of one week was most often reported (n=89; 20%) (Figure 29a), followed by a maximum delay of one day (n=75; 17%), real-time (n=74; 17%) and “Other” (n=71; 16%). Sixteen countries provided additional information on timeliness of reporting (Annex 5, section 23.1). Of those seven countries that selected “other”, six (86%) provided additional information in the aforementioned section 23.1 (Annex 5).

In two countries, laboratory results of all 19 pathogens are reported real-time (LU, NO), followed by DK and Estonia (EE) with real-time reporting for 16/19 (84%) and 12/16 (63%) pathogens, respectively (Figure 29b). In

MT, laboratory data on all 19 pathogens are reported with a maximum delay of one day. Of the pathogens for which laboratory-based surveillance is conducted, more than 70% of laboratory data are reported with a maximum delay of one week in Ireland (IE; n=14/19; 74%), NL (14/17; 82%), DE (16/19; 84%) and LV (16/17, 94%), respectively. In BE, the NRL shares data with the NIPH mostly on a three-month or annual basis (Annex 5, section 23.1).

Figure 29c shows the combined timeliness for real-time reporting up until including reporting with a one-week delay by pathogen and country. Reporting within this time period is most often done for SARS-CoV-2 (17 countries), followed by *Campylobacter spp.*, Influenza virus, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Legionella spp.*, *Neisseria meningitidis*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Salmonella spp.* as reported by 15 countries.

Figure 29a. Timeliness of Reporting Laboratory-Based Surveillance Data by the Local Laboratories to the NIPH across 23 Countries and 19 Pathogens

Figure 29b. Timeliness of Reporting Laboratory-Based Surveillance Data to the NIPH by Country
 The intensity of the colour shading reflects the number of pathogens (maximum=19) that are reported via the respective timeliness option. Pathogens, for which no laboratory-based surveillance is conducted in a country are excluded from the count. Bar charts on the top and to the right side indicate the percentage of pathogens across countries and answer option.

Figure 29c. Combined Timeliness for the Period ranging from Real-Time Reporting up until Including one Week Delay by Pathogen and Country

Dark blue shading reflects that the pathogen is reported within a timeliness range of real-time up until including one-week delay. Light blue shading reflects reporting with more than one-week delay, or another time period specified as “Other”. White shading reflects that no laboratory-based surveillance is in place for the respective pathogen in the respective country. Bar charts on the top and to the right side indicate the percentage of pathogens across countries and answer option.

Cloud-based storage of laboratory-based surveillance data

None of the NIPH in the 23 countries store (parts of) the laboratory surveillance data in the cloud on EU/EEA or non-EU/EEA-territory. Twenty-one countries (91%) reported that their data are stored on NIPH premises, and two countries (7%) reported unknown. Four countries provided additional information (Annex 5, section 24.1).

Reporting back of laboratory-based surveillance data from NIPH to local laboratories

The NIPH of 12 of the 23 countries (52%) routinely report data back to the local laboratories for some pathogens and five countries (22%) for all pathogens. Six countries (26%) do not report back any data (Figure 30). Sixteen countries (70%) elaborated on what results the NIPH reports back to the local laboratories (Annex 5, section 25.1).

Figure 30. Overview of Countries in which NIPHS Report Laboratory-Based Surveillance Data back to Local Laboratories

Dark blue shading reflects the answer per country. Bar charts to the right side indicate the percentage of the answer options.

Description of laboratory surveillance system

Of the 23 countries, eight (35%) provided (links to) further descriptions of their laboratory-based surveillance system (Annex 5, section 26).

Financial aspects

Availability of stable funding to maintain the laboratory surveillance system

Of the 23 countries, about half (n=12; 52%) responded that their NIPH has stable funding source(s) to some extent to maintain laboratory surveillance systems. One country (4%) reported that stable funding is available to a very large extent, three countries (13%) to a large extent, another three countries (13%) to little extent, two countries (9%) to no extent and two countries (9%) reported unknown (Figure 31). Nine countries provided more details (Annex 5, section 27.1).

Figure 31. Extent of Availability of Stable Funding Source(s) at the NIPH of the 23 countries to Maintain the Laboratory Surveillance System

Dark blue shading reflects the answer per country. Bar charts to the right indicate the percentage of the answer options.

Compensation of local laboratories for laboratory surveillance infrastructure

In 14 countries (61%), the local laboratories receive no compensation in any way for the infrastructure needed to contribute to laboratory surveillance, such as laboratory equipment or laboratory information system extensions for extracting or sending through data. In three countries (13%), local laboratories get compensated to some extent, two countries (9%) to little extent and four countries (17%) reported unknown (Figure 32).

Figure 32. Extent of Compensation of the Local Laboratories in the 23 countries for the Laboratory Surveillance Infrastructure

Dark blue shading reflects the answer per country. Bar charts to the right indicate the percentage of the answer options.

Compensation of local laboratories for performing additional tests

In nine countries (39%), local laboratories are in no way compensated per sample for performing additional tests that are purely in the interest of public health surveillance (e.g. screening, studies, targeted surveys, characterization etc.). Six countries (26%) reported compensation to little extent, four (17%) to some extent and four (17%) reported unknown (Figure 33).

Figure 33. Extent of Compensation of the Local Laboratories in the 23 countries for Performing Additional Tests Solely for Laboratory Surveillance Purposes
Dark blue shading reflects the answer per country. Bar charts to the right side indicate the percentage of the answer options.

Compensation of local laboratories for sending samples and/or data

In nine countries (39%), local laboratories are in no way compensated per sample for sending through samples and/or data to the NRL and/or NIPH. Six countries (26%) reported compensation to some extent, four (17%) to little extent and four (17%) reported unknown (Figure 34).

Figure 34. Extent of Compensation of the Local Laboratories in the 23 countries for Sending through Samples and/or Data to the NRL and/or NIPH
Dark blue shading reflects the answer per country. Bar charts to the right side indicate the percentage of the answer options.

Of the 19 countries that knew to what extent local laboratories are compensated, eleven countries (58%) provided additional information (Annex 5, section 30.1).

3.4 Evaluation and conclusions

Within task 1, the **review/inventory of laboratory-based surveillance systems** of seven countries that were active partners of subtask 1 furthered our understanding on how laboratory-based surveillance systems are organized, which stakeholders are involved and provided insights into the sample/data flow. Although the organization and sample/data flow – including modes of reporting and associated level of digital maturity of laboratory-based surveillance systems – varied between countries, the overall challenges were comparable. For instance, the lack of human resources and insufficiency of stable funding were identified as two areas that

negatively affect the robustness of laboratory-based surveillance. Legal challenges revolve around discrepant interpretations of the GDPR within and between countries, or outdated national legislations that hamper sharing of laboratory-based surveillance data. Technical challenges, needs and gaps were specific to the countries' situations, as well as the planned developments to address these gaps. In general, the COVID-19 pandemic – bolstered by the availability of increased funding – has accelerated the implementation of digital solutions, which countries are now striving to expand towards the surveillance of other pathogens.

The survey “**Needs and Gaps Analysis for Laboratory-Based Reporting**” provided a comprehensive overview of needs and gaps with respect to laboratory-based reporting across 23 of the 25 countries of the UNITED4Surveillance Consortium. With the most recent data on Laboratory Capability dating from 2018, as bi-annually assessed by the ECDC (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, 2020), results presented here reflect current challenges with respect to laboratory-based surveillance after the COVID-19 pandemic. The following sections highlight major findings with respect to general, legal, policy and organizational, technical (data and IT) and financial aspects of laboratory-based surveillance.

The section on **general aspects** highlighted that – with exception of four countries – there was largely homogeneity between countries as to which of the 58 surveyed diseases listed under the EU case definitions (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, 2018) are notifiable at the national level. Of the 23 countries, 19 (83%) countries either classify all 58 diseases as notifiable or reported a difference of less than five with the surveyed list. The comparable number of notifiable infectious diseases across the EU/EEA aids comprehensive surveillance on a European level, e.g. through reporting of data on the European Surveillance Portal for Infectious Diseases EpiPulse hosted by the ECDC (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, 2021). All countries performed subtyping for SARS-CoV-2 and influenza. However, for a subset of the other 19 pathogens the capacity varied across countries, indicating potential need for further strengthening.

In addition to the legal challenges reported by countries during the kick-off workshop as described in section 3.3.1 of this report, the **legal aspects** section of the survey provided a structured overview of the types of legal challenges participating countries experience. For instance, countries described how the GDPR hampers and facilitates laboratory-based surveillance and which aspects, in their opinion, would need to be adapted or changed. The GDPR (“General Data Protection Regulation,” 2016) allows for national legislation to implement how personal data, including the special category of medical data, can be processed in the public interest, as is the case for surveillance of infectious diseases. National legislation may well date from a time when laboratory data was less important for preventing and controlling infectious diseases (e.g. positive or negative result only, implicit in case notification data), or was often generated centrally at the NIPH and did not need to be transferred. This changed substantially with the advent of (cheap) genetic sequencing of the pathogens which allowed laboratories to perform sequencing locally and introduced the need to share these data with the national level or internationally. The survey highlighted that about half the countries experience challenges with laboratory data sharing, ranging from some to a very large extent. The feedback given by countries provides input for potential improvements in the short and long term.

Today’s standard of prevention and control of infectious diseases requires that pseudonymized clinical microbiology laboratory data can legally be processed at the national level, by the national public health agency or equivalent, on the legal basis of a task carried out in the public interest (GDPR Art 6.1.e; (“General Data Protection Regulation,” 2016). To what extent these data are actually generated and shared in practice at national level – e.g. depending on available resources – remains an additional and separate issue. The potential adaptation of EU or national legislation to improve public health is normally a time-consuming process. However, progress could potentially also be made in addition to such adaptations, as outlined in the following paragraphs.

Four countries (17%) currently do not assess the risk of identification of an individual based on lab surveillance data and half of the respondents (n=12; 52%) reported having limited or no legal expertise at the NIPH to assist

with setup and maintenance of laboratory-based surveillance. These gaps could be addressed by organizing trainings for legal professionals specifically on the legal aspects of public health, including the sharing of personal data and the special categories needed for public health (health data, sexual preference, genetic information). In its most accessible form, this could be a freely accessible tutorial, e.g. on the ECDC Virtual Academy, complemented by more in-depth training courses. Similar training for epidemiologists and microbiologists to understand the legal basis of surveillance might be useful as well.

There was substantial variation in the legal basis used for processing laboratory-based surveillance data between countries. Since there can be unclarity on e.g. which legal basis can be used for laboratory-based surveillance, the following actions could be considered to support EU/EEA countries in addressing their legal challenges. It may be useful to conduct an assessment at EU level of what is actually allowed under the GDPR and e.g. what jurisprudence and European Data Protection Supervisor guidance exists. For instance, an assessment could be made – if not already done – of how the rights and freedoms of individuals could or would be infringed by national-level processing of limited (pseudonymized) personal data, along with microbiological data on the pathogen they are infected with, for the purpose of prevention and control of infectious diseases. In other words, what is the probability and impact of identification of an individual based on these data and for a different purpose than intended. A second need would be a common assessment of how not processing these data, or processing only anonymized data at national level, could harm the public interest. A third need would be a common assessment of how the balance between public interest and individual rights and freedoms can reasonably be struck. Finally, the legal basis for sharing of these surveillance data, or subsets thereof, in public databases such as European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), Sequence Read Archive (SRA) or Global Initiative on Sharing All Influenza Data (GISAID), should also be clarified.

Since infectious diseases have different incidences, severity, transmission modes (some associated with e.g. sexual preference, a special category of personal data) and potential for outbreaks, such assessments should likely be performed by individual disease and aetiological agent. In addition, those assessments would need to consider the nature and extent of the personal data elements that would need to be shared for each disease to reach sufficient added value for public health. While this is a complex endeavour requiring both public health and legal experts, an expert opinion on this matter that can e.g. subsequently be taken into account by the EU as well as national data protection supervisors, and individual legal experts, could well be of high value for many countries while waiting for potential improvement of legislation. Finally, it should also be remarked that the European Court of Justice, in its judgment of 26 April 2023 for case T-557/20 (Single Resolution Board vs European Data Protection Supervisor), may question that what is today considered pseudonymised personal data, such as laboratory-based surveillance data including only an identifier but no directly identifiable data, may in some cases be considered anonymous data, and as such not fall under the GDPR altogether ("Single Resolution Board v European Data Protection Supervisor," 2023). This important development should also be followed up closely.

Identified gaps in the section on **policy and organizational aspects** included that more than half the countries experience difficulties to some or to a large extent in meeting training needs for laboratory-based surveillance (n=13; 57%). The specific challenges that countries experience could be further explored and addressed. The number of organizational units at the NIPH involved in laboratory-based surveillance varied between countries, ranging from one to seven with a median of three units. An overview of best practices and pros and cons of the different set-ups might be helpful for countries to improve the organization of their laboratory-based surveillance systems. In addition, the listed specific measures taken by countries to attract and retain talent in the area of laboratory-based surveillance might provide new insights to countries in how to further strengthen their workforce involved in laboratory-based surveillance.

The section on **technical aspects** (data and IT) highlighted that the data standards that are most often used across countries (13/23; 57%), are “Other, including national standards”. This provides relevant input for other European initiatives, for instance, the EU4Health project “EU Interoperability with HERA’s IT Platform” (EU-HIP) (Statens Serum Institut, 2023b), which focuses on strengthening national IT systems with the aim to work towards achieving interoperability with the planned IT platform of the Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority (HERA) of the EC, and the European Health Data Space (EHDS), which sets out to share and increase access to health data across the EU (European Commission, 2023). Reporting formats of laboratory-based data varied widely between countries. The 23 respondent countries most often use paper-based reporting for the 21 pathogens surveyed (n=177), followed closely by machine-to-machine upload reported in 157 instances. Previous results from a 2018 survey on automated digital reporting of clinical laboratory information in 30 EU/EEA countries showed that in 14 countries, all, most or some of the clinical laboratories used machine-to-machine communication to report data to the national level. In 16 countries, data was reported manually (Leitmeyer et al., 2020). As also mentioned in section 3.3.1, the survey results showed that, of all surveyed pathogens, machine-to-machine upload was most often used for SARS-CoV-2 across countries (n=11; 48%), reflecting that many countries have developed new electronic surveillance systems in response to the emergence of this new pathogen (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, 2023a). As paper-based reporting affects timeliness of data sharing, efforts could be made to invest in further digitalization of reporting of other pathogens, as some countries have already mentioned to be ongoing or planned. Cloud-based storage of laboratory-based data is not currently used in any of the respondent countries. The reasons for this could be further explored and potential barriers addressed.

Finally, the section on **financial aspects**, showed that the majority of countries have stable funding to some extent to maintain laboratory-based surveillance at the national level, with four countries facing larger challenges with no or little stable funding in place. Another finding was that local laboratories in the majority of countries receive no or little compensation for infrastructures used for laboratory surveillance or for sending samples and/or data. Improving compensation for local laboratories and investigating the subsequent effect on the quality and timeliness of laboratory-based surveillance data could be further explored.

4. Task 1 – Description of pilots

4.1 Background

This section provides describes the setups including status of four national pilots (subtasks 3-6) carried out in the Netherlands, Denmark, Finland and Norway with the aim to improve laboratory-based reporting through addressing country-specific gaps.

4.2 Subtask 3: Open-source reference data pilot in the Netherlands

Background

The Netherlands conducted a preparatory study in which its current application landscape to support laboratory-based surveillance was assessed, along with the national and EU legal context (Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu, 2023a). In summary, the study concludes that different technical systems are used for different diseases and that some of these systems are outdated.

In addition, the study describes the user and technical requirements for a new application or platform to mitigate the issues found. These requirements were set up in consultation with medical microbiology laboratories and

municipal health services as primary stakeholders, together with the national public health institute (RIVM). The next step after this preparatory study is a pilot phase with selected pathogens, in which components are rapidly developed and adjusted on the basis of user input.

This pilot phase consists of the entire platform. The pilot for one of the main components of the platform, the open-source sequence database, falls within the scope of this grant. It covers the range of possible reporting forms and corresponding use cases from molecular detection (PCR) and complete genome sequence to individual allele sequences as well as relevant classifications based on that. Sequence reads are excluded. The sequence database will also include an application programming interface (API) and reference data for at least SARS-CoV-2 and *E. coli*.

Pilot objectives

The objectives below were taken from the project plan for the pilot phase of the entire platform. All these requirements all applicable to the sequence database as well:

1. Routine user functionality. Is the routine functionality offered to internal users, MMLs and MHSs (GGDen) sufficient, and is it user-friendly and performant?
2. Preparedness functionality. Is the functionality to expand the platform to an emerging disease X sufficient and performant enough to work with high case incidence?
3. Data standardisation. Are the data standards used for storage adequate?
4. Legal compliance. Is the platform compliant with legal requirements?
5. Production environment. Which parts of the pilot components can be used for production, and which should be replaced by either commercial software/outsourcing or re-development?
6. External governance. Is the governance of the laboratory-based surveillance platform (LSP) together with external partners and including the terms of use (ToU), adequate?
7. Internal governance. Is the internal governance of the LSP, including the division of tasks between business (Centre for Infectious disease control) and IT departments, adequate?
8. Lessons learned. Which other aspects of the pilot need to be changed in order to have a well-functioning production system?

Status of the work – January-October 2023

- As part of milestone 22, "Logical Data Model", the following has been done:
 - The technical responsibilities of the sequence database versus the other components in the pilot have been defined.
 - The use cases have been defined: 15 operational use cases and 7 maintenance use cases.
 - The logical data model for the sequence database has been developed and tested against existing databases.
 - This work has been summarized in a milestone report (annex 3).
- The sequence database implementation has the following status:
 - The main technology stack has been chosen: JSON/REST HTTPS API, implemented in Python using the FastAPI package that complies with the OpenAPI standard. Persistent storage in SQL database(s).
 - A proof-of-concept architecture for deployment on Azure cloud infrastructure has been created.
 - The API and business layer Python software architecture has been created. The domain is defined through data classes and abstract services, providing flexibility for composing the actual application from different implementing classes. An event-driven design was adopted. Horizontal scaling for performance, typical for cloud-native applications should be possible.

Planned work – November 2023-September 2024

In general, the sequence database should be implemented to the extent that it supports most of the use cases:

- The cloud architecture should be finalized.
- The sequence database should be able to store SARS-CoV-2 and *E. coli* data:

- Sequence data.
- Locus detection (allele) data.
- Classification (subtyping) data.
- Antimicrobial resistance data.
- The sequence database should be able to calculate and store pairwise distances.
- The sequence database should be able to calculate hierarchical clustering trees.
- The sequence database should be able to return all of the above data as part of the corresponding use cases.

Challenges

Authentication on cloud remains a challenge, as RIVM is moving to the cloud but at the same time its main identity provider components are on-premise or in a different cloud. The implementation of this aspect, which is an RIVM-wide issue, is largely beyond the direct control of the implementing team. There are potential organizational challenges related to tying together different initiatives that RIVM is part of and that were set up in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic. We do not foresee personnel, legal or financial challenges at the moment.

4.3 Subtask 4: Pilot in Denmark

Background

The Danish Microbiology Database (MiBa) operated by SSI plays an integral part in infectious disease surveillance in Denmark (Statens Serum Institut, 2023a). MiBa is a national database that comprises (i) microbiology test results from ten clinical microbiology laboratories covering all regions of Denmark, (ii) test results from SSI, including selected SARS-CoV-2 results from the WGS Center, (iii) Test Center Denmark (established in April 2020 to respond to the increased testing needs for SARS-CoV-2; (Statens Serum Institut, 2023c) and (iv) SARS-CoV-2 PCR and Antigen test results from private laboratories. Laboratories reporting to MiBa use different laboratory IT-systems (LIS) with their own local data codes and structures. In MiBa, the incoming data is harmonized by standard data transfer protocols (e.g. XRPT05, XRPT06; (MedCom, 2023b)) published by MedCom, a public non-profit organization responsible for the development of data standards in the Danish health sector (MedCom, 2023a). In MiBa, local codes are mapped and transferred in real time to a database called EpiMiBa, which is a mirrored version of MiBa used for surveillance purposes. Over recent years, the purpose of infectious disease surveillance has shifted from merely identifying a pathogen to also monitoring associated properties (e.g. subtypes, genetic profiles, resistance mechanisms etc.). Currently, not yet all clinical microbiology laboratories are technically equipped to report microbial properties or molecular level information of pathogens in MiBa in a structured way and report properties in local codes or in free text. This makes data cleaning and analysis for surveillance outputs cumbersome. To address this challenge, the aim is to implement a revised national data transfer protocol in MiBa, i.e. the data standard called "XRPT06 32M" that allows standardized reporting of properties and the use of common codes, instead of free text and local codes. Information on properties in MiBa is independent of laboratory methods used and will cover old as well as new typing methods, including WGS. In addition, information on method principle used (e.g. PCR for Stx-2d) is included in the test report. With the expanding use of WGS in clinical microbiology, there is an urgent need for a structured data model that can handle the rapidly increasing amount of molecular details reported. Relevant properties need to be determined by pathogen. The focus of this pilot is on SARS-CoV-2 variants and STEC as representatives for viruses and bacteria, respectively.

Pilot objectives

1. To agree on the classification of molecular level information for SARS-CoV-2 variants and microbial properties STEC in Denmark
 - To make an inventory of relevant molecular level information or microbial properties with respect to patient treatment, surveillance (laboratory and epidemiology), outbreak

- investigation and public health research (e.g. estimating vaccine effectiveness, assessing severity etc.)
 - To agree on common terminology for properties, a common data structure and associated reporting codes for uniform reporting to MiBa
- 2. To revise and further develop the currently implemented data standard "XRPT06 30M" towards the revised data standard "XRPT06 32M" that will use common codes and be able to handle properties in a standardized way
- 3. Technical integration of the revised data standard "XRPT06 32M" in the majority of clinical microbiology laboratories in Denmark

Status of the work – January-October 2023

- *National Workshop on XRPT06 M32, Integration of Properties and National Classification of Laboratory Results* conducted from 8-9 February 2023 in Vejle, Denmark
 - Participants included microbiologists, physicians, surveillance and health IT specialists, public health researchers and other relevant roles
 - The program of the workshop focused on objective 1 listed above
 - After the workshop, clinical microbiology laboratories submitted ideas on how to revise the current data model so that properties could be handled in a standardized way
 - Figure x shows the agreed-on revision to the data standard
- Completed the revision of the data standard "XRPT06 M32" and submitted to MedCom for evaluation (see objective 2, Figure 35)
 - Medcom has collected the documentation and has sent it to SSI and the vendors of the IT systems operational at CMLs for consultation.
 - All parties involved have agreed on the new data standard, the new data standard will be published on MedCom's website (expected in quarter 1) and the technical developments have begun for the IT vendors
- Working group established with aim to discuss the use and principle of how to work with microbial properties. In addition, the working group will describe guidelines for the use of properties for CML.
 - First meeting planned in October 2023.
- Pilot timeline is on track

Planned work – November 2023-September 2024

- Continue implementation of the revised data standard "XRPT06 M32" in the CMLs
- Adapt EpiMiBa so that it can receive the new data and can be used in the surveillance system
- Ensuring progress in the working group

Challenges

Potential competing priorities at CMLs and risk that central IT developers from the suppliers are not available (e.g. due to illness etc.) might affect the pilot timeline.

Explanation of terms:

Property: The property/ characteristic that is relevant to monitor, e.g. "STEC" or "Stx". An infinite number of properties can be added in the data standard.

Property analysis: The analysis (one or in combination with others) that is carried out to investigate whether the property of interest is present, e.g. "PCR for Shiga Toxin (Stx) gene". An infinite number of property analyses can be added in the data standard.

Specification: Specification of the property, e.g. "-2a" for the property "Stx". The specification field is a free text field as a starting point.

Variant: This specifies the property analysis in case more variants exist. E.g. the variant "-2d" for the property analysis "PCR for Stx gene". The variant field is a free text field as a starting point.

Figure 35. a) Property structure of revised data standard "XRPT06 32M" that will be able to handle microbial properties and molecular level information in a standardized way. New developments of "XRPT06 32M" compared to the current "XRPT06 30M" are highlighted in green. b) shows an example how STEC and c) how SARS-CoV-2 variants will be reported in "XRPT06 32M"

4.4 Subtask 5: Pilot in Finland

Background

In THL, needs, gaps and deficiencies were noticed in collecting and storing information in the current Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS) and the National Infectious Diseases Register (NIDR), as well as in transferring data between the systems and reporting to clinical microbiology laboratories. These constraints particularly hampered the epidemiological surveillance of STEC. Both a new THL LIMS and a technically updated NIDR have been planned to be implemented, with the aim to improve and broaden our data collection, storage and reporting.

Pilot objectives

- To describe a STEC data model and study how it can be integrated in the national surveillance in Finland.
- To update and modify the laboratory surveillance tools (THL LIMS and NIDR) to meet the requirements of the STEC data model.

Status of the work – January-October 2023

- A central part of the STEC data model has been identified and described.
 - Reporting steps with more results to NIDR and to clinical laboratories
- The updated NIDR is in production since 3 October 2023
- The THL LIMS is under construction.
 - New tests, analyses, and parameters have been created for the new THL LIMS.
 - In addition, instrument connections from LIMS to RT-PCR machines used for STEC isolation and isolate characterization, are currently under construction. The connections will be made through the generic instrument interface available in the new THL LIMS. This will allow an automatic two-way connection between LIMS and instrument enabling transfer of sample ids from LIMS to instrument and the results [cycle threshold (ct)-values] from the instrument to the LIMS.

Planned work – November 2023-September 2024

- Adding the collection and transfer of epidemiological data into the STEC data model, e.g. travel, symptoms, farm contact
- Defining a timeline which information should be available at which point
- Making the necessary modifications to NIDR to receive/store both typing results and epidemiological data
- Developing and testing the API from the THL LIMS to NIDR (to transfer typing results) and from NIDR to THL LIMS (to return epidemiological data)
- HL7 piloting between a clinical laboratory (ISLAB or HUSLAB) and THL LIMS
- Launching and testing the epidemic view in LIMS to link laboratory data and epidemiological data
- Testing the robustness of the data model by using data from ongoing STEC case or cluster

Challenges

The THL LIMS is planned to be in production in September 2024. All the nomenclature and connections can be created and tested while it is under construction. However, testing the timeline or data transfer to TESSy can only be accomplished after THL LIMS is in production.

4.5 Subtask 6: Pilot in Norway

Background

According to the Infectious Disease Control Act (Helse- og omsorgsdepartementet, 2003), the Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH) is responsible for the surveillance of infectious diseases in Norway as well as for contributing to international surveillance of infectious diseases. This work is facilitated through the Norwegian

Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases (MSIS) and the National Reference Laboratories (NRLs). The NRLs are obligated to perform both patient and public health-oriented core functions, including i) reference diagnostics, ii) maintaining reference material resource, iii) give scientific advice, iv) collaborate on research, and v) perform surveillance, alert, and response to outbreaks.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, Norway established a national laboratory database (MSIS laboratory database) for real time monitoring of test activity of SARS-CoV-2. The MSIS laboratory database (MSIS-lab) is an important add on to the laboratory-based surveillance of SARS-CoV-2, however currently not in use for other pathogens. A combination of data from the MSIS-lab and NRL database will improve the laboratory surveillance of infectious diseases in Norway.

STEC reported to MSIS.

All positive laboratory results matching with the notification criteria for clinical STEC cases are reported along with a clinical notification from the patients' doctor to MSIS. Case based results are stored at a centralized server environment in Norway. Reporting is both paper-based and utilizes the existing technical infrastructure for reporting within the Norwegian Health Network (NHN). NHN is a closed network specifically designed for electronic messaging exchanges in the healthcare sector in Norway. The network is a secure digital arena for all stakeholders in the sector.

STEC reported to the MSIS laboratory database.

All laboratory results, both with and without findings, from all medical microbiology laboratories (MMLs) in Norway, irrespective of whether the laboratory is public or private are reported to the MSIS-lab. The results are stored at a centralized server environment in Norway. Reporting utilizes the existing technical infrastructure for laboratory reporting within NHN.

Data is accessible for NIPH within minutes after the laboratories have sent the test results. This facilitates real-time surveillance and daily reporting both nationally and internationally. The use of a national identity number, which is unique to every individual, allows the data from the database to be used linked to other national data sources.

STEC submitted to the National Reference Laboratory.

All MMLs that examine human-samples in Norway are obligated to send samples or isolates along with preliminary laboratory results to the NRL for verification and detailed characterization (MSIS act § 2.4a; (Helse- og omsorgsdepartementet, 2003). The requisition, including metadata and available laboratory results is sent together with the sample/isolate by mail from MMLs to the NRL.

A rapid microbiologically based risk assessment to identify STEC with a high potential of causing the life-threatening complication haemolytic uremic syndrome is performed by PCR (*stx2* subtyping) on all STEC isolates. Subsequently, STEC isolates are routinely whole genome sequenced to identify serotype, virulence genes and clusters. All the molecular data, as well as the metadata, are stored in the Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS) of NRL. Results from isolate characterization (virulence genes, *stx*-subtype, serotype, sequence type and cluster type) are reported to MSIS and MSIS-lab.

Pilot objectives

Both NRL and MMLs electronically report results of diagnostic tests and genotypic characteristics to MSIS and MSIS-lab. However, the reporting is a non-standardized automated machine-to-machine reporting. This requires exhaustive data managements and compilation resources and present a risk for misclassification and ultimately inadequate date for effective real-time surveillance. This pilot aims to develop standardized reporting and data analyses protocols to enhance the laboratory-based surveillance of STEC in Norway.

1. We will develop a data management protocol for diagnostic test data on STEC reported to the MSIS-lab, covering the range of all possible tests, methodology and reporting forms. The data management protocol will be based upon the existing SARS-CoV-2 model.
2. We will explore the possibility of data transfer protocols between NRL and MSIS-lab and use diagnostic data from the MSIS-lab and genotypic characterization data from the NRL molecular database to enable an integrated real-time laboratory surveillance of STEC in Norway.

Status of the work – January-October 2023

- Assessed the diagnostic test data on STEC reported to MSIS-lab, getting an overview of the diversity of codes, and reporting practices at the different laboratories to identify targeted areas for better harmonized reporting.
- Started developing a questionnaire for MMLs to better understand the diagnostic flow of utilized tests and reporting procedures.

Planned work – November 2023-September 2024

- Complete, send out and analyse the questionnaire on diagnostic and reporting practices at the MMLs.
- Compose a standardized reporting schema based on existing national reporting codes.
- Provide recommendations to MMLs for harmonized STEC reporting.
- Explore legal and technical requirements and possibilities for integrated NRL and MSIS-lab surveillance.

Challenges

MMLs are autonomous bodies which implement diagnostic test protocols and reporting practices according to their given needs and resource allocations. Harmonized test protocols and reporting practices may therefore become a challenge, as long as the laboratories are fulfilling their legal requirements. Individual LIMS systems may also pose a challenge for some laboratories to adhere to recommendations from NIPH. Both legal and technical constraints may be a challenge in the implementation of an integrated laboratory-based surveillance system for real time surveillance using NRL and MSIS-lab database.

5. Task 2 – Description of work & main achievements

5.1 Background

Task 2 on “Outbreak and Signal Detection” focuses on improving algorithms for outbreak detection using routine surveillance data of infectious diseases and is directly linked to the UNITED4Surveillance project goal to ensure better detection of early warning signs and to strengthen infectious disease surveillance systems at the national level. As the performance of outbreak detection methods depends on the availability and quality of surveillance data, the task is also interlinked with task 1 on “Improving laboratory-based reporting” and in the future, tools could potentially be integrated into hospital surveillance systems addressed by WP 3. Through early detection of infectious disease outbreaks, the further spread of diseases can potentially be contained, thereby reducing harmful consequences (Steele et al., 2016). Automated signal detection using tools can thereby help to identify specific events of concern and manage and foster automated data analysis. The timelier and more reliable the signals are, the more they can contribute to comprehensive surveillance and allow for timely implementation of outbreak management measures. The automatization of outbreak detection is especially useful in the context of growing availability of surveillance data and limited human resources, as an efficient detection through manual detection of events is not always possible (Salmon et al., 2016; Simonsen et al., 2016).

Previous work in the field has shown that already in 2010, six institutes in five European countries used automated outbreak detection methods for routine surveillance data to support public health actors in epidemiological evaluation and outbreak detection of infectious diseases. Based on the existing systems and practical experiences, recommendations including the regular evaluation of outbreak detection systems and aiming for a user-friendly tool directed at epidemiologists were drawn (Hulth et al., 2010). Additionally, a workshop held in 2017 brought together stakeholders from 17 institutions across Europe, reflecting the interest to further improve algorithms and exchange expertise across countries. The workshop concluded with recommendations to further exchange data and experiences, provide visual outputs for users and to assess and compare algorithms of outbreak detection (Ghozzi & Ullrich, 2017).

While there has been continuous work across Europe on this topic, many countries do not yet use any methods or tools for automated outbreak detection or use methods that have been designed for other surveillance systems and datasets than their own. There are also no published evaluations of outbreak detection methods for a broad range of surveillance systems that would support the choice of an appropriate method according to local needs and context. Although it has been pointed out that routine evaluations could support the further development and improvement of algorithm performance, report generation, and user-friendliness, there is currently no evaluation framework available to assess the overall performance of an automated outbreak detection tool.

Task 2 aims to address these challenges and gaps by developing tools validated across different datasets from different countries and surveillance systems and deploy them in MS for the timely and accurate detection of outbreaks in surveillance data with the overall objective to increase the capacity of MS running an automated outbreak detection tool. The work under Task 2 is carried out by four subtasks:

Subtasks 1: Review of outbreak detection activities

This subtask consists of several steps:

- Conducting a survey and workshop on the types of surveillance systems and outbreak detection methods currently used by the MS.
- Identifying gaps and needs in detecting outbreaks from routine surveillance data.
- Define common terminology for different aspects of surveillance data and outbreak detection.
- Specify common use cases for outbreak detection.

Participating institutions/ countries: NPHC/HU, NVSC/LT, MoS/ES, RKI/DE
The work carried out within this subtask is described in section 5.2.1 and 5.3.1.

Subtask 2: Benchmarking of outbreak detection methods

This subtask consists of two steps:

- Developing an evaluation framework that allows useful comparison of outbreak detection methods for different use cases, including the use of several appropriate performance metrics.
- Evaluating outbreak detection methods on a diverse set of datasets either through data sharing or federate evaluation.

Participating institutions/ countries: AGES/AT, THL/FI, SSI/DK, NPHC/HU, NVSC/LT, RKI/DE
The work carried out within this subtask is described in section 5.2.2 and 5.3.2.

Subtask 3: Tool development

This subtask focuses on developing tools for outbreak detection and evaluation:

- Outbreak detection methods that were developed in earlier tasks, already exist as ready to use tools or available legacy code from active outbreak detection system have to be provided as tools with a consistent interface in terms of input data and resulting signals.
- An evaluation tool that can be performed on different datasets and with the developed outbreak detection tools has to be provided to the piloting MS.

Participating institutions/ countries: AGES/AT, SSI/DK, THL/FI, RKI/DE
The work carried out within this subtask is described in section 5.2.3 and 5.3.3.

Subtask 4: Piloting and training

This subtask consists of several steps:

- Deploying the developed tools from subtask 3 in order to identify the most relevant outbreak detection methods for the local context of the piloting systems.
- Continuous use and evaluation of the outbreak detection methods.
- Reviewing experiences and tools, the results will be provided for interested MS.

Participating institutions/ countries: RIVM/NL, MFH/MT, NPHC/HU, NIJZ/SI, NIH/PL, SSI/DK, THL/FI, RKI/DE, HPSC/IE, CDPC/LV, NVSC/LT, MIN SAUDE/PTThe descriptions of planned pilots are outlined in section 6.

5.2 Description of the work carried out

The following section describes the work carried out under subtasks 1-3 in the first year (2023) of the project. While subtask 1 has been completed, the work under subtasks 2-3 reflects preliminary results and preparatory work as part of an iterative process that will continue throughout the project duration.

5.2.1 Review of outbreak detection activities

In order to get an overview, the survey “needs and gaps analysis on automated outbreak detection tools for routine surveillance data” among participating MS was conducted aiming to gather information about

1. the types of surveillance systems with existing automated outbreak detection including the methods, and
2. the types of surveillance systems in MS with a potential for automated outbreak detection, and
3. identifying gaps and needs for automated tools detecting outbreaks from routine surveillance data.

Survey development

The survey was jointly developed with NPHC (HU), NVSC (LT), RKI (DE) and MoS (ES) over approximately one month in March and April 2023. During the kick-off meeting of the project in February 2023, active partners were asked to provide a first input for the survey on topics that should be covered in order to describe the needs of MS for an early warning system, hurdles and challenges in setting up an early warning system. This activity was followed by three subsequent meetings with active partners involved in subtask 1. After the first brainstorming on topics and questions and further elaboration of these, the first draft of the survey was shared with all task 2 active partners. Feedback was incorporated and the survey was constructed using the EUSurvey platform. Prior to distribution of the survey among the MS, a pilot test was carried out with subtask 1 active partners using the EUSurvey platform aiming to rule out any technical issues and to test the logic flow of the survey.

Scope of the survey

The survey comprised two main parts 1) description of public health surveillance system and 2) automated outbreak detection tools. The first part covered questions on the type, disease groups, and data collected within the surveillance system for infectious diseases. It was assumed that in MS several public health surveillance systems exist. Due to heterogeneity of surveillance systems, responsible authorities and stakeholder on MS level and the aim of the task to identify existing use cases as well as prospective application of the developed tools, the participants were asked to choose one of the national public health surveillance systems for which an automated outbreak detection is already in place or which would be most suitable for automated outbreak detection tools in order to complete the survey. The second part was further divided into a section on resources for automated outbreak detection tools, a section on signals and outbreaks and one on existing tools specifically covering questions on the tool characteristics and performance. The survey primarily addressed the systems, methods and data available at national levels of MS. The survey consisted of 33 questions of which 22 questions were mandatory. The section on signals and outbreaks should only be filled in if the participating institutions have a surveillance system with tools in place or plans to implement these. Questions were mainly single or multiple choice, ranking and followed by free text fields to further elaborate on a given answer. The questionnaire is presented in Annex 6.

Terminology used

To ensure a common understanding the participants were provided with a definition of the following terms at the beginning of the questionnaire:

Automated outbreak detection is the process of comparing the current epidemiological situation to a baseline (usually based on historic and/or geographic data) using some form of outlier detection. It processes surveillance data in a way that demographic and geographic characteristics are considered. The detected outliers or signals are usually summarized in a table or descriptive report.

Case-based vs. aggregated data: Case-based data is surveillance data that is collected and processed in a way that each entry represents one case or report of an infection or disease event, whereas aggregated data summarizes the number of cases or reports in groups, e.g. by regions, age groups or other demographic information.

Historic data are surveillance data that were collected by the same surveillance system which will be used for the automated outbreak detection and that can be used to estimate a baseline against which the current surveillance data can be compared. These data may have to be adjusted for trends or shifts.

Library: A library for automated outbreak detection is a repository of programming code that provides functions for detecting signals (outbreak warnings) in surveillance data and possibly further functionality for reporting these results.

Tool/software: A software or tool for automated outbreak detection that takes surveillance data as input and provides the resulting outbreak warnings in the form of an automatically generated report or summary table. We will use the term “tool” for this survey.

Warning/Signal: A warning or signal is an outlier in a subset (e.g., a region or age group) of the surveillance data. An outlier is an anomalous number of cases or reports compared to a historic or geographic baseline. We will use the term “signal” for this survey.

Data collection and analysis

The survey was distributed on 17 April 2023 by the UNITED4Surveillance coordination to one selected contact point of the 25 countries participating in the consortium. If one country was represented in the project consortium by several organisations, the most suitable institution was selected by task 2 lead. Since the survey needed to be completed by more than one expert (e.g. epidemiologist and data scientist), it was recommended that the contact point jointly fills in the survey with relevant national experts online. For awareness and facilitation, the survey was also distributed by ECDC among the NFP for Surveillance. The initial deadline for response was set for 5 May 2023 and was extended to 12 May 2023.

Survey results were analysed using RStudio and Excel and were first presented during a workshop on outbreak detection use cases under task 2 end of May 2023. The workshop was used to present and discuss the survey results and attending participants had the opportunity to comment on the results.

Workshop on outbreak detection use cases

The onsite workshop on outbreak detection use cases was held at RKI in Berlin with 30 participants from national public health institutes of 16 countries (AT, BE, HR, DK, EE, FI, DE, HU, IE, LV, LT, MT, NL, PL, PT, SI). It brought together a diverse group of experts from public health, epidemiology and data-science. The workshops’ objectives were to

- 1) meet active partners and other interested participants,
- 2) review existing outbreak detection systems and discuss gaps and needs,
- 3) identify relevant use cases for outbreak detection and
- 4) discuss next steps and the pilot phase.

The workshop was organized and hosted by the Unit for Surveillance and Electronical Notification- and Informationsystem (DEMIS) at the Robert Koch-Institute (RKI). Countries, who were interested in piloting the tools and countries, who were interested in tool development were asked to prepare a presentation on piloting aim and automated outbreak detection methods. The entire consortium of the JA was invited to participate in the workshop in person. Due to limited capacities on site participation was limited to two persons per institution. Online sessions were offered for the presentations on the survey results, overview of the work package outbreak detection within AI4Health on the first day. Prior to the workshop one meeting with active partner institutions took place to prepare and exchange expectations. A detailed report of the workshop can be found in Annex 7.

5.2.2 Benchmarking of outbreak detection methods

The goal is to perform a fair and systematic evaluation of different outbreak detection methods on a set of realistic surveillance data. As a first step, a review of scientific literature on outbreak detection methods and studies evaluating and comparing such methods was performed. From this, a list of outbreak detection methods, evaluation strategies and performance metrics was gathered.

Based on the insights of evaluation schemes described in the literature and the needs and experiences in the MS, an evaluation framework and analysis plan were proposed and discussed. This encompasses the definition of the required input data format allowing an extensive evaluation. The description of the data format and

required metadata was adapted to the needs and possibilities of the MS. Standard operating procedures and additional validation and evaluation tools were provided to the MS. Since several MS had issues with sharing case-based surveillance data with additional outbreak information, the validation and evaluation tools had to be developed in a way that they can be used locally without sharing potentially sensitive data with external partners. This led to a delayed development of the overall evaluation framework and the realisation of the evaluation itself. Yet, it has also led to the development of additional tools for validation and evaluation that will potentially result in a better user experience for the final outbreak detection tools and enables us to more easily extend the evaluation to further MS or even external surveillance systems. Due to the delay, we have decided to collect the evaluation results in a dynamic report that is available within the project consortium. The report will be updated whenever new methods, evaluation analyses or datasets are added. This may again lead to a more extended evaluation analysis than previously planned.

5.2.3 Tool development

The process of tool development started with a design session during the workshop in May 2023. Participants from piloting and tool development MS were identifying use cases and collecting functional and technical requirements. Furthermore, they had the task to specify goals for the outbreak detection tools according to the SMART criteria, i.e. relevant enough goals for the piloting MS to be useful and realistic enough for the tool development team to succeed in the given time. Goals were defined for the overall aim, the surveillance data to be used, the handling of the tool, necessary resources, the output of the tool and how it should be communicated. The results of the group work were discussed in a following session and a final list of use cases and requirements were agreed upon.

Data scientists from assigned MS (AT, DE, DK, FI) have decided to develop R-packages (independent software modules written in the statistic programming language R) for outbreak detection and the evaluation of outbreak detection methods. The development process ought to follow an open source software development process with the programming code residing in a repository on a public hosting site called *github.com* to which all participants have access and through which the resulting code and tool can be shared publicly. The development process is thought to be agile, i.e. trying to achieve a minimum viable product as soon as possible and then adding further features with each round while maintaining a viable product. A roadmap with goals for each development round was developed. The *github.com*-platform also allows to define tasks (there called "issues") which are used to define new features, report bugs and discuss concepts. In bi-weekly meetings the progress of the previous round (last 2 weeks), open questions and the upcoming tasks as well as overall design decisions are discussed. So far there have been about ten project meetings with around eight to ten attendees and eight rounds of development. The progress reports and meeting protocols are stored on the Microsoft teams channel. Furthermore, the *github.com* platform records the changes in the programming code and the defined tasks, acting as a transparent project management and tracking tool. Thus far, all participants from assigned MS (AT, DE, DK, FI) have contributed to the development process (provided programming code, documented new tasks, participate in design discussions) and the success of the project meetings. In addition, two participants from Croatia and one participant from Belgium have contributed to the development and discussions.

Most of the goals that were defined in the initial roadmap for the current rounds were achieved and the project is on track to provide a functioning outbreak detection tool by the start of the piloting phase and refine the tool until the deadline in March of next year. The evaluation tool has functioning programming code to perform an evaluation and output evaluation results. The tool was extended by a graphical user interface so it can be used by the piloting MS themselves on their local system. It is planned to add further metrics and outbreak detection methods even after the deadline of the deliverable.

5.3 Results

5.3.1 Review of outbreak detection activities

Needs and gaps analysis on automated outbreak detection tools for routine surveillance data

General aspects

Out of the 25 MS invited to take part in the survey, 21 questionnaires were completed representing 21 countries and institutions and a response rate of 84% (Figure 36). A detailed overview of survey respondents' answers per country including free text can be found in Annex 8. All survey respondents work in the public health sector, with the majority working at national institutes of public health (n=19; 90%) and the remaining working for the Ministry of Health (n=2; 10%), whereby Spain indicated that the organisation falls both under the ministry of health and national institute of public health.

Figure 36. Map of UNITED4Surveillance consortium countries invited to participate in the survey
 The countries of survey respondents are coloured in dark blue: Austria, Belgium, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Estonia, Spain, Finland, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, The Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Sweden and Slovenia. The countries who were invited to take part in the survey but did not respond are coloured in light blue: Cyprus, France, Italy and Norway

Surveillance system

The development and regular use of outbreak detection tools depends on the type of surveillance system and available and adequate surveillance data on which the tool is deployed. Two countries (9%) indicated to have an automated outbreak detection tool for the chosen surveillance system in place (DE, FI). In ten countries (48%) the implementation of automated outbreak detection tools in the surveillance system is planned and nine countries (43%) reported to have no automated outbreak detection tools planned or in place, but where such tools would provide a potential benefit (Figure 37).

Figure 37. Distribution of automated outbreak detection tool status for the chosen surveillance system in 21 participating countries

In order to get an overview of the chosen surveillance systems, respondents were asked to provide the name, type and data source of the system. The provided names of the surveillance systems such as “National Public Health Information System” (HR) or “The Information System of Infectious Diseases” (CZ) displayed that 18 countries (86%) chose the statutory infectious disease surveillance system in order to complete the survey. Three countries (14%) chose surveillance systems for specific diseases and pathogens, namely COVID-19 (SI), STEC (NL) and the national surveillance system for salmonella (BE). Yet, BE noted that while the survey was filled out for surveillance of salmonella answers could be extrapolated to other food- and waterborne diseases (FWD) pathogens, potentially also for other non-FWD diseases with outbreak potential. The most frequently reported types of surveillance systems were laboratory-based (n=19; 90%) and GP-/primary care-based (n=14; 67%) followed by hospital-based (n=11; 52%) and event-based systems (n=9; 42%). Molecular and sentinel surveillance system (n=3; 14%) were the least commonly included systems (Figure 38). Overall, in 90% of the countries the reported types of surveillance systems are mandatory. DK noted that an amendment of the current act for notifiable diseases is expected and will make reporting of infections monitored in the chosen database mandatory. In the NL case-reports are mandatory but information on the molecular or isolate is voluntary.

Figure 38. Types of surveillance systems for the chosen surveillance system
Multiple answers per country were possible given that one system can fulfil several attributes

Figure 39 shows the reported disease groups for which the surveillance systems are designed. This information indicates potential use cases for outbreak detection tools and for which disease groups the tool would provide a potential benefit. FWD diseases (n=19; 90%), air-borne diseases (n=18; 86%) and vector-borne disease and zoonotic disease (n=17; 81%) were the most common disease groups. AMR (n=9; 43%) and healthcare-associated infections (n=8; 38%) are not as extensively covered by the systems, whereby some countries attempting to expand the systems to AMR.

Figure 39. Disease groups for which the chosen surveillance systems are designed. Multiple answers per country were possible

The implementation and performance of automated outbreak detection tools primarily rely on the availability and information available at the national level. Therefore, the survey covered several questions on data sources, variables and geographical resolution. For almost all systems across countries data stems from laboratories (n=20; 95%), hospitals (n=19; 90%) and GP/primary care (n=18; 86%) (Figure 40).

Figure 40. Data sources of the chosen surveillance systems. Multiple answers per country were possible

Almost all survey respondents stated that data is reported case-based (n=20; 95%) and on a daily base (n=19; 90%) to the national level. If data is reported case-based, in 12 countries (60%) some personal identifiable data (e.g. address, date of birth, personal identity number) is available. Two countries (10%) indicated that a case identifier is available at national level and can be used to communicate and get further information from regional authorities. An overview of information routinely reported to the national level is displayed in Table 4. Yet, countries noted that the information available depends on the pathogen and if an investigation of the cases was conducted. Additionally, 15 countries (71%) indicated to have address information available at national level, whereby this was revised mostly by all countries during the workshop and clarified that this is only visible at lower level such as local or county. Further, historical data is needed for the development of automatic outbreak detection to take baseline comparison, trends and seasonality for the development into account. The survey revealed that historic data for 20 years or more are available in 10 countries (48%), in 8 countries more than 8 years of historic data and in all countries at least 3 years of historic data can be used.

Table 4. Variables routinely reported to the national level
Multiple answers per country were possible

Variables routinely reported to the national level	Total number of countries n (%)
Pathogen	21 (100)
Age	21 (100)
Sex	21 (100)
Geographical information (address/region)	21 (100)
Laboratory method	20 (95)
Date of laboratory confirmation	19 (90)
Death	19 (90)
Disease	18 (85)
Data of symptoms onset	17 (81)
Hospitalisation	17 (81)
Possible exposure (e.g. epi-link)	15 (71)
Vaccination status	15 (71)
Symptoms	14 (67)
Molecular and genomic typing	14 (67)
Date of clinical diagnosis	12 (57)
Risk factors	11 (52)

Automated outbreak detection tools

All survey participants were asked to answer the section on resources for automated outbreak detection tools, even if their chosen surveillance system does not (yet) have automated outbreak detection tools or are planning to implement them. The questions should be answered on the resources that were available at that point in time or can be made available in the foreseeable future to implement tools aiming to identify challenges and gaps. As Figure 41 shows, funding is very limited in most countries, particularly for research on automated outbreak detection tools, as well as resources for data science research, which includes the development and extension of methods (pink). More resources seem to be available for maintenance and initial set up to implement the automated outbreak detection tool.

Figure 41. Rating of available resources for running an automated outbreak detection tool
Five indicating fully available resources and one indicating no resources available

In line with this, sustainable funding (n=14; 67%) and data quality issues (n=9; 43%) were the most commonly reported challenges faced when developing and implementing tools, followed by legal mandate challenges (n=5; 23%). Additionally, respondents from five countries mentioned to have shortage of personnel and qualified personnel is often committed to other projects. In three countries the prerequisite for implementing tools such as having a proper IT-infrastructure and linkage between systems has been pointed out as a barrier. One country summarized that the development of automated outbreak detection tools is not prioritized high enough.

Signals and Outbreaks

The section on signals and outbreak detection was completed by all survey respondents, regardless if signals stem from a tool or manual inspection. In all countries signals once verified, are followed by epidemiological investigation and public health intervention measures are implemented if necessary. In most countries the investigation is undertaken by an epidemiologist or public health expert. In countries with a decentralized system, local or regional health authorities are contacted to gather more information and if needed initiate further measures and outbreak investigation. Moreover, feedback on the subsequent public health action is given in 67% (n=14) of the countries in forms of videoconferences, reports or through email communication to the national. In half of the countries (n=11; 52%) feedback is collected in a systematic way, while only eight countries (38%) actually use the feedback to evaluate outbreak detection signals and the approach, in order to implement changes and improvements.

Automated outbreak detection tools

Information on automated outbreak detection tools were provided by 13 countries (62%) given that they already have a tool in place or planning to implement one. Some countries added that the tool is under development and tool's characteristics are not fully developed. Out of those 13 countries, 6 (29%) use or plan to use a self-developed solution (e.g. R or Stata scripts), two countries (10%) referred to existing open library (e.g. surveillance) and in one country the tool is based on an external software (e.g. SATSCAN). The most commonly reported statistical method used is time series outlier analysis (n=4; 19%) and two countries use spatial clustering analysis (10%). Two countries reported to explore R scripts/ R shiny to implement a tool in the near future and two other countries did not provide any further information regarding the tool indicating to be at an early stage of planning. Various formats of output data and presentation of results are used across countries including dashboards, graphs, situation reports, lists or tables and excel or CSV files. Demographic information stratified by age group is used/available in nine countries.

At the end survey respondents were also asked to share their ideas how existing tools can be improved. One survey respondent commented that *"resulting signals should be better summarized and tested through other information channels in order to reduce the number of signals. Reporting could be more flexible so as to reflect the different objectives of the users"*. Another respondent suggested to add criteria about the point of time when to initiate an investigation as they have refined these based on experiences in the early years of WGS availability.

Workshop on outbreak detection use cases

The survey results were presented on the first day of the workshop on outbreak detection and were complemented by country presentations and panel discussions. Throughout the presentations, many similarities between the pilot countries were apparent, especially on the aim and how and what kind of data is collected and is often based on similar types of registries. All countries aim to implement automated outbreak detection methods to foster a timely detection of potential outbreaks and to compensate for staff shortages. For instance, WGS surveillance provides more detailed data on pathogens and larger data sets in the Netherlands emphasizing the necessity for automated outbreak detection. Countries routinely follow-up on signals, whether generated manually or automated and initiate investigation when needed. However, reporting and evaluation of the signals and the results of investigations is only carried out systematically in a few countries. Presentations of active partners during the workshop displayed the heterogeneity of national surveillance systems placed in different organizational structures, capacities and population size as well as quite a diverse set of different use-cases. Additionally, deviating from reporting requirements mandated by law, cases are often reported with a time delay and at varying speeds across countries.

Tool development countries gave a brief overview on different algorithms and approaches used for outbreak detection in the respective countries. Germany and Finland an established automated outbreak detection system. Austria and Denmark are planning an implementation of automated outbreak detection tools. Tools are mostly self-implemented scripts and some established statistical methods like SATSCAN, the MEM-method or methods provided in the surveillance R-package having the potential for making methods usable for others. The participants agreed on the importance of considering the different users of the tool during the development phase. Yet, evaluation of the tools is much up to discussion as outbreak detection systems are currently not being systematically evaluated.

During the ensuing discussion, funding and IT resources were the main challenges identified for the piloting countries when developing and implementing automated outbreak detection tools. Maintenance and running the tool once it has been implemented are considered to be more feasible. Piloting countries stressed the lack of qualified IT personnel being available and addressed the need for support to deploy and run the tool. Countries and participants experience in automated outbreak detection tools pointed out that without having access to and knowledge about the IT systems, technical support would be challenging. Collaboration and assistance within the project activities and the created network as a possible support system for arising challenges was advocated for by all participants. Arising from the discussion on data sharing between pilot and tool countries, a defined minimum set of variables shall be shared within the project.

Further one part of the discussion evolved around the questions on how to define an outbreak, when to give a signal and how to prioritize signals. Only a limited number of outbreaks can be followed-up due to limited human resources and competing tasks. Ireland and the Netherlands use a defined set of questions to prioritize signals and determine which should be investigated. As this initial assessment is qualitative, it requires expertise and experience and therefore it was questioned if these could be adopted into an algorithm. Nonetheless, binary questions would be feasible to implement. A few participants mentioned WGS surveillance as an emerging method that can enhance outbreak detection and integration with epidemiological data and thus should be considered for automated outbreak detection.

On the second day, participants engaged in breakout sessions deeper into generating ideas for piloting and tool development. Piloting countries worked on "what an ideal outbreak detection tool looks like" and tool countries

focused on “outbreak detection tools we want to provide”. Results of the sessions were documented and presented in poster format. Through the discussions and collaborative exercises with a transnational perspective, it became apparent that there are different needs and priorities in the piloting countries. The desired and identified use cases for automated outbreak detection ranged from gastroenteritis to respiratory diseases. The conversation unfolded with the question of how signals should be reported and whether a dashboard should display one disease group or several as well as differentiating between internal and external dashboards. Underlying issues of the discussion are that signals are managed by different experts in the countries with varying IT competencies emphasizing the necessity of user-friendly, easy to use and adaptable tools. The envisioned generated output data should be capable to granulate by local level and be user-friendly for national level experts. In the context of evaluating the pilot, a brainstorm session yielded several proposals, considering the specificity, sensitivity, timeliness, usefulness, satisfaction, ease of use of the tools and comparison to manually detected outbreaks, allowing for public health interventions. This was also reflected by the discussion and vision of tool countries, who aim to provide an effective solution for early detection of outbreaks and enable the monitoring of clusters. Thereby, case-based, routinely collected, historic and if possible, regional data should be the basis of the tool. Ideas on tool evaluation also included sensitivity, specificity, timeliness and user feedback. In order to serve the needs of the pilot countries, it was expressed that these have to share surveillance and historic data.

In the further course of the project and as the survey was designed in a such a way that information about only one surveillance system per country could be gathered, the Netherlands added to their survey contributions, emphasizing that an active surveillance system with automated outbreak detection tools is in place in the Netherlands. The system is using an R shiny surveillance dashboard for multiple pathogens such as: CPE, Gonorrhoea, Group A Streptococcal (GAS), Hantavirus, Hepatitis A, B and C, Haemophilus influenzae type B (hib), Legionella, Leptospirosis, Listeria, Measles, Meningococcal disease, Mumps, Paratyphi A, B and C, Pertussis, Psittacosis, Query fever (Q-fever), Rubella, SARS-CoV-2, Shigellosis, Tuberculosis, Typhoid fever.

5.3.2 Benchmarking of outbreak detection methods

We have performed a systematic evaluation of different outbreak detection methods (see table 5 for a list of used methods) on real world surveillance data from several MS (see table 6 for a short description of the used data sets). For this we have stratified the data by county, age group, pathogen and subtype and then aggregated by week of report to derive timeseries. Each timeseries was then analysed with the different outbreak detection methods and the resulting signals compared with the true outbreaks, several metrics were computed to inspect different aspects of performance (see table 7 for an overview of performance metrics). Comparisons were done per timeseries, per strata and overall.

Table 5. Systematic evaluation of different outbreak detection methods

Method	Short description	Reference
Farrington Flexible	Quasi-poisson regression method with trend and seasonality on a multi-year baseline	(Noufaily et al., 2013)
CUSUM	Cumulative sum statistical control chart approach	(Rossi et al., 1999)
EARS-C	Moving average and sliding window approach	(Fricker et al., 2008)

Table 6. Short description of the used data sets

Member state	Surveillance system	Pathogens	# of cases	# of outbreaks
Germany	Lab reported cases	Salmonella	> 80k	~2k
Germany	Lab reported cases	Campylobacter	>400k	~3k
Netherlands	Lab reported cases	STEC	~3k	~10
Malta	Lab reported cases	Salmonella	>1k	~100
Hungary	Lab reported cases	Varicella	>25k	~100
Poland	clinical and laboratory notifications	Salmonella	>25k	not provided (~5k cases in outbreaks)

Table 7. Overview of performance metrics

Metric	Short description	Reference
Sensitivity	Percentage of true outbreaks that were detected	-
Specificity	Percentage of generated signals that coincide with true outbreaks	-
False Positivity Rate	Ratio of false alarms and the number of time units without an outbreak	-
Average time before detection	Number of time units from start of the true outbreak until detection by the method	(Enki et al., 2016)
POD_x	Probability of detecting a true outbreak until time unit x	(Craig et al., 2023)

To evaluate the performance of a single outbreak detection method on a timeseries a plot showing the number of cases per reporting week, the found signals and the true outbreak is provided (see Figure 42 for an example). For the overall comparison the distribution of metrics is presented in form of a table (mean, median, IQR) and plot (boxplot). Tables and plots are generated for each strata as well as an overall performance comparison. The entire evaluation is summarized in Annex 10, examples are shown in Table 8 and Figure 43.

Figure 42. Timeseries plot with number of cases per week as column, the computed anomaly threshold as blue line, the generated signals in red and the true outbreaks in yellow. It can be seen that the algorithm produced one false positive alarm where there an alarm is generated but no real outbreak, two true positives were it correctly predicted the outbreak and one missed outbreak where it did not raise an alarm.

Table 8. Sample rows from the results table of the evaluation analysis. Each row shows the resulting mean and median one performance metric for one combination of one outbreak detection method, one stratification (e.g. by state, county, subtype or age group) and one dataset.

Method	Strata	Dataset	Metric	Measure (mean, median, IQR)
cusum	State	Germany CAM 2014-19	Sensitivity	0.55, 0.57 (0.4-0.68)
ears	State	Germany CAM 2014-19	Sensitivity	0.03, 0.03 (0.0-0.05)
farrington	State	Germany CAM 2014-19	Sensitivity	0.05, 0.05 (0.01-0.07)
cusum	State	Germany CAM 2014-19	Specificity	0.70, 0.66 (0.57-0.83)
ears	State	Germany CAM 2014-19	Specificity	0.98, 0.98 (0.97-1.0)
farrington	State	Germany CAM 2014-19	Specificity	0.96, 0.97 (0.94-1.0)

Figure 43. Sensitivity comparison for the three outbreak detection methods on the seven different datasets. The points show the mean sensitivity measure averaged over all regions on the state level.

5.3.3 Tool development

Several tools have been developed for the purposes of outbreak detection, the evaluation of outbreak detection methods and to check the correct input data format. All tools are written in the statistical programming language R and an easy-to-use user interface is provided to input the surveillance data and inspect results.

Outbreak detection tool

The outbreak detection tool was developed as an *R* package and provided as a binary for easy installation only requiring a current version of the free software *R*. In addition to the tool, documentation to its installation and use is provided with a guided tutorial. The tool provides functionality to run a dashboard or generate a report, the report can also be generated from the dashboard. The dashboard is organized in several tabs leading the user to inspect their surveillance data and the signals produced from the outbreak detection methods that are performed in the background, see a Screenshot of the dashboard structure in Figure 44. The dashboard includes a "Help" section that contains a short tutorial with instruction for the use of the dashboard and description of the methodology and terminology. In the "Data" section the user can upload the surveillance data for which the outbreak detection should be performed and set some filters to restrict to specific regions or time intervals. The input format is a line list of infectious disease cases, the detailed description of the input data can be found in Annex 9. The user can set parameters (e.g. pathogen, method, stratification) for the outbreak detection analysis in the "Parameter" section of the dashboard and then start the computation with the push of a button. Once the analysis is finished the user can change either to the "Signals" tab for a dashboard like exploration of the surveillance data and generated signals or to the "Report" tab to initiate the generation of a report. Both in the dashboard and the report several plots and tables are shown, examples can be seen in Figure 45.

United4Surveillance Signal Detection Tool

Figure 44. Screenshot of the top part of the outbreak detection dashboard showing the organisation in different tabs.

Figure 45. Screenshots of plots showing different aspects of the surveillance data and generated signals

Evaluation tool

Similar to the outbreak detection tool, the evaluation tool is a tool in the R programming language and provides a graphical user interface in which the user can load their surveillance data and immediately perform analysis and inspect and export the results. The tool generates signals for the provided data with several outbreak detection methods and compares it with the provided true outbreak information, from which it computes several performance metrics and summarises the results in plots and tables as discussed in section 5.2.3. Furthermore, the output can be exported in a file that then can be shared because it does not contain any personal data.

Data validation tool

Since the users have to run the outbreak detection and evaluation tools by themselves, it is essential that they input their data in the correct format to ensure the correct behaviour of the tools. To this end, a data validation tool was developed that allows the easy upload of surveillance and outbreak data, see Figure 46 for a screenshot of the UI of the tool. The tool then performs a comparison of the input data with the description of the required data format. Thereby, the correct column names, column format and used entries in the columns are checked. The mismatches are listed with a short description of the required changes.

DataCheckTool

Figure 46. Screenshots of the UI and output of the Data validation tool

On the left, a file dialogue can be seen where the user selects their input data to be tested. On the right, the results of the validation are shown, first all required columns are checked for its format and entries, then mismatches to the allowed columns is are listed.

5.4 Evaluation and conclusion

In summary, the work carried out under task 2 in the first year of the UNITED4Surveillance project provided an overview of surveillance systems with existing automated outbreak detection including methods and surveillance systems with a potential for automated outbreak detection in the participating MS. Further, an overview and evaluation of three different outbreak detection methods was provided as well as preliminary results of the tool development.

The survey results provide an overview of the types of surveillance systems with existing automated outbreak detection tools including the methods as well as an overview of the systems with a potential for automated outbreak detection in 21 countries of the UNITED4Surveillance consortium. Overall, the findings reveal a heterogenic landscape, with countries already using automated outbreak detection tools or being at different stages of planning to implement chosen methods. While only three countries have tools in place, the implementation of tools is planned in 10 countries. The reported surveillance systems, which would be suitable for automated outbreak detection, include sufficient historic data, daily and case-based reporting and additional information on cases. This demonstrates the need, interest and potential in MS for automated outbreak detection tool and supports the overall aim of the activities.

Additionally, the existing tools predominantly consist of self-implemented scripts utilizing some established methods specifically tailored for the local context and system. Drawing from the survey results and the subsequent workshop discussions, it is evident that collaborative efforts are crucial to navigating the complexities of implementing and refining automated outbreak detection tools for different systems across countries. The survey results highlighted diverse needs and priorities, emphasizing the necessity for flexible, user-friendly tools that can adapt to the unique requirements of different countries.

Insights into the varies forms of output data and how signals are presented, highlighted also the different preferences, priorities and the need for flexible outputs provided by the tool. Additionally, in most of the countries an assessment of feedback mechanism via communication means or reporting about outbreaks takes place, while there is not always a comprehensive and systematic way of evaluation methods in order to

implement changes and improvement. The introduction of new methods for outbreak detection offers a chance to implement a systematic routine feedback mechanism and evaluation approach and activities. Further, the survey as well as the workshop consolidated that the implementation of automated outbreak detection activities in itself in MS are not systematically embedded in surveillance systems and overall surveillance strategies and therefore lack of adequate sustainable funding, staff and expertise making this activity vulnerable to reprioritization or discontinuation if challenges such as change of staff or increased workload arise.

Yet, the survey has some limitations. While the results present an overview and are valuable in course of the further project activities, the survey was limited to only one chosen surveillance system per country as it would have been too comprehensive to assess all surveillance system being available in the MS and the goal was to identify potential piloting sites or existing tools to be included in the project. Further, it should be noted that the survey was filled in by only one or two respondents per country. The information represented in this report may depend on the respondent's expertise and some important aspects from certain countries may not have been covered in this report.

The investigation into the field of benchmarking for outbreak detection methods has shown that there is a wide range of approaches that provide extensive comparisons of a large number of methods. The used metrics are often similar and allow a good comparison of the methods performance from different perspectives. Most benchmarking approaches either use simulated data or a rather limited real-world dataset specific for one country or one task. In this work package, a very diverse repertoire of datasets is collected from different surveillance systems (e.g. country, type) for different use cases (e.g. pathogen). This allows for a more realistic comparison of outbreak detection methods beyond pure performance towards actual usability and utility within the context of its use in public health surveillance.

The process for the development of tools for outbreak detection and benchmarking outbreak detection methods has been defined and already led to three preliminary tools that are being tested by the piloting countries. The aim is to develop the tools in an agile way and open source, i.e. viable tools will be provided to the piloting MS in a regular fashion while adding new features and adapting to changing requirements throughout the process. Given the current progress, it is expected to have fully functional tools until March 2024. Furthermore, the tools are developed on the github.com platform which will allow it to provide the tools openly to the public. This also enables to maintain and extend the tools through community contributions even beyond the project timeline. Even during the current development process further contributors have joined, raising the hope of establishing such a community.

Ultimately, the survey and workshop outcomes provide valuable insights into the current state of automated outbreak detection among MS within the consortium of JA United4Surveillance, laying the foundation for the planned pilot phase with the identified use cases of gastroenteritis and respiratory diseases as well as the benchmarking of different methods and the tool development progress.

6. Task 2 – Descriptions of pilots

Building upon the workshop discussions, country presentations, and active partner meetings, the subsequent section offers a detailed description of the envisioned pilots for each country, in which the developed tool under subtask 3 will be deployed. Aligned with the initial discussions in the workshop, the countries' selected use cases primarily focus on gastrointestinal diseases, with an additional use case on respiratory diseases. The pilots aim to deploy and test the tool on real-time surveillance data in different EU countries and to evaluate the tools' ability to identify outbreak in a timely and precise manner. The group of pilot countries expanded from initially seven to eleven countries, reflecting the high interest in piloting and using the Signal Detection Tool. However, as Latvia, Lithuania, and Portugal joined later, no pilot descriptions are available for these countries.

6.1 Denmark

Aim

Finding signals for outbreak detection is currently to a large degree performed as a manual process SSI. For some diseases, a pre-assigned multidisciplinary team, with experts in microbiology, epidemiology and data management, regularly look directly into current surveillance data on cases or specific lab tests. For other diseases there are no systematic evaluation of signals. As an example, a large outbreak of Group A streptococci (GAS) was discovered in January 2023, after a number of other countries reported an increase in incidence. This prompted establishment of a multidisciplinary team and development of a data algorithm-based case definition for GAS in our infectious disease surveillance system.

Standardized case definitions integrated with an automated signal detection tool will contribute to discovering outbreaks earlier while a reliable automatic presentation of a signal will free up time spent at regularly revisiting raw data looking for any potential outbreaks in the first place.

Our aim with the pilot study is to evaluate the automated signal detection tool using GAS as use case. This will allow testing a counterfactual scenario for the known increase in incidence of 2023 as well as determine how well the tool can support current operational processes for more timely and efficient GAS monitoring and outbreak detection.

Surveillance system

A new Ministerial Act entered into force November 1 2023, expanding the list of notifiable diseases from 42 to 90 and this also now directed to regulate digital automated laboratory reporting. Regional Departments of Clinical Microbiology report real-time laboratory data to the national Danish Microbiology Database (MiBa) managed by DIAS at SSI. MiBa plays a central role in the surveillance system data flow. Based on standardized codes data flows at the level of individual tests into a data mart called Keys to Infectious Disease (KIDS), which defines populations for each disease by applying data algorithms and business rules to interpret microbiology lab reports and define cases. This forms the final data for the disease surveillance system. Some of the diseases are then subsequently coupled with demographic, other personal data and health care data to form a case-based line list.

Pathogens/syndromes

The surveillance data we intend as use case for automated outbreak detection is directly tapped from a line list based on KIDS data with personal level data available. We will focus on infections with GAS which has historical data going back to 2018.

Relevant variables in surveillance data

Mandatory variables in our dataset:

Case_id

- We have directly case-based data and can make a running number.
- In addition, we have civil registration numbers (CPR) which can be pseudonymized to individual-level ids.

Date_report

- Date for when the sample has been probed.

Country and Country_id

- We can add country of residence based on the CPR number. Our laboratory data is from Denmark only and we have no data regarding country of exposure.

Age & Sex

- Age at Date_report as well as Sex can be extracted from the [CRPR](#) number.

Age_groups

- Can be made from the age variable above.

Pathogen

- Is the same for the whole dataset.

Optional variables in our dataset:

County and County_id

- "Region", the 5 Danish counties and associated NUTS-2 codes.

Community and Community_id

- "Landsdel", smaller province-like communities and associated NUTS-3 codes.

Date_death

- Can be added by coupling to CPR register.

Death

- From the one above

Hospital admissions in general are available but rules defining which admissions are related to GAS (e.g. time window around GAS diagnosis) are not defined clearly in our surveillance system.

Extra variables in our dataset:

Severity

- Invasive / non-invasive

Based on a categorization of sample materials. Materials indicating an invasive infection are ranked higher than others, i.e. blood cultures supersede throat swabs in cases that have multiple samples taken.

Reporting

The plan is to send an e-mail to the multidisciplinary GAS team at SSI, whenever a signal is detected to prompt them to look closer into the case numbers to evaluate whether the signal should be declared as an outbreak and needs of a higher level of preparedness.

Challenges

Currently none, or to be determined.

6.2 Finland

Aim

Our primary objective in implementing automated outbreak detection tools is to improve the surveillance of the infectious diseases. Now, many diseases lack automated surveillance and clinical experts typically contact the people responsible for the surveillance, once they observe increased number in cases in clinical work. However, this approach often results in delayed responses, making it imperative to acquire this information sooner.

Deployment of automated signal detection tools serves as a solution to this issue, minimizing labour intensive manual case checks. This, in turn, optimizes resource allocation, freeing up valuable time and ensuring more efficient utilization of resources for other critical tasks. Furthermore, the implementation of automated outbreak detection tools aligns with our urge in preparing for future epidemics and pandemics, enhancing our ability to respond swiftly and effectively to emerging health crises.

In 1994 there was a hepatitis A outbreak among drug users in Finland. It took time and effort to keep up to date with the situation and some clinical experts even walked down the streets to try to reach potential infected persons. In this case, an automated outbreak detection tool would have been beneficial, enabling us to identify the outbreak significantly earlier.

Surveillance system

Surveillance of infectious diseases in Finland is mandatory by law (Communicable Diseases Act) and is mainly based on the National Infectious Diseases Register (NIDR). The NIDR consists of notifications from physicians and laboratories and covers nearly 40 different diseases. Physicians use a web-based notification form for reporting cases. Laboratory notifications are seamlessly transmitted from labs to NIDR ensuring swift and direct communication. Our surveillance system is based on centralized model and THL administers the system. Surveillance system is complemented by several other registers, such as National Hospital Discharge Register and Register of Primary Health Care Visits, which provide valuable support to the system.

Figure 42. Surveillance of infectious disease at THL

Pathogens/syndromes

Our surveillance data include cases of Salmonella and Campylobacter infections. Data structure is case-based and anonymous however, we do have access to the personal data as well if necessary. The data covers years from 2018 to 2023.

In the dataset, Campylobacter is represented by a single pathogen group. In contrast, the Salmonella includes three distinct pathogen groups: Salmonella Typhi, Salmonella Paratyphi, and other variants of Salmonella.

Relevant variables in surveillance data

The surveillance data consists of seven variables:

- Case id: Unique identifier for a specific case.
- Country: Name of the country in which the case was reported (Finland in this case).
- Country id: Id of the country in which the case was reported in NUTS-0 format.
- Pathogen: Name of the pathogen that was identified.
- Reporting date: Date when the case was reported in ISO 8601 format.

- Age group: Age group of the reported case at the time of reporting by five-year age grouping.
- Sex: Sex of the reported case, one of male or female.

The data include all mandatory variables from the input variable list. Due to our strict data sharing policy, we had to limit our data to only mandatory variables.

Reporting

During the piloting, the generated signal can initiate various actions, such as reaching out to local health authorities, conducting contact tracing, or collecting samples. The choice of communication method will depend on the intended audience. Specifically, when dealing with Salmonella and Campylobacter outbreaks, clinical physicians and local health authorities are the primary recipients of information. In this context, email notifications or concise PDF reports would prove highly beneficial. However, if we decide to share the generated signals to the public, key finding or figures could be reported on our disease-specific web pages which are publicly available.

Challenges

Currently, our organization lacks a well-defined long-term strategy for the utilization and advancement of automated outbreak systems. It is important, that we address this gap and establish a clear plan for development and utilization of automated outbreak systems. Furthermore, our IT personnel are currently engaged in various critical tasks, so we need to ensure resources for maintenance and development in the future.

6.3 Hungary

Aim

One of the lessons learned by the COVID-19 pandemic that the improvement of the IT system is necessary. We have a system to notify communicable diseases. We have been using the current IT system (OSZIR) since 2014. According to the plans the new system is going to connect the patient database system of health care providers (National eHealth Infrastructure) and our IT system (database of the notifiable diseases). This means the new system is going to be on a higher level regarding automatic operation. We plan to involve outbreak detection tool in the new system.

Surveillance system

The notification system in Hungary is based on the Act XLVII of 1997 on the Management and Protection of Health and Related Personal Data and the Decree 1/2014. (I.16.) of the Minister of Human Capacities on the regulation of notification of communicable diseases. This system provides case-based notification with detailed personal and address data and constantly up-to-date data: notification is compulsory within 24 hours of the diagnosis (even of the suspicion of the disease). The system is comprehensive and nation-wide: all physicians (GPs, specialists working in outpatient clinics, physicians working in hospitals, at emergency service, pathologists, microbiologists) should report suspected, probable or confirmed cases. The EU case definitions are used for classifying reported cases, particularly as for laboratory criteria.

There are three administrative function levels within the public health system in Hungary:

- national level: National Center for Public Health and Pharmacy (NCPHP). The role of NCPHP is coordination of surveillance (including health care associated infections), public health response, operation and development of the national immunization programme etc.
- county level: 19 county institute – the Public Health Departments of the County Governmental Offices. Their roles are providing co-ordination, data analysis and evaluation, sampling and laboratory services etc.

- local (district level): 80 subregional public health institutes – within the District Offices of the County Governmental Offices. They are the principal enforcement authority, they are doing field work and inspections, outbreak investigations.

The notification system is centralised, there is only one national database, physicians report into this database and each public health institute at every level – can see the data of their area. There is an obligation for the health care workers to notify any case or event, if a notifiable infectious disease or any healthcare-related infection occurs cumulatively or epidemically (suspicion of an outbreak) and if any other infectious disease occurs in an unusually severe form or occurs with a significantly higher frequency than usual (in a specific period and in a specific area). It is obligatory for the healthcare workers to report if they notice an accumulation of food-borne illnesses, and this obligation also applies to the managers of institutions/events (festivals, camps, etc.), especially where they provide care for children.

Pathogens/syndromes

We have a large surveillance database; data are electronically available backward (since 1991) for a lot of diseases/pathogens (about 75 entities). As there is an obligation to notify any outbreak especially foodborne outbreak, we consider an automated outbreak detection would be useful to detect not just foodborne but to detect other e.g. airborne outbreaks. We have quite comprehensive case-based data for most of the notifiable diseases/pathogens (entities) which includes personal data, address data, laboratory, hospitalization data.

Relevant variables in surveillance data

For most entities we have the following data:

- Case-id
- File number
- Creation method (e.g. reported by physician; based on laboratory result)
- Case type (e.g.: symptomatic patient; asymptomatic carrier) Patient classification (suspected/probable/confirmed)
- Start of illness
- Start of illness unknown
- Responsible public health organization County
- Patient insurance number
- Patient insurance number type
- Patient name code
- Patient name
- Patient gender
- Patient date of birth
- Patient age in years
- Patient age in months
- Patient's place of birth
- Patient's country of birth
- Patient's job title (given answer options)
- Patient's job title – text
- Patient's workplace
- Patient's workplace address
- Place of treatment (at home/hospital)
- Place of infection (or address)
- Notified illness
- BNO code of notified illness
- Epidemiological name
- Date of hospital admission
- Name of hospital
- Date of hospital discharge

- Outcome of illness
- Date of death/complication
- Complication diagnosis
- Complication BNO code
- Import case
- Suspected country of infection
- Sample collection date
- Sample type –
- Pathogen
- Pathogen type
- Test method
- Laboratory result classification
- Sporadic/Outbreak
- Postal code
- Place of exposure
- Time of exposure
- Mode of spread
- Spreader
- Creation date
- Creator
- Last modification date
- Last modifier
- Closing date
- Epidemic identifier
- Epidemic name
- Epidemic confirmed diagnosis
- Case classification comment
- Patient phone number
- Patient e-mail address

Reporting

The local public health authority has to investigate any outbreak of which they become aware. If the national level (NCPHP) recognizes a sign, we have to report it to the local level. They decide on the investigation (its extent) and on the measures. They have to send a report to the national level about any outbreak investigation.

Challenges

We have no real knowledge, experience about the automated outbreak detection tools. We plan to develop and introduce a new system which is going to connect the patient database system of health care providers (National eHealth Infrastructure) and the public health IT system (database of the notifiable diseases). We plan to involve outbreak detection tool in the new system.

6.4 Ireland

Aim

Our aim is to have an automated detection tool which provides an objective evaluation of the weekly number of reported cases of gastroenteric disease and has the potential to indicate the occurrence of an outbreak. In particular, we are interested in a system that recognises exceedances in particular population subsets. Examples where this would have been useful in the past include: increase in shigellosis in adult males, or increase in cryptosporidiosis among Irish residents returning from travel to Spain. Exceedances will be communicated to

relevant national health protection office staff and infectious disease consultants in regional health offices as relevant.

Surveillance system

The Computerised Infectious Disease Reporting (CIDR) database captures data on 80 of the 89 notifiable diseases in Ireland. Both laboratory directors, general practitioners and other medical officers are required to notify their regional medical officer of health of all episodes of notifiable diseases, and these data are captured in this centralised database which is shared between laboratory, regional public health staff and national staff at HPSC. Access is controlled according to role, and HPSC have access to pseudonymised data. It also captures data on outbreaks of disease (which are notifiable in their own right), and it is possible to link individual cases of disease with their associated outbreak. Further information on how notifiable diseases are reported, how the HSPC handles notifiable disease data and what the computerised infectious disease reporting (CIDR) system is, can be found on the HPSC official website (Health Protection Surveillance Centre, 2023).

Pathogens/ syndromes

A list of infectious diseases notifiable in Ireland is available at the HPSC official website as well (Health Protection Surveillance Centre, 2022).

The diseases we intend to prioritise in this pilot include: salmonellosis, campylobacter infection, shigellosis, cryptosporidiosis, VTEC infection and giardiasis. Anonymised case-based data are available since 2004, and for salmonella, cryptosporidiosis and VTEC, there is a sizeable amount of outbreak data available, with linked case information, for evaluation purposes.

Relevant variable in surveillance data

Variables available at the time of notification include age, sex, geographical area (regional health authority), date of reporting to CIDR, and to some extent country of infection. WGS data are available for all salmonella, shigella, listeria, VTEC cases, and for a subset of campylobacter cases. Serotype and AMR can be inferred from this, but would not be available the same week as the notification is made. Extensive disease-specific 'enhanced' are also collected, but again maybe not timely or complete enough to incorporate on a same week analysis.

Reporting

In the very near future, HPSC will publish a Notifiable Disease Information Hub for all 80 diseases using data from CIDR. Updated on a weekly basis, this hub will contain an epidemiological description of the current week for each of the diseases, and a number of time series plots with metrics (counts, rates, etc) for case numbers overall, and by age, sex, geographical distribution, and hospitalisation status. This is currently made available on a pilot basis in-house, with a view to making available on our website in the New Year.

This cluster detection pilot will be an adjunct to the hub, but this output would likely be made available either as a list or on a restricted dashboard cascaded for review by regional and national colleagues. The outputs will be incorporated into an existing process we have for evaluation of other clusters, e.g. WGS clusters flagged by reference laboratories. The evaluation process takes into account size and cluster, rate of evolution and other data available when deciding on what is the appropriate response.

Challenges

Ireland has a relatively low number of weekly notifications (only 5M population), and the likelihood of reaching a statistically significant finding may be lower that with a dataset with larger case numbers for a larger population.

6.5 Malta

Aim

The Infectious Disease Prevention and Control Unit (IDCU) is the national surveillance unit for infectious diseases in Malta responsible also for the public health management of infectious disease cases/outbreaks. Currently the unit does not have any available automated outbreak detection tools and also no automated surveillance tools to analyse data and trends on a regular basis. Clusters and outbreaks, most commonly of food-borne illness, are usually detected following telephone interviews with notified laboratory confirmed cases.

Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) capacity in Malta is limited and only started being rolled out for Salmonella and Campylobacter by the Pathology Department at the main state hospital (Mater Dei Hospital - MDH) since October 2022. This delayed cluster detection limits the effectiveness of public health interventions. The implementation of an automated outbreak detection tool at IDCU would therefore allow for a rapid detection and management of outbreaks.

Surveillance system

IDCU is the national surveillance centre for communicable diseases in Malta which is also responsible for the public health management of infectious disease cases/outbreaks. The unit is part of the Health Promotion and Disease Prevention Directorate, under the Department of Health Regulation within the Ministry for Health. Further details on IDCU can be found on the official webpage: <https://hpd.gov.mt/idcu>

Malta has a publicly funded-healthcare system at primary, secondary and tertiary level. A centralized Pathology Laboratory based in MDH routinely receives samples from public institutions including primary care and long term-care facilities.

Being a small MS country, surveillance is centralised with no distinction between local/regional/national levels. IDCU collates data on a total of 73 statutory notifiable infectious diseases through notification from various sources, mainly: Public and Private laboratories; GPs and health practitioners; Schools, Nurseries and Long-Term Care Facilities; GU clinic at MDH; National Blood Transfusion services; Environmental Health Directorate; Death certificates; and from direct notifications by the public and community. Reported cases are investigated by IDCU staff and further information is gathered on symptoms, exposures, travel etc. Further public health measures are taken as necessary. IDCU collates and reports surveillance data regularly on the official webpage and to WHO/ECDC as part of its obligations.

Figure 43. Infectious Disease Surveillance Data flow

The legal basis for surveillance relies on the following 3 legislations:

- The **Health Act** defines the role of the Department of Health Regulation including "to prevent communicable and non-communicable diseases and carry out surveillance and control in order to protect the general public from such diseases" (" Functions and Responsibilities of the Department of Health Regulation Regulations (391 of 2013)," 2013).
- The **Public Health Act** of Malta obliges clinicians and laboratories to report notifiable infectious disease to public health authority as part of the prevention and control of infectious diseases CAP. 465 Part IV ("Public Health Act," 2003).
- Subsidiary Legislation 528.10 on **Processing of Personal Data (Secondary Processing - Health Sector)**, allows the processing of personal data for the purpose of public health surveillance ("Processing of Personal Data (Secondary Processing) (Health Sector) Regulations (263 of 2019)," 2019).

Pathogens/syndromes

Food-borne illness outbreaks, specifically those caused Salmonella and Campylobacter are the ones most commonly reported in Malta. In view of this, Salmonella has been selected as the pathogen of choice for use of automated outbreak detection. As IDCU is also responsible for the case management of infectious disease cases, personal, case-based data is available for Salmonella. Historical data for Salmonella is available for many years with more complete, electronic data being available from at least 2010.

Relevant variables in surveillance data

The following list highlights the variables available for Salmonella that are relevant for the calculation of exceedance thresholds and deployment of the outbreak detection tool.

Table 9. Relevant and available variables for salmonella

Variable name	Explanation
case_id	Unique identifier for a specific case, but nothing that can be used to identify the case or patient within the national surveillance system
outbreak_status	Indication whether the case is known to be part of an outbreak, YES, NO, Unknown
outbreak_id	Unique identifier for the specific outbreak to which the specific case belongs to, but nothing that can be used to identify the case or patient or outbreak within the national surveillance system
date_report	Date when the case was reported
date_onset	Date when symptoms started
country	Name of the country in which the case was reported
Address	Locality the case resides in
Imported	If infection was likely acquired abroad
Imported country	Country infection imported from
age	Age of the reported case at the time of reporting as integer between 0-125
age_group	Age group of the reported case at the time of reporting as interval, e.g. 05-14 for cases with an age between 5 and 14 years
sex	Sex of the reported case, one of male, female, diverse, unknown
pathogen	Name of the pathogen/diagnosis that was identified
serotype	Salmonella serotype identified
hospitalization	Indication whether the case was hospitalized, YES, NO or unknown
death	Indication whether the case has died, YES, NO or unknown
symptoms	List of symptoms that were observed

Reporting

Malta has a centralised surveillance system. IDCU is responsible for surveillance of infectious diseases as well as for the public health management of infectious disease cases and outbreaks and data reporting. In view of this, signals generated by the tool will be assessed and evaluated within IDCU and outbreak investigations will be launched accordingly.

Challenges

The IDCU has various functions including infectious surveillance, case management and control, reporting, teaching and training amongst others. The limited human resources at IDCU especially related to data and project management and lack of analytical/statistical support challenges the optimization of surveillance activities. There is also limited IT expertise to assist with technical issues. IDCU is also in the process of upgrading its database to a web-based platform as the current access-based platform does not allow for standardized data inputting and automated report generation. Malta has a population of only 535,064 and therefore the case numbers reported weekly may be too low to allow for significant detection. In addition, WGS capacity is still being developed and therefore cannot be used as yet for timely outbreak detection.

6.6 The Netherlands

Aim

Implementation of automated outbreak detection could help to all work in a standardized way with less time effort. Keeping overview and detecting clusters is still a lot of manual work and therefore time consuming. Furthermore, a list of different pathogens is surveilled in the Netherlands by several people all with their own methods of how to do surveillance.

Surveillance system

Notifiable diseases are reported to the regional public health service by the physician and/or the laboratory. The health service contacts the patient for gathering extra data on for example disease and risk factors and reports it in the online system Osiris. On national level, all notifications are gathered, monitored and analysed, which is done by the RIVM. For some diseases, there is also a voluntarily laboratory surveillance. Local laboratories are requested to send in the isolates of the particular pathogen to the RIVM for further typing. The NVWA (Dutch Food Safety Authority) is involved in case of leads towards contaminated food.

Figure 44. Infectious disease surveillance in the Netherlands. Pink lines: notification procedure; Blue lines: voluntary laboratory surveillance; Black lines: in case of leads of contaminated food; Green lines: communication within the care system.

Pathogens/ syndromes

In the pilot, data from the STEC surveillance will be used. Data is gathered case-based in a pseudonymized way. Surveillance of STEC O157 exists since 1999, STEC non-O157 was added to the surveillance in 2007-2008. As the notification criteria have been changed in 2016, data gathered since 2017 is used.

Relevant variables in surveillance data

As far as available, date of onset of disease will be leading for cluster detection as it is closest to the moment of exposure. Date of report can be used if date of onset is not available. Further stratification of the data for more precision will be on state/county level, age group and sex, however, outbreaks can be national and affecting all age groups. For specification of a cluster, subtyping (O-type in case of STEC) will be needed.

Reporting

When a signal is generated, data from the surveillance will be examined to determine if an outbreak investigation should be initiated. One of the steps are then to look whether WGS data are available and if so, whether there are also matches on WGS level.

Challenges

Currently, the automated outbreak detection will mainly be based on number of cases. Nevertheless, STEC consists of many different subtypes (O-types). This leads to two challenges: first, the number of STEC cases can already be quite high with only sporadic cases. Detection of small outbreaks will therefore be difficult. Second, it will be hard to decide who belongs to a cluster and who does not in case of a signal without subtyping/WGS data.

6.7 Poland

Aim

Since 2020, a new electronic epidemiological surveillance system - Epibaza has been implemented in Poland. The Epibaza system gathers data on all notifiable diseases in Poland. Notifications of cases from physicians (including electronically transferred directly to the system) and notifications of positive test results for selected pathogens detected in patient's specimens from laboratories are recorded in the system. Based on clinical and laboratory notifications, after their verification and classification, a case-based registry is created.

The primary users of the Epibaza system are employees from local, regional, and central departments responsible for the epidemiological surveillance of infectious diseases. Epibaza includes some additional tools and modules, including an alert module. Currently, in the system simple alerts are generated based on notification of cases of diseases such as meningococcal disease, VTEC and CJD. In the next step, we plan to implement in the system the tools enabling the detection of increases in the number of cases than expected. Therefore, the aim of the pilot is to test the outbreak detection tool offered by RKI partners on data from the case-based registry. After evaluation of the tool's effectiveness in generating an outbreak signal, we will decide about including it in the Epibaza system. Depending on the set of variables that will be used for the model generating an alert signal we will consider use data from the case-based registry or directly from notifications from doctors/laboratories.

Surveillance system

General information

The surveillance system in Poland is based on Act of 5th December 2008 on prevention and control of infections and infectious diseases in humans. Poland is divided into 16 voivodeships (administrative regions) and each voivodeship is subdivided into poviats. In total, there are 380 poviats. Poviats Sanitary and Epidemiological Stations (PSSE) (318) are responsible for routine epidemiological surveillance at local level; Voivodeship Sanitary

and Epidemiological Stations (WSSE) (16) at regional level; the Chief Sanitary Inspectorate and the National Institute of Public Health, National Institute of Hygiene (NIPH NIH-NRI) at central level. All these institutions closely cooperate.

Data flow

Any physician who has diagnosed or suspected an infection under surveillance, including death due to an infectious disease sends a notification including only basic information. Each laboratory which has a positive test result for an etiological agent of diseases under surveillance sends a notification including only basic information on positive test results to Poviats Sanitary and Epidemiological Stations (PSSE). The notifications can be provided by physicians or laboratories in the following ways: electronic-automated; paper-based; encrypted electronic documents via e-mail. The reports which are not sent automatically directly to the system must be entered manually (this should be done in real-time). For most diseases under epidemiological surveillance – based on information from notification, a “case report” is created in EpiBaza.

Outbreaks can be reported to sanitary and epidemiological stations by any person, including director/representative of any institutions, doctors, nurses, parents and other citizens. After receiving such a report, the PSSE is obliged to verify this information. When the outbreak is confirmed, the PSSE starts an outbreak investigation and collects all necessary data. PSSE then enters collected data into the ROE system. NIPH NIH - NRI verifies, compiles and then publishes national-level data in periodic, biweekly reports. After analysis, NIPH NIH - NRI provides case-based data to TESSy, and data on outbreaks to EFSA.

Electronic surveillance systems

The surveillance system in Poland is based on two electronic systems: EpiBaza and ROE (Electronic Registry of Epidemic Outbreaks) (Pol. Rejestr Ognisk Epidemicznych). EpiBaza is a case-based electronic surveillance system - as a registry of infectious diseases - which monitors the epidemiological situation through constant and systematic collection, analysis and interpretation of information on diseases or other processes occurring in the field of public health, used to prevent and control infections/infectious diseases. ROE is a national system for tracking foodborne and waterborne outbreaks and facilitating outbreak investigations. PSSE receives notification/information in case of an outbreak occurring or a suspicion of an outbreak. In case of an outbreak occurring, the PSSE enter data into ROE collected during outbreak investigations. The entered data is verified by the employees of WSSE and of the Department of Epidemiology of Infectious Diseases and Surveillance of NIPH NIH-NRI.

Figure 45. Flow of the Polish surveillance people system data from local to national and EU level

Pathogens/syndromes

In the first phase of the pilot, we will use case-based data on salmonellosis cases from the Epibaza registry for the years 2020-2022. We provided a set of anonymized case-based data to our RKI partners to run the model on their servers. Additionally, we will provide, a second set of data with extended range starting from 2017. After evaluation of the model output, we will consider the incorporation of this tool into the Epibaza system. If the automatically generated alerts for salmonellosis outbreak are deemed useful for decision-making, the application of the model will be extended to other pathogens belonging to the group of foodborne pathogens.

Relevant variables in surveillance data

As a part of the pilot, the following variables will be used to implement the tool:

- Basic variables: Case id, date_report, date_onset, country, country id, county - NUTS-2, age, sex, pathogen, outbreak_status.
- Additional variables: community, hospitalization and date of hospitalization, death and date of death, symptoms, occupation, serotype, outbreak id.

Reporting

After implementing the tool into the electronic surveillance system, PSSE and WSSE will be informed about the generated signal via the EpiBaza system - alerts. At the same time, an email can be sent to selected users informing about an alert in the system.

Challenges

Due to the lack of implementation of routine genomic surveillance for salmonellosis in Poland and the predominance of cases caused by *S. Enteritidis* (over 70% yearly), detection of non-clustered outbreaks which occurred in different parts of the country may be difficult. Additionally, not all regions perform serotyping at similar frequency. Moreover, salmonellosis is underdiagnosed and underreported in Poland (70% of reported cases are hospitalized), which may also require adjustment of model parameters.

6.8 Slovenia

Aim

To date, Slovenia still uses passive outbreak notification and sometimes manual analysis for outbreak detection. No automated outbreak detection tools have been developed yet, however some are in their initial development stages. With digitalization of reporting communicable diseases an automated tool would be helpful in a more active and timely detection of potential outbreaks (e.g. analysing routine data of chosen communicable diseases on a frequent base to look for any signals). The aim of implementing automated outbreak detection tools is to provide a more timely and comprehensive detection of clusters and outbreaks, in order to improve and speed up their management.

Surveillance system

Legal background of our surveillance system:

Act on communicable diseases (CD) (OJ 69/1995)

- List of mandatory reportable CD
- Mandatory reporting of CD outbreaks

Rules for reporting of CD and specific measures for their prevention and control (OJ 16/1999)

- who – medical doctors, microbiology laboratories
- time frame – CD arranged in 4 groups according to urgency for public health action
- what – list of variables
- how – case-based reporting forms
- whom – Regional units of National institute of public health (NIPH)

Act on databases in the area of health protection (OJ 65/2000) (list of variables, purpose, data providers, database manager, ...)

- CD database („Survival“)
- HIV/aids database, STD database
- Tuberculosis database

Organization of national surveillance and role of NIJZ and other stakeholders (Figure 1)

- **Medical doctors:** reporting cases and outbreaks of communicable diseases
- **Microbiology laboratories:** laboratory confirmation and reporting cases of CD, additional testing for public health purposes
- **Veterinary services:** reporting of all diseases or deaths of animals due to zoonosis
- **National Institute of Public Health:**
 - regional units: entry and review of case reporting forms of CD, epidemiological investigation, contact tracing, outbreak investigation, 24/7 preparedness, risk assessment with advice on preventive measures
 - CDC: management of national databases of CD, data analysis, preparation of reports, 24/7 preparedness (national contact point IHR, EWRS), risk assessment with advice on preventive measures
- **University Clinic of Respiratory and Allergic Diseases Golnik (tuberculosis):** treatment, contact tracing, outbreak investigation, management of national TB database, laboratory for mycobacteria
- **Ministry of Health:** legislation for surveillance, funding (data analyses, risk assessments)
- **National Health Insurance:** funding (databases management, clinical microbiology testing, public health microbiology testing)

Figure 46. Organization of national surveillance of communicable diseases and role of NIJZ and other stakeholders

Pathogens/syndromes

The surveillance data that we would like to use for piloting the automated outbreak detection tool

- Gastrointestinal pathogens (salmonellosis, campylobacteriosis, norovirus, rotavirus)
- Pseudonymised or anonymised case-based data (depending on project’s legal competencies)
- 5 years of historical data as well as data on outbreaks for the same time period from 2019 until September 2023

Relevant variables in surveillance data

Our list of variables is based on the basic descriptive epidemiological concept of outbreak detection – time, place, person concept. The relevant variables for the deployment of the tool on our dataset are:

1. `date_report` – reporting of the same disease in a close time frame can suggest a cluster/outbreak
To be able to declare the end of an outbreak (or a signal), a **double incubation period** of a pathogen must pass. For our chosen pathogen, these are as follows (Heymann, 2022):
 - salmonellosis: 6 days from the last reported (or last date of symptom onset?) case
 - campylobacteriosis: 20 days from the last reported (or last date of symptom onset?) case
 - norovirus: 4 days from the last reported (or last date of symptom onset?) case
 - rotavirus: 6 days from the last reported (or last date of symptom onset?) case
2. `date_onset` – an epidemiological investigation of cases can produce similar symptom onset for infected people in a close time frame, which can suggest an epidemiological link or a cluster/outbreak
3. `community` – if there is a geographical link of cases, this can suggest a cluster/outbreak
4. `age_group` – if a defined group of people close in age is affected (e.g. kindergarten, school, LTCF etc.), it can suggest a cluster/outbreak
5. `pathogen` – same pathogen or diagnosis in a close time frame and geographical span can propose a cluster or an outbreak.

Reporting

The initial plan would be to receive a signal from the tool (internal alert), only meant for the epi teams (e.g. regional epi teams would be notified by mail to check if the signal predicted an actual outbreak, has it already been reported to the regional unit etc.). A basic descriptive dashboard would be produced to be able to describe the signal in terms of time, place, person. If an outbreak is confirmed, an investigation and its management would follow. After an outbreak has been declared over, a report would be prepared.

Challenges

- Legal: national legislation on CD surveillance outdated, compliance of reporting entities inconsistent (data quality); The Health Information System Act – submitted for public consideration by the MoH (medical personal data are collected in one place, recorded according to uniform standards, properly secured – a consistent and efficient framework for the secondary use of medical data)
- Financial – funding guaranteed only for the piloting phase (U4S project), a more permanent implementation depends on the process of CD digitalisation in Slovenia (negotiations and implementation ideas to receive governmental funding in place at the moment)
- Technical – a simple tool, freely available (R code?)
- Personnel – any kind of training before piloting would be of great benefit for our data managers
- Data protection challenges – unable to share pseudonymized data if sharing parties don't sign a mutual agreement

7. Deviations from the work plan

Task 1

The finalization of milestone 22 “Logical Data Model”, that was due in month 9 (September 2023), was delayed by two months due to pending legal clarifications regarding whether sharing and displaying the entity-relationship model of an existing database potentially poses a cyber-security risk. This issue has been resolved and the milestone is expected to be finalized by the end of November 2023. Other milestones associated with task 1 are on track.

Task 2

As mentioned in section 5.2.2, data privacy issues and different interpretations of the GDPR among pilot countries delayed or hindered data sharing of sample surveillance and outbreak detection data needed for the evaluation of outbreak detection methods and made a further tool development necessary. Hence, the report linked to milestone 24 “Benchmarking”, due in December 2023 is a dynamic document that will be updated whenever new methods, evaluation analyses or datasets are added. Furthermore, the addition of outbreak detection methods is slightly delayed as internal scripts have to be exported as packages and one promising outbreak detection package got discontinued. Nonetheless, with the current approach of living documents on the internal project platform, further evaluation results and methods can be added in the course of work.

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9. List of abbreviations

AGES	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety
AIDS	Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome
AMR	Antimicrobial Resistance
API	Application Programming Interface
AT	Austria
AT	Austria
BE	Belgium
BE	Belgium
BSL-3	Biosafety Level 3
CD	Communicable Diseases
CDISC	Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium
CDPC	Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
CIDR	Computerised Infectious Disease Reporting
CL	Consiliary Laboratories
CML	Clinical Microbiology Laboratories
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease
CPE	Carbapenemase Producing Enterobacteriaceae
CSV	comma-separated values
CT	cycle threshold

CY	Cyprus
CZ	Czechia
DE	Germany
DEMIS	Deutsches Elektronisches Melde- und Informationssystem für den Infektionsschutz;
DK	Denmark
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
ebXML	eXtensible Markup Language
EC	European Commission
ECDC	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
EE	Estonia
EHDS	European Health Data Space
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
EOC	Emergency Operations Centre
ES	Spain
EU	European Union
EU-HIP	EU Interoperability with HERA's IT Platform
EWRS	Early Warning and Response System
FWD	Food and Waterborne Diseases
FHI	Folkhelseinstituttet
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
FI	Finland
FiRe	Finnish Study Group for Antimicrobial Resistance
FR	France
FR	France
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GAS	Group A Streptococcal
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GISAID	Global Initiative on Sharing All Influenza Data
GORAN	Global Outbreak and Response Network
GPs	General Practitioners
HAIBA	Hospital Acquired Infections Database
Hib	Haemophilus influenzae type b
HIV	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
HR	Croatia
HSE	Health Protection Surveillance Centre
HU	Hungary
ICD	International Classification of Diseases
IE	Ireland
IfSG	Infektionsschutzgesetz
IGS	Integrated Genomic Surveillance
IHR	International Health Regulations
ISIS-AR	Infectious Disease Surveillance Information System – Antimicrobial Resistance
IT	Information Technology
IT	Italy
KIDS	Keys to Infectious Disease System
LABA	Laboratory Database
LIMS	Laboratory Information Management System
LIS	Laboratory IT-systems
LOINC	Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes
LSP	Laboratory-based surveillance platform
LT	Lithuania

LU	Luxembourg
LV	Latvia
M. tuberculosis	<i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i>
MDR	Multidrug Resistant
MFH	Ministry of Health - Government of Malta
MHS	Municipal Health Services
MiBa	Microbiology Database
MIS	Meldesystemet for infektionssygdomme
MMLs	Medical Microbiology Laboratories
MoIH	Ministry of the Interior and Health
MoS	Ministry of Health (Spain)
MPF	Molecular Platform
MRSA	Methicillin-Resistant Staphylococcus Aureus
MS	Member States
MSIS	Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases
MT	Malta
NFPs	National Focal Points
NGS	Next Generation Sequencing
NIC	National influenza Centre
NIDR	National Infectious Disease Register
NIJZ	Nacionalni Inštitut za javno zdravje
NIPH	Norwegian Institute of Public Health
NIPH/ FHI	National Institute of Public Health/ Folkehelseinstituttet
Nivel	Netherlands Institute for Health Services Research
NL	Netherlands
NL	Netherlands
NLZOH	National Laboratory of Health, Environment and Food
NPHC	Nemzeti Nepegeszsegugyi Kozpont
NPU	Nomenclature for Properties and Units
NRL	National Reference Laboratories
NVSC	Nacionalinis Visuomenes Sveikatos Centras Prie Sveikatos Apsaugos Ministerijos
PCR	Polymerase-Chain Reaction
PL	Poland
PT	Portugal
Q-fever	Query fever
RAT	Rapid Antigen Tests
RIVM	Rijksinstituut Voor Volksgezondheid en Miljø
RKI	Robert Koch Institute
RO	Romania
ROE	Electronic Registry of Epidemic Outbreaks
SARS-CoV-2	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2
SDTM	Study Data Tabulation Model
SE	Sweden
SI	Slovenia
SIRO	Surveillance of Healthcare-Associated Infections: Finnish Hospital Infection Programme
SNOMED	Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine Clinical Terms
SRA	Sequence Read Archive
SSI	Statens Serum Institut
STDs	Sexually Transmitted Diseases
STEC	Shiga-toxin producing E. coli
TB	Tuberculosis

TESSy	The European Surveillance System
THL	Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare
ToU	Terms of use
TTL	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health
Type-Ned	Typing Network Netherlands
UCUM	Unified Code for Units of Measure
vCJD	Variant Creutzfeldt-Jakob Disease
VISUMS	State Infectious Disease Surveillance and Monitoring system
VTEC	Verotoxigenic Escherichia coli
WGS	Whole Genome Sequencing
WP	Work Package

Annexes

Annex 1. Consortium of the Joint Action UNITED4Surveillance

Country	Abbreviation	Entities
Austria	AT	Federal Ministry of Social Affairs, Health, Care and Consumer Protection; Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES)
Belgium	BE	Sciensano (Sciensano)
Croatia	HR	Croatian Institute of Public Health (CIPH); Ministry of Health
Czechia	CZ	The National Institute of Public Health (SZU)
Denmark	DK	Statens Serum Institut (SSI); University of Copenhagen (UCPH)
Estonia	EE	Health Board (HEALTH BOARD)
Finland	FI	The Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL)
France	FR	French Agency for food, environmental and occupational health & safety (ANSES); Santé publique France
Germany	DE	Robert Koch Institute (RKI)
Hungary	HU	The National Center for Public Health and Pharmacy (NPHC)
Ireland	IE	Health Protection Surveillance Centre (HPSC)
Italy	IT	Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS); Mario Negri Institute for Pharmacological Research, Ministry of Health; Tuscany Regional Health Agency
Latvia	LV	The Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (CDPC)
Lithuania	LT	National Public Health Centre under the Ministry of Health (NVSC)
Luxembourg	LU	Laboratoire National de Santé (LNS); Direction de la Santé
Malta	MT	Health Promotion and Disease Prevention Unit, Ministry for Health (MFH)
The Netherlands	NL	National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM); Wageningen Bioveterinary Research

Norway	NO	The Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH); Norwegian Veterinary Institute; Directorate of Health
Poland	PL	National Institute of Public Health – National Institute of Hygiene – National Research Institute (NIPH NIH - NRI)
Portugal	PT	Ministério da Saúde (MIN SAUDE)
Romania	RO	The National Institute of Public Health
Slovenia	SI	Slovenian National Institute of Public Health (NIJZ); National Laboratory of Health, Environment and Food; University Medical Centre Ljubljana
Spain	ES	Regional Ministry of Health and Families of Andalusia; Progress and Health Foundation; Ministry of Health (MoH); Instituto de Salud Carlos III
Sweden	SE	Public Health Agency of Sweden (FOHM)

Annex 2. Structure of Work Package 2 “Outbreak Detection”, including tasks, subtasks and active partners

Annex 1

United4Surveillance

Work Package 2 Task 1

Milestone 22

Logical Data Model for a Sequence Database

Contents

Introduction.....	3
Scope and separation of concerns.....	4
Use cases	5
Logical Data Model.....	7
Species and Taxon	7
Sample, Sequence and Contig.....	8
Locus and Allele	9
Alignment, Single Nucleotide Variant and Single Nucleotide Polymorphism.....	10
PCR detection results.....	12
Results derived from an individual sequence	12
Sequence distance	13
Physical Data Model.....	14
Immutability	14
Data compression and pre-computation	15
Custom identifiers and properties.....	16
Standardisation	17
General performance considerations.....	17
Testing	18
European Nucleotide Archive	18
Bacterial Isolate Genome Sequence Database	18
SnapperDB	20
BioNumerics	21
Denmark	21
Finland	22
The Netherlands.....	23
Norway	24

Introduction

The advent of affordable and qualitatively good whole genome sequencing has had a large impact on public health of infectious diseases. In general, it allows to establish detailed phylogenetic relationships that may elucidate transmission chains up to a level of detail that it can inform public health action. Relevant phenotypic properties such as virulence and reduced susceptibility to antimicrobials or vaccine-induced antibodies may also be predicted from the genome with sufficient accuracy, depending on the complexity of the mechanism and the amount and quality of training data available for modelling.

The practical issue of storing these data and results, as well as making them comparable with those of other organisations remains a complex one.[\[food-and-waterborne-diseases-next-generation-typing-methods.pdf \(europa.eu\)\]](#) There are organizational, legal and technical issues that need to be addressed. These include e.g.:

- Organizational structure in terms of who manages which part of the case data, i.e. typically the epidemiological and clinical data, the microbiological sample data and the whole genome sequence data.
- Maintaining compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
- General organisational technical preferences for physical storage and management of data, driven by wider IT considerations.
- Sharing sequence data with other organisations, both specifically for use for public health and for public use and research in particular.
- Organizational preferences for particular scientific methodologies for generating whole genome sequence data, determining phylogenetic relationships and predicting phenotypic properties.
- Making sequence data, and in particular the derived data including phylogenetic relationships, easily accessible to users that are directly involved in public health decision making.

In this report, we describe the preparatory steps for a system that should be able to address many of these concerns. We will call this system the Sequence Database as a working name. We start with a clear delineation of what is within scope and what not in the section on Scope and separation of concerns. Subsequently, the actual use cases that the Sequence Database should support are outlined in the Use cases section. The Logical Data Model and Physical Data Model sections then describe how the data that is involved in these use cases can be stored. Finally, the Testing section compares the logical data model of the Sequence Database against a number of

existing models, including those of the countries implementing a pilot within this project.

Scope and separation of concerns

Separation of Concerns is a fundamental principle for good design of software systems. [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Separation_of_concerns] In essence, systems must have a modular design, whereby each module has its own responsibilities that are not overlapping with those of other modules. Each module can then further implement those responsibilities without any other dependency on other modules than the interface that they expose.

Here, we consider the envisaged Sequence Database as one module of a broader system for public health data management and analysis. It will itself consist of sub-modules that are however beyond the scope of this document and instead are part of the subsequent software development process.

The Sequence Database will have the following general responsibilities:

- Storing and retrieving sequence data – excluding sequence reads – and PCR detection data for samples.
- Storing official taxonomy, loci and sequence classification nomenclature as reference data.
- Storing and retrieving results derived only from sequence data, including official taxonomical and other genotypic classifications, quality controls, alignment against a reference, locus detection, and predicted phenotypes.
- Deriving simple phylogenetic relatedness results in the form of pairwise distances between sequences and corresponding hierarchical clustering or minimum spanning tree results. The pairwise distances are also stored up to a relevant maximum distance, to fundamentally improve end-user performance.
- Access through an application programmer interface (API) accessible over HTTP(S).

Conversely, the Sequence Database will not have the following responsibilities, and for the following reasons:

- Storing epidemiological, clinical data or other (phenotypically measured) laboratory data for samples. These types of data are typically already stored in other systems and have very varying implementations. In addition, storing only the sequence data in the Sequence Database makes it impossible to identify individuals based on these data alone, which fundamentally reduces its risk level with respect to the GDPR and as such may reduce related security requirements. This in turn may make it easier for organizations to deploy the Sequence Database.

- Generating sequence data from reads and deriving results from sequence data. Running actual algorithms – typically called bioinformatics pipelines – to generate assembled sequence data, aligning genomes, finding loci, predicting phenotypic properties etc. is instead left to other systems that can subsequently store the relevant output in the Sequence Database if needed. These systems normally already exist in the organization and need not be replaced to be able to use the Sequence Database. They may also retrieve any reference data to run these pipelines from the Sequence Database as needed. The only algorithms that are part of the Sequence Database are those that calculate pairwise distances, hierarchical clustering and minimum spanning tree results (see included responsibilities).
- User management. The Sequence Database will authenticate users against an external identity provider and is not expected to implement specific user roles for authorization. This substantially reduces the complexity of the system, leaving other systems with machine-to-machine access to the Sequence Database the responsibility to determine who should have access to what functionality and data.
- Access to the Sequence Database through a web interface that makes use of the API. The interaction with the Sequence Database is expected to be machine-to-machine, whereby other public health systems retrieve or store the data they need. For example, in order to detect public health signals, another system may request the Sequence Database to find closely related samples, which subsequently provides a distance matrix or phylogenetic tree for these samples. The requesting system then uses these data together with the epidemiological and clinical data that it has itself access to to perform the signal detection. These results may then e.g. be made available through a web interface that combines all these data.

Use cases

Use cases are a technique for capturing, modeling, and specifying the requirements of a system.[\[https://www.worldcat.org/title/50041546\]](https://www.worldcat.org/title/50041546) A use case corresponds to a set of behaviors that the system may perform in interaction with its actors, and which produces an observable result that contributes to its goals. Actors represent the role that human users or other systems have in the interaction. For the Sequence Database, the user is expected to be another machine that accesses it through the HTTP(S) API. Two classes of use case are distinguished: operational use cases that center around actual sample data, and maintenance use cases that center around the reference data that is used to further describe the sample data.

The operational use cases are the following:

1. Store a sequence for a sample:
 - a. All contiguous sequences (contigs, one or more) that together form the entire sequence.
 - b. Protocol used to generate the sequence.
 - c. Optional read coverage information, either averaged over the entire sequence, over the individual contigs or for individual nucleotides within each contig.
 - d. Optional additional quality control results such as proportion covered of the reference used for assembly.
 - e. Optional minority bases and their coverage, typically for positions where there is a higher proportion of at least one minority base than would be expected as a result of sequencing errors. This may indicate the presence of minority variants, which may be relevant for some analyses.
2. Store a PCR detection result for a sample:
 - a. Overall positive or negative result and/or overall Cycle threshold (Ct) value.
 - b. Positive or negative result for each PCR target and/or Ct value for each target.
3. Store locus information for a sequence
4. Store an alignment against a reference for a sequence
5. Store other derived results for a sequence, e.g.:
 - a. Official taxonomical classification, typically up to species level
 - b. Subtyping scheme classification, typically below species level
 - c. Predicted phenotype category
 - d. Predicted phenotype numerical value
 - e. Classifications for the purpose of quality control
6. Find matches for a sample or sequence up to a maximum distance
7. Find all sequences classified as X, including taxonomical classification and membership of set of taxa
8. Retrieve a nucleotide sequence
9. Retrieve derived results for a sequence
10. Retrieve a multiple sequence alignment for a set of sequences
11. Retrieve a distance matrix or hierarchical clustering tree for a set of sequences
12. Delete a sample
13. Delete a sequence for a sample
14. Link a sequence to another sample

15. Store additional properties for a particular instance of an entity

The maintenance use cases are the following:

1. Store a new locus
2. Store a new set of loci
3. Store a new SNV
4. Store a new set of SNVs
5. Store a new taxon
6. Store or update a new set of taxa
7. Store a new protocol

Logical Data Model

The logical data model is described here as an entity-relationship model that can store the data that is required to be able to implement the use cases [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Entity%E2%80%93relationship_model]. Further information about the rationale for choosing these entities, including examples, is provided as well. Figures show parts of the entity-relationship model as a simplified set of tables with foreign keys between them and only the most relevant content fields. As is commonly done, names for tables and fields in the figures have been put in snake_case, while names of entities have been put in UpperCamelCase.

Species and Taxon

In biology, taxonomy is the scientific study of naming, defining (circumscribing) and classifying groups of biological organisms based on shared characteristics [[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Taxonomy_\(biology\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Taxonomy_(biology))]. Organisms are grouped into taxa (singular: taxon) and these groups are given a taxonomic rank; groups of a given rank can be aggregated to form a more inclusive group of higher rank, thus creating a taxonomic hierarchy. The principal ranks in modern use are domain, kingdom, phylum (division is sometimes used in botany in place of phylum), class, order, family, genus, and species.

Species is therefore the subset of all Taxa with rank species, and along with a standard name, frequently used synonyms should also be taken into account. In addition, sets of taxa may be defined that may not all have the same rank or most recent common ancestor, such as all species and/or genera that are relevant for antimicrobial resistance in human infections.

Figure 1 Logical data model for Taxon and TaxonSet entities.

Sample, Sequence and Contig

The DNA or RNA in a sample may be sequenced zero or more times, each time producing a sequence after assembly of the reads generated by the sequencer. A sample may be sequenced more than once for technical reasons, e.g. when the first sequence was of insufficient quality. There is therefore a one-to-many relationship between Sample and Sequence.

A sequence can consist of one or more contiguous sequences (contigs) for both biological and technical reasons. Biological reasons include:

- The species has more than one chromosome, or equivalent such as viruses with a genome that consists of several segments
- The species can carry within its cell other species or equivalent, such as plasmids or intracellular parasites
- The species has extrachromosomal DNA, such as mitochondrial DNA
- The source material did not consist of a pure clone of the species in question

Technical reasons include:

- Only part of the DNA in the source material had sufficiently high concentration for sequencing, such as through partial PCR amplification
- The sequence reads produced by the sequencer could not be assembled with high confidence into a single contig, such as in repetitive regions that are longer than the maximum read length

Conversely, a contig can contain multiple species, such as when a viral parasite integrates into the host species' genome. There is therefore a one-to-many relationship between Sequence and Contig, and a many-to-many relationship between Contig and Species/Taxon. The relationship between Contig and Taxon also needs to specify which part of the contig, if not in its entirety, corresponds to the species. Instead of Sequence, the entity could also be called SequenceExperiment for consistency with other types of Experiment entities (see sections on PCR detection results, and Results derived from an individual sequence). However, since the entity is

used ubiquitously throughout the database and its content also serves as input for other experiments, Sequence is used instead.

A Protocol may specify how a Sequence was generated, both in terms of the reads generated by the sequencer and the assembly into one or more contigs. It may also contain references to other documents. There is therefore a many-to-one relationship between Sequence and Protocol.

Figure 2 Logical data model for the Sample, Sequence and Contig entities.

Locus and Allele

A DNA or RNA sequence of a species can be annotated with loci that are of interest for further analysis. Generally, loci correspond to genes, but they can be any contiguous subset of the sequence. Loci may also overlap with one another, such as a PCR primer binding locus with the locus of the entire gene within which it lies, or overlapping loci between the forward and the reverse strand. Loci are also often conserved across multiple species or taxa. The exact subsequence of a contig that corresponds to a particular locus, as defined by its start, end and forward/reverse strand location (direction), is the allele.

There is therefore a many-to-many relationship between Taxon and Locus. There is also a one-to-many relationship between Locus and Allele, containing only the unique alleles for each locus. Finally, there is a many-to-many relationship between Contig and Allele, captured by a ContigAllele entity. A Protocol may specify how the sequence was annotated with loci, and consequently how alleles were defined.

Often, more than one locus is of interest for a specific type of analysis, requiring the definition of sets of loci (LocusSets). In addition, sets of loci may be agreed and

understood between different groups to help standardize results and their interpretation.

Figure 3 Logical data model for Locus, LocusSet, Allele and ContigAllele entities.

Alignment, Single Nucleotide Variant and Single Nucleotide Polymorphism

The DNA or RNA sequence of a species can be aligned against typically a reference genome for that species. For this purpose, the alignment should express which nucleotides are most likely phylogenetically equivalent, and which nucleotides arose through insertion or deletion events since divergence from the most recent common ancestor. More complex genetic such as chromosomal structural rearrangements may theoretically also be captured by the alignment. The alignment should however not express only functional or structural relationships, such as whether the corresponding amino acids have the same functional role or are structurally equivalent. This may not always be the case, even if the nucleotides in question do correspond phylogenetically to the same position.

Single Nucleotide Variants (SNVs) are the single nucleotide differences, after alignment, between a contiguous nucleotide sequence and a reference nucleotide sequence. Other differences between both sequences may include insertions, deletions and rearrangements. The reference may be an entire biological Contig or an Allele for a particular Locus. Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNPs) are generally

the subset of SNVs that are present in a sufficiently large fraction of the considered population, and whereby the reference used is representative for the most recent common ancestor of that population.

There is therefore a one-to-many relationship between Contig and ContigAlignment, which must specify which other Contig was used as reference, and which contains the set of start positions (contig and reference contig) and lengths of the individual ungapped alignment blocks that make up the entire alignment. In practice this will mostly be a one-to-one relationship if the contig is from a single species and since typically only one same reference genome is aligned against. There is a many-to-many relationship between ContigAlignment and SNV, which can also specify the coverage that each SNV occurred with, in case it is important to capture minority variants. Analogously, there is a one-to-many relationship between Allele and AlleleAlignment, which must specify which other Allele was used as a reference. Finally, sets of SNVs can be defined that are relevant in practice and therefore will likely be sets of SNPs.

Figure 4 Logical data model for ContigAlignment, AlleleAlignment, SNV and SNVSet entities.

PCR detection results

PCR detection results for a sample take the form of either a Ct value, or, derived from that, a positive, negative or unclear result. They are given either for the entire experiment, i.e. for all target loci if more than one, or for each individual target. A PCRExperiment entity can be defined that captures these results.

There is therefore a one-to-many relationship between Sample and PCRExperiment, and a one-to-many relationship between PCRExperiment and Locus that contains the result for each target, if specified. A Protocol may specify how the PCR detection result was generated, including which set of loci was used as targets.

Results derived from an individual sequence

Nucleotide sequences in general do not lend themselves to direct human interpretation. Instead, classification algorithms, which are a particular type of Protocol, are frequently used to classify individual sequences into relevant types, such as phylogenetic relatedness below the species level (often called subtypes, lineages or clades) and phenotypic characteristics such as antimicrobial resistance or virulence. The result is expressed as a particular category, such as the subtype in question, or resistant or susceptible. A special case of classification is the taxonomical classification, which is generally applicable to all species and handled separately (see Species and Taxon). Apart from that, classification algorithms tend to be species-specific and different algorithms for the same species may produce overlapping types.

Similarly, regression algorithms may produce numeric results derived from individual sequences, such as the degree of resistance to a particular antimicrobial. Regression algorithms are also a particular type of Protocol.

In theory, an Experiment entity could therefore be defined that contains the classification result (category) or regression result, if available, for each unique and relevant combination of Sequence and Protocol. This result can be a single result, such as for classifying the sequence as a whole or a set of results, such as the antimicrobial susceptibility classification for a set of antimicrobials. In practice, it is likely better to model this polymorphism through separate ClassificationExperiment and ASTExperiment (whereby AST stands for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing), analogous to the PCRExperiment.

The ClassificationExperiment can be further split up into a SequenceClassificationExperiment, whereby an entire sequence - typically a whole genome - is classified, and an AlleleClassificationExperiment, whereby a single allele sequence is classified. Example of a SequenceClassificationExperiment are determining which SARS-CoV-2 variant a sequence belongs to, or which E. coli pathotype a sequence belongs to. Examples of an AlleleClassificationExperiment for E.

coli are determining which Shiga toxin 2 (stx2) subtype an allele expresses, or whether the attaching and effacing (eae) gene is present.

There is therefore a one-to-many relationship between Sample and, respectively, ASTExperiment, SequenceClassificationExperiment and AlleleClassificationExperiment. Each has a many-to-one relationship with a Category, which in turn has a many-to-one relationship with the corresponding classification Protocol.

Figure 5 Logical data model for PCRExperiment, ASTExperiment, SequenceClassificationExperiment, AlleleClassificationExperiment and Category entities.

Sequence distance

The evolutionary relatedness between two sequences is ideally expressed as the actual mutations, such as substitutions, insertions, deletions and rearrangements each have undergone from the moment they diverged from their most recent common ancestor. This is generally not directly observed and, depending on the rate of

evolution and time since divergence, hard as well as computationally intensive to reconstruct from both sequences.

For the common practical public health purpose of detecting and responding to an event, such as a (possible) outbreak or ongoing transmission, short time spans of up to a few years – and often only days or weeks – are of direct practical use. For such short time spans, sequences are generally very closely related and the problem of assessing evolutionary relatedness can be addressed by calculating a single distance between each pair of sequences, which is generally easier and less computationally intensive. In addition, distances larger than a certain threshold are not of practical relevance, opening up the possibility of not calculating such a distance in the first place if it can be demonstrated in advance that it will be too great, and subsequently not storing it. Such distance is typically derived as the number of alleles – for a given set of loci – that are different between the two sequences, or the number of SNVs that are different between the two sequences.

The algorithm to derive a distance is a particular type of Protocol. A

SequenceDistance entity can therefore be defined that contains the distance between each pair of Sequences and for each relevant Protocol.

Figure 6 Logical data model for the SequenceDistance entity.

Physical Data Model

The physical data model is the actual implementation of the logical data model, satisfying all the same entities and relationships. Additional concerns need to be taken into account, such as storage volume and performance. For both these aspects, nucleotide sequence data lends itself to improvements as well as realistic constraints.

Immutability

The fact that the data model not only stores the original sequence information but also derived information, such as loci and classifications, imposes data integrity constraints beyond the regular atomicity, consistency, isolation and durability (ACID) requirements for any create, read, update or delete (CRUD) operation on instances of an individual entity. While these additional constraints are normally enforced by e.g.

foreign key constraints within a relational database and business rules implemented by the business tier of the system, this approach is difficult due to the nature of nucleotide sequence data.

Nucleotide sequence data are essentially long strings that are subsequently annotated, and the consequences on any change in these strings on derived information is difficult or even impossible to predict. As a result, any change in a sequence would have to lead to invalidating and likely recalculating all derived results, including e.g. pairwise distances with other sequences. This can in turn lead to inconsistencies in other systems that have meanwhile used the original results. To avoid this complexity and associated risks, a nucleotide sequence must be immutable. That is, once stored, a Sequence cannot undergo a change in the nucleotide sequence it represents, and therefore derived results can be guaranteed to remain reliable. This is similar to e.g. the immutable property of the str (string) class in Python, which allows not only for often efficient handling of strings and but also makes them hashable and guarantees any code that a string cannot be changed by another piece of code.

The disadvantage of this approach is that any nucleotide sequence that would need to be changed, e.g. because an incorrect sequence was stored, has to be stored as a new sequence instead. The data model however does allow this in general, since there is a one-to-many relationship between Sample and Sequence. The frequency of occurrence of having to change a nucleotide sequence is expected to be very low, so that the overall effect on storage of both the original and the updated sequence is expected to be negligible.

Data compression and pre-computation

In terms of storage, the full nucleotide sequence can be sizeable depending on the species. However, it is possible to reduce the storage in several ways. Firstly, there are general compression algorithms as well as specialized algorithms for compressing nucleotide sequences. These do not necessarily require any additional parameterization, but the compressed sequence also does not lend itself for subsequent computation and would need to be decompressed again before further use.

Secondly, a nucleotide sequence can be represented as a series of alleles (represented by their identifier), with corresponding locus, intermitted by the rest of the sequence that is not part of a locus. Depending on the proportion of the sequence that is covered by loci, and the diversity of the allele sequences, the storage can be reduced since only the unique allele sequences need to be stored.

Thirdly, and similarly to the second option, a nucleotide sequence can be represented as a set of SNVs, together with insertions and deletions versus a reference sequence. Depending on the diversity of the sequence, the storage can be reduced accordingly.

In addition, allele sequences can also be described this way versus a reference allele sequence, opening up the potential for further storage reduction by combining the second and the third option. This is also captured by the ContigAlignment and AlleleAlignment entities. Reference sequences themselves can also be described as a set of SNVs, insertions and deletions versus another reference.

Both the second and the third option also allow to store the nucleotide sequence in a way that allows subsequently calculating the pairwise distances between sequences with low computational complexity, since these distances normally count the number of differences between both, either in terms of alleles or in terms of SNVs. In addition, the representation of a sequence as a set of SNVs, insertions and deletions versus a reference is equivalent to a pairwise alignment of these two sequences. When stored for multiple sequences with the same reference in common, a multiple alignment can also be reconstructed from it with low computational complexity both in terms of time and memory, and retrieved as an output.

In summary, storing nucleotide sequences as a set of allele identifiers intermitted with the rest of the sequence, storing nucleotide sequences as a set of SNVs, insertions and deletions versus a reference, and a combination of both can significantly reduce both storage and computational requirements required to respond to user requests. The total computational requirements remain the same, but the most intensive part can be precomputed, which is essential to be able provide a responsive system for this type of application. The storage requirements are in theory minimal for the most parsimonious choice of references and alignments.

Custom identifiers and properties

The Sample entity is added to this model to be able to have a normally one-to-one relationship with Sample entities in other systems. To be able to unambiguously make this link, it must be possible to store identifiers from these other systems as properties of the Sample. In practice, this possibility may not be used, and instead the identifier of the Sample in this system is stored in the other system. Both should be possible, and the latter option may be chosen e.g. to reduce the possibility of identifying persons, in case the sample is derived from a human host.

In addition, depending on the organizational setup, it may be desirable to store some properties of the sample in the system, such as the sampling date. The same may be true for other entities such as Sequence, Protocol etc. This is however beyond the core intended use of the system to store nucleotide sequence data, and no further modelling is expected on this beyond a simple unconstrained property-value storage for each entity.

Standardisation

A crucial part of collaboration between groups and organizations is being able to interpret data in the same way, which requires using the same (i.e. standard) methodology. For the use cases implemented by the Sequence Database, this is an issue in particular for finding matches for a sample or sequence up to a maximum distance, and for retrieving a distance matrix for a set of sequences. The common aspect between these two is how a distance between two sequences is calculated, which in turn translates mainly to (i) how and with which loci sequences are annotated, and which reference alleles are used to detect loci, and to (ii) how genomes are aligned to a reference and SNVs enumerated.

To facilitate such standardisation, the Sequence Database needs at a minimum to be able to easily allow importing standard sets of loci, reference alleles and reference genomes. At the level of the physical data model, this translates e.g. to using primary keys for the corresponding entities that can safely be generated outside of the database, typically in the form of universally unique identifiers or UUIDs. The business logic of the Sequence Database also has to support standardized protocols for calculating a pairwise distance given either the allelic profile of both sequences, or the SNV profile.

The methodologies for deriving other results, such as for sequence classification and phenotype prediction, also need to be standardised. However, since the Sequence Database only stores the final results of these calculations, these are technically out of scope. Naturally, agreeing on which standards to use is also technically out of scope.

General performance considerations

Performance is a key issue for these types of database, since the amount of data can be very large and the operations can have high time and/or memory complexity. Several measures can be taken to improve performance, beyond simply using a more performant machine. Firstly, pre-computing derived results is very relevant in this case, and is described further in section Data compression and pre-computation. Secondly, parallelization can be implemented. In particular, the calculation of distances of a new set of sequences to all currently stored sequences can be parallelized, taking into account the need for eventual consistency as new sequences may likely also be added concurrently. Infrastructure that allows automatic horizontal scaling should be supported. Thirdly, the command query separation (CQS) design pattern may be implemented to physically separate actions that change the data from queries that only retrieve data. [\[Command–query separation - Wikipedia\]](#) Finally, the time complexity of the calculation of all pairwise distances up to a relevant maximum distance may be reduced to lower than the $O(n^2)$ for the naive algorithm.

Testing

To test the validity of the logical data model, we compare it to a number of existing physical data models, and the main corresponding entities and relationships equivalent to the logical data model for that database. These include databases that are used by several organisations as well as databases used by the partners for this Task that will implement a pilot, and which are Denmark, Finland, the Netherlands and Norway. For these countries, the physical data models for storage of respectively SARS-CoV-2 and E. coli data are used.

European Nucleotide Archive

The European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) is one of the largest databases for genetic sequencing information in the world. The General Guide on ENA Data Retrieval, ENA Training Modules 1 was used as a source for the logical datamodel (<https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/retrieval/general-guide.html>, Table 1).

Main differences:h

- Sequence Database: has locus, allele and genome reference data; has distance data; is open source
- ENA: has reads data; has projects/studies to group sequences

Table 1 European Nucleotide Archive logical data model entities.

Data Domain	Description	Example Records
Projects/Studies	Contains information on a biological research project. This holds all the data generated as part of this research	PRJEB1787 (ERP001736)
Samples	Represents biological samples collected and sequenced in real life	SAMEA2620084 (ERS488919)
Reads (Runs/Experiments)	Hold raw read files and sequencing methods	ERR1701760, ERX1772048
Analyses	Hold results files of analyses performed on sequencing data and analysis methods	ERZ1195979
Contig set	Hold contig sets generated as part of a genome or transcriptome assembly.	CABHOY010000000.1
Assemblies	Represents an entire genome assembly and holds any contig sets or sequence records generated as part of the assembly	GCA_000001405.28
Assembled/Annotated Sequences (*)	Any sequence records from coding or non-coding regions to full assembled chromosomes	CM000667.2
Taxon	The sequenced organism or metagenome of a sample	Taxon:9606
Sample Checklist	The checklist of metadata that the sample was registered with	ERC000013

Bacterial Isolate Genome Sequence Database

The Bacterial Isolate Genome Sequence Database (BIGSdb) is the open source technical platform behind, among others, the pubMLST website. [pubmlst.org] The

SQL databases that provide the persistent storage for a BIGSdb instance were initialized based on the online documentation. [[Bacterial Isolate Genome Sequence Database \(BIGSdb\) — BIGSdb 1.43.0 documentation](#)] The physical data model for different parts of the databases is shown in Figure 7, Figure 8, Figure 9 and Figure 10.

Main differences:

- Sequence Database: single database usable for many or all taxa, rather than one database per taxon; has additional experiment data; has contig alignment and SNV data; has precomputed distances
- BIGSdb: has detailed authorization (user roles); has curation of alleles; has algorithms for locus detection; has graphical user interface

Figure 7 BIGSdb sequence definition sub-database physical data model.

Figure 8 BIGSdb isolates sub-database physical data model.

Figure 9 BIGSdb authorization sub-database physical data model.

Figure 10 BIGSdb users sub-database physical data model.

SnapperDB

SnapperDB is an open source database solution that focuses on bacterial isolates and SNP-based distances. [\[GitHub - ukhsa-collaboration/snapperdb\]](https://github.com/ukhsa-collaboration/snapperdb) It does not appear to be maintained any longer, but was used for several years within Public Health England. The SQL database that provides the persistent storage for a SnapperDB

instance was initialized based on the online documentation, and the physical data model is shown in Figure 11.

Main differences:

- Sequence Database: single database usable for many or all taxa; rather than one database per taxon; has locus and allele reference data; has additional experiment data
- SnapperDB: has dynamic hierarchical cluster nomenclature

Figure 11 SnapperDB database physical data model.

BioNumerics

BioNumerics is a commercial software that has been in use for several decades, including for public health. <https://www.applied-maths.com/bionumerics> It provides a comprehensive suit of functionality for processing and visualising different types of laboratory test results, including genetic sequences. It also provides, among others, phylogenetic tree and hierarchical clustering methods and visualization for aggregated analysis. Persistent storage is handled by an SQL database.

Main differences:

- Sequence Database: single database usable for many or all taxa; has precomputed distances; is open source
- BioNumerics: has wide range of algorithms for both local and cloud computing; has graphical user interface

Denmark

The Danish sequence database for SARS-CoV-2, which contains around 1 million samples, was compared to the logical data model. This database has the following main entities:

- Batch
- Sample
- Sequenced sample
- Plate
- Read set
- Consensus sequence

- Pangolin results
- NextClade results
- Sample blacklist
- Line list to WGS key

Main differences:

- Sequence Database: has sequence data; has locus, allele and genome reference data; has distance data; single database usable for many or all taxa; is open source
- Danish sequence database: contains data about the source reads; connects to other databases with epidemiological and clinical data; has concept of linking to a line list

Finland

The Finnish sequence database for E. coli, which contains around 1000 samples, was compared to the logical data model. The physical data model is shown in Figure 12 and has the following main entities:

- Sample
- Run
- Reads
- Amr report
- Typing report
- Sample report
- User
- Software

Main differences:

- Sequence Database: single database usable for many or all taxa, rather than one database for bacteria; has genome reference data; has distance data
- Finnish sequence database: has epidemiological and clinical data; can perform analyses on reads and genomes

Figure 12. Finnish sequence database physical data model

The Netherlands

The Dutch sequence database for SARS-CoV-2, Nonacris, was developed as a temporary platform during the pandemic, as the platform that was being used was not able to handle the amount of data. It has a minimal interface for uploading data, with data extraction handled programmatically directly from the underlying SQL database. The E. coli database is a standard BioNumerics database, see section on BioNumerics for a comparison.

Main differences

- Sequence Database: single database usable for many or all taxa, rather than one database per taxon; has additional experiment data; has locus, allele reference data; has distance data
- Nonacris: has epidemiological and clinical data

Norway

In Norway, the logical data model structure for national laboratory-based surveillance is built around the medical microbiology laboratory infrastructure (Figure 13). Primary medical microbiology laboratories are required to send an electronic notification of all test results to the National Laboratory Surveillance Database (MSIS-Lab). At the time of submission, all test results include a personal identifier (Person ID), sample identifier (Sample ID) and a test code (from the national standardized codebook or local codes) corresponding to pathogenic specific tests. For pathogens with an assigned National Reference Laboratory (NRL), as is the case for Shiga-toxin producing *E. coli* (STEC), the primary medical microbiology laboratories are required to submit sample material to the assigned NRL for confirmation and in-dept characterization which includes whole genome sequence analysis. All samples submitted to NRL include a Person ID, a Sample ID, and results of tests performed for the identification of the pathogen.

Figure 13. Logical data model structure for laboratory-based surveillance of STEC in Norway. Medical microbiology laboratories submit samples with unique identifiers to the national reference laboratory (NRL) for confirmation and characterization of isolated pathogens. The NRL request tests on the received samples through their laboratory information management system (LIMS), and results are reported back to LIMS using a unique identifier (Reflab ID). Next generation sequencing is performed using the Illumina platform and raw sequences are stored on servers located at Norwegian Health Network (NHN). Results from various bioinformatical pipelines run in an in-house Linux script and the SeqSphere software are reported to NRL LIMS. The medical microbiology and the NRL submit results to the MSIS laboratory database (MSIS-lab). MSIS-lab database is a SQL-database that partitions and stores results and metadata using unique identifiers.

The STEC NRL is located at the National Institute of Public Health (NIPH). On reception, all samples are registered in the NRL Laboratory Information Management

System (LIMS) with a unique Reference Laboratory Identifier (Reflab ID). Different tests are requested from within the LIMS for the confirmation and characterization of submitted pathogen. For STEC, this includes culture, PCRs for *stx*-subtyping, Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) and occasionally multiple locus variable number of tandem repeats analysis (MLVA) during an outbreak investigation. NGS of STEC is performed using the Illumina platform and raw sequences are stored in an in-house server which is hosted by the National Health Network (NHN). Bioinformatical pipelines, which include the identification of serotype, *stx*-subtype, virulence genes, antimicrobial resistance (AMR) markers, mobile genetic elements, sequence type (MLST) and cluster type (core genome MLST), are run between two separate workflows, an in-house Linux script and within the commercial Ridom SeqSphere software. [<https://www.ridom.de/seqsphere>] Outputs from the different bioinformatical pipelines run in SeqSphere are stored in a SQL-database on a server located at NHN. Results from the sequencing analysis are reported and stored into the NRL LIMS. The NRL LIMS generates a unique Sample ID and reports NGS generated results to the MSIS-lab database.

The MSIS-lab database is a SQL-database which organizes data submitted by national medical microbiology laboratories and the NRL using an existing standard for reporting laboratory results (.xml). Data elements are then extracted from this file and can be linked to one another using identifiers such as Person ID, Sample ID and other relevant information found in the notifications. Such data elements can for example be the requester information, sampling date, etc. While the sequencing data is not stored in the MSIS-lab database, it is possible to use the Sample ID and Person ID keys to trace back the corresponding Reflab ID to retrieve sequences from the NHN sequence server. The STEC pilot aims to explore this logical data model to standardize reporting from the medical microbiology laboratories and NRL to MSIS-lab and retrieve stored data from the NRL using unique identifiers and visualize for real-time integrated laboratory-based surveillance of STEC.

Main differences

- Sequence Database: single database usable for many or all taxa, rather than one database per taxon; has genome reference data; has sequence data; has distance data
- MSIS-Lab database: has epidemiological and clinical data

Annex 2. Template of the Survey “Needs and Gaps Analysis Laboratory-Based Reporting” Conducted Under Task 1

Needs and gaps analysis laboratory-based reporting

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

Introduction

This survey is part of the Joint Action “United4Surveillance” and is conducted under work package 2 “Outbreak detection”/ Task 1 “Improving laboratory-based reporting”.

Please note: If your organization is a beneficiary of the Joint Action, your organization has funds earmarked to respond to surveys, among others, and is therefore kindly expected to respond.

The survey is aligned with the bi-annual survey from the European Union Laboratory Capability (EULabCap) monitoring program conducted by ECDC and the survey on mapping digitalization and integration of surveillance systems across Europe commissioned by the European Commission.

The **objective** of the survey is to get an overview of countries’ laboratory-based reporting systems with respect to legal, policy and organizational, technical (data and IT) and financial issues to assess current needs and gaps. Results from this survey will help identify possible areas for action and also feed into planning subsequent Joint Actions.

The **scope** of the survey is limited to the laboratory-based reporting processes shown in the white boxes below and includes both notifiable and non-notifiable diseases. Boxes in grey are outside the scope of the survey.

Instructions

This survey is sent to selected contact points of countries that are part of the consortium of the Joint Action "United4Surveillance":

- Contact points are responsible for coordinating and compiling responses of national experts and filling in the survey online **by 2 April 2023**.
- If there is more than one contact point per country, only one survey should be filled in.
- **We strongly recommend that the contact point liaises with relevant national experts and fills in the survey together with them online whenever possible.**
- **You can use the Save-as-Draft feature in the top right of the page as needed to continue with the rest of the survey at a later moment. Be sure to save the link you receive, you can also email it to yourself!**
- If that is not feasible, this Word version of the survey can be used to facilitate coordinating and compiling responses of national experts, in case needed. The designated country contact point is requested to subsequently add the combined input in EU survey.
- This survey will be forwarded to ECDC National Surveillance Focal Points (NSFPs) and National Microbiology Focal Points (NMFPs) of the countries participating in the Joint Action for awareness and facilitation, if necessary.
- Please use Microsoft Edge, Mozilla Firefox or Google Chrome to complete the questionnaire. Using other browsers might cause compatibility issues.
- When you have entered all your answers, please press "submit" at the bottom of the page.
- For FAQs: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/home/helpparticipants>
- For questions, please contact Gudrun Witteveen-Freidl (gwit@ssi.dk) and Ivo van Walle (ivo.van.walle@rivm.nl)

Data privacy and (anonymized) handling of data

This survey is sent to the selected contact points of countries that are part of the consortium of the Joint Action "United4Surveillance". Their name and email-address are already known to the organisers, and it is important to be able to take up contact, if needed. Survey results will be anonymised. No individual persons will be mentioned, only the country.

Terminology and abbreviations

Please note that terms marked in *italics* throughout the survey refer to the definitions in this section:

1. *National Institute for Public Health (NIPH)*: national authority or agency responsible for public health surveillance of infectious diseases
2. *Local laboratories*: clinical laboratories that perform diagnostics of infectious diseases.
3. *Lab surveillance (data)*: samples and/or data on samples taken from human subjects stored by *local laboratories* on samples that can be used for the purpose of public health surveillance of communicable diseases. This contains data on laboratory tests as well as selected clinical or epidemiological data as available.
4. *National reference laboratory (NRL) not at NIPH*: national reference laboratory that is not part of the NIPH and performs additional diagnostics of infectious diseases that are not normally performed by *local laboratories*. NRLs that are part of the *NIPH* are not considered as a separate category, but instead considered as the *NIPH* itself.
5. *Lab-surveillance data sharing*: in this context, “Lab-surveillance data sharing” refers to the sharing of *lab surveillance data* by *local laboratories* with the *NIPH*, either directly or indirectly via e.g. a local or regional public health authority or national reference laboratory (in case the latter is not at the NIPH).
6. *GDPR* – [General Data Protection Regulation](#)

General aspects

*1. Please provide your email address **Free text**

*2. Which country are you reporting for? **Choose one**

Austria
Belgium
Croatia
Cyprus
Czechia
Denmark
Estonia
Finland
France
Germany
Hungary
Ireland
Italy
Latvia
Lithuania
Luxembourg
Malta
Netherlands

Norway
 Poland
 Portugal
 Romania
 Slovenia
 Spain
 Sweden

*3. Which organization do you work for? **Choose one**

- NIPH
- NRL not at NIPH
- Local laboratory
- Local or regional public health authority
- Other

3.1. If Other, please describe which: **Free text**

*4. Which diseases are notifiable in your country on the national level? The list of diseases below was taken from the list of [EU case definitions](#). **Choose one per row by putting e.g. an X**

	Yes	No	Unknown
* Anthrax			
* Avian influenza in humans			
* Botulism			
* Brucellosis			
* Campylobacteriosis			
* Chikungunya virus disease			
* Chlamydia infections			
* Cholera			
* COVID-19			
* Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease, variant (vCJD)			
* Cryptosporidiosis			
* Dengue			
* Diphtheria			
* Echinococcosis			
* Giardiasis			
* Gonorrhoea			

	Yes	No	Unknown
* Hepatitis A			
* Hepatitis B			
* Hepatitis C			
* HIV infection and AIDS			
* Infections with haemophilus influenzae group B			
* Influenza			
* Invasive meningococcal disease			
* Invasive pneumococcal disease			
* Legionnaires' disease			
* Leptospirosis			
* Listeriosis			
* Lyme neuroborreliosis			
* Malaria			
* Measles			
* Mumps			
* Pertussis			
* Plague			
* Poliomyelitis			
* Q fever			
* Rabies			
* Rubella			
* Rubella, congenital			
* Salmonellosis			
* Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS)			
* Shiga toxin /verocytotoxin -producing Escherichia coli (STEC/VTEC)			
* Shigellosis			
* Smallpox			
* Syphilis			
* Syphilis, congenital			
* Tetanus			

	Yes	No	Unknown
* Tick-borne encephalitis			
* Toxoplasmosis, congenital			
* Trichinellosis			
* Tuberculosis			
* Tularaemia			
* Typhoid and paratyphoid fevers			
* Viral haemorrhagic fevers			
* West Nile virus infection			
* Yellow fever			
* Yersinosis			
* Zika virus disease			
* Zika virus disease, congenital			

*4.1 Please indicate which other diseases are notifiable in your country, and/or provide a link to an overview of notifiable diseases: **Free text**

*5. For which pathogens do you perform subtyping (sequencing, serotyping, etc.) and/or phenotyping (AMR, etc.) for surveillance at the national level? **Choose one per row by putting e.g. an X**

The list of pathogens below was taken from [ECDC strategic framework for the integration of molecular and genomic typing into European surveillance and multi-country outbreak investigation](#) and was supplemented with SARS-CoV-2.

	Yes	No	Unknown
* Carbapenem- and/or colistin-resistant Enterobacteriaceae (C/CRE)			
* Carbapenem-resistant Acinetobacter baumannii (CRAB)			
* Clostridium difficile			
* Meticillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA)			
* Outbreaks of emerging multidrug resistant pathogens/clones/plasmids			
* Outbreaks of newly emerging pathogens/new modes of transmission of known healthcare-associated pathogens			
* West Nile virus			
* Campylobacter jejuni/C. coli			

	Yes	No	Unknown
* Hepatitis A virus			
* Legionella spp.			
* Listeria monocytogenes			
* Salmonella enterica			
* Shiga toxin-producing E. coli (STEC)			
* Antibiotic-resistant Neisseria gonorrhoea			
* HIV transmitted drug resistance			
* Influenza virus			
* SARS-CoV-2			
* Multidrug-resistant tuberculosis			
* Bordetella pertussis			
* Neisseria meningitidis			
* Streptococcus pneumoniae			

*5.1 Please indicate if there are any other pathogens for which you perform subtyping or phenotyping for surveillance in your country at the national level: **Free text**

Legal aspects

*6. For notifiable communicable diseases, to what extent do you experience legal constraints or challenges (e.g. data cannot be shared or is very difficult to share) with *lab surveillance data sharing* that is considered critical for the purpose of laboratory-based public health surveillance? **Choose one**

Critical importance would mean that the surveillance objectives of for the disease in question cannot (all) be met.

- To a very large extent
- To a large extent
- To some extent
- To little extent
- To no extent
- Unknown

6.1 Please provide any additional comments about legal constraints or challenges: **Free text**

*7. Under what legal basis ([GDPR Art 6.1](#)) does your *NIPH* process *lab surveillance data*, including directly identifiable or pseudonymized personal data? **Choose at least one**

- The GDPR does not apply, we only process anonymous data. As such, directly identifiable information (e.g. name or national identifier) or other identifiers (e.g. sample identifier) are not provided to us.
- Informed consent (Art 6.1.a)
- Compliance with a legal obligation (Art 6.1.c)
- Protection of the vital interests of the data subject or another natural person (Art 6.1.d)
- Performance of a task carried out in the public interest (Art 6.1.e)
- Other
- Unknown

7.1 Please provide any additional comments, in particular if you chose multiple options: **Free text**

*8. Indicate for each pathogen the different data elements that *local laboratories* report to the *NIPH* (directly or indirectly) along with their test results for a particular sample. Choose at least one per row by putting e.g. an X

In case a data element is reported only in some cases, it should still be selected. Choose “No lab surveillance” in case only diagnostic test results are reported by *local laboratories* and no dedicated sending of samples and/or reporting of test results for the purpose of surveillance is done. Please note that the last columns may only be visible by using the horizontal scrollbar, if present.

	No lab surveillance	National identifier(1)	Name	Residence postal code	Date of birth	Sample identifier	Date of sampling	Date of onset of disease	Symptoms	Vaccination status(2)	Ethnicity(3)	Travel history
* Carbapenem- and /or colistin-resistant Enterobacteriaceae (C/CRE)												
* Carbapenem- resistant Acinetobacter baumannii (CRAB)												
* Clostridium difficile												
* Meticillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA)												
* Outbreaks of emerging multidrugresistant pathogens /clones/plasmids												
* Outbreaks of newly emerging pathogens/new modes of transmission of known healthcare-associated pathogens												
* West Nile virus												

	No lab surveillance	National identifier(1)	Name	Residence postal code	Date of birth	Sample identifier	Date of sampling	Date of onset of disease	Symptoms	Vaccination status(2)	Ethnicity(3)	Travel history
* Campylobacter jejuni/C. coli												
* Hepatitis A virus												
* Legionella spp.												
* Listeria monocytogenes												
* Salmonella enterica												
* Shiga toxin- producing E. coli(STEC)												
* Antibiotic-resistant Neisseria gonorrhoea												
* HIV transmitted drug resistance												
* Influenza virus												
* SARS-CoV-2												
* Multidrug-resistant tuberculosis												
* Bordetella pertussis												
* Neisseria meningitidis												
* Streptococcus pneumoniae												

Footnote:

(1) Or equivalent such as social security number or encrypted national identifier

(2) If applicable

(3) Can e.g. be migrant status, country of origin or birth, membership of a minority population

8.1 Please indicate if there are any other data elements that *local laboratories* report for surveillance in your country at the national level: **Free text**

*9. Is the *NIPH* legally allowed and able to link *lab surveillance data* with surveillance data from other sources, e.g. notifications by physicians? **Choose one**

- Yes
- No, not allowed
- No, allowed but not able
- Not applicable
- Unknown

9.1 Please provide any additional comments: **Free text**

*10. With respect to the assessment of the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects that is part of a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA, [GDPR Art 35.7.c](#)): has the *NIPH* assessed the risk of identification of a person based on the *lab surveillance data* provided to the *NIPH*? **Choose one**

- Yes, in general
- Yes, per disease
- No
- Unknown

10.1. If Yes, please describe how this risk was assessed: **Free text**

*11. Do you have legal expertise available at the *NIPH* to assist you with setting up or maintaining *lab surveillance*? **Choose one**

- Yes, sufficient
- Yes, limited
- No
- Unknown

11.1. If Limited or No, please describe in more detail: **Free text**

12. Please provide some examples of how national or international legislation either hampers or facilitates *lab surveillance* at the national level, and how you have potentially overcome any hampering issues: **Free text**

*13. Does your country have any provisions in national law that further specify how personal data can be processed in the interest of public health, as described in e.g. [GDPR Art 6.2](#) or [Art 9.2.i](#)? **Choose one**

- Yes
- No
- Unknown

13.1 If yes, please elaborate on the rationale: **Free text**

14. In your opinion, what aspects of the *GDPR*, if any, would need to be changed or adapted to facilitate performing *lab surveillance*? **Free text**

Policy and organizational aspects

*15. What organizational units at the *NIPH* deal directly with *lab surveillance*?

In case a team is only involved in *lab surveillance* of particular pathogens, it should still be selected. **Choose at least one**

- Laboratory/Microbiology team
- Epidemiology team
- Bioinformatics team
- Data science team
- IT team
- Interdisciplinary team
- Other

15.1. If "Other", please provide more information: **Free text**

*16. Do you regularly provide dedicated training on *lab surveillance* for the teams mentioned in question 15? **Choose one**

E.g. scientific aspects, data management, communication, infrastructure etc.

- Yes
- No
- Unknown

16.1. If yes, how and for which aspects (e.g. scientific aspects, data management, communication, infrastructure) do you organize and train teams? **Free text**

*17. Do you have training needs for *lab surveillance* (e.g. scientific aspects, data management, communication, infrastructure) at the *NIPH* that are difficult to meet? **Choose one**

- To a very large extent
- To a large extent
- To some extent
- To little extent
- To no extent
- Unknown

17.1. Please describe training needs in more detail: **Free text**

18. Do you take any specific measures to attract and retain talent in the area of *lab surveillance*, including people with an IT or data science background? **Free text**

Technical aspects (data & IT)

*19. Which (international) data standards, such as terminologies and ontologies, are used for *lab surveillance* in your country? **Choose at least one**

Check all that apply.

- Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes ([LOINC](#))
- Systematised Nomenclature of Medicine – Clinical Terms ([SNOMED-CT](#))
- International Classification of Diseases ([ICD](#))
- Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical ([ATC](#)) classification for medicinal products
- Unified Code for Units of Measure ([UCUM](#))
- Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium – Study Data Tabulation Model ([CDISC SDTM](#))
- Health Level 7 ([HL7](#)) - Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR)
- Health Level 7 ([HL7](#)) - Previous versions
- Other, including national standards
- Unknown

19.1. If "Other, including national standards", please describe which. Additional comments can be added as well: **Free text**

*20. Does the *NIPH* technically assist *local laboratories* with providing the *lab surveillance data*? **Choose one**

- Yes, in general
- Yes, for some diseases
- Yes, but very limited
- No
- Unknown

20.1. If yes, how does the *NIPH* technically assist *local laboratories* with providing the *lab surveillance data*?
Free text

21. Where do *local laboratories* report *lab surveillance data* to in first instance, if not directly to the *NIPH*?
Choose one per row by putting e.g. an X

Choose “No *lab surveillance*” in case only diagnostic test results are reported by *local laboratories* and no dedicated sending of samples and/or reporting of test results for the purpose of surveillance is done.

	No lab surveillance	Directly to <i>NIPH</i>	<i>NRL</i> not at <i>NIPH</i>	Local or regional public health authority	Unknown
* Carbapenem- and/or colistin-resistant Enterobacteriaceae (C/CRE)					
* Carbapenem-resistant <i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> (CRAB)					
* <i>Clostridium difficile</i>					
* Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (MRSA)					
* Outbreaks of emerging multidrug resistant pathogens/clones/plasmids					
* Outbreaks of newly emerging pathogens /new modes of transmission of knownhealthcare-associated pathogens					
* West Nile virus					
* <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> / <i>C. coli</i>					
* Hepatitis A virus					
* <i>Legionella</i> spp.					
* <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>					
* <i>Salmonella enterica</i>					

	No lab surveillance	Directly to <i>NIPH</i>	<i>NRL</i> not at <i>NIPH</i>	Local or regional public health authority	Unknown
* Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)					
* Antibiotic-resistant <i>Neisseria gonorrhoea</i>					
* HIV transmitted drug resistance					
* Influenza virus					
* SARS-CoV-2					
* Multidrug-resistant tuberculosis					
* <i>Bordetella pertussis</i>					
* <i>Neisseria meningitidis</i>					
* <i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>					

21.1 Please provide any additional comments about how *lab surveillance data* are reported to the national level, in particular if they are reported indirectly: **Free text**

22. In what format do local laboratories report the lab surveillance data to the organisation of question 21? **Choose at least one**

Check all options that apply. Choose “No *lab surveillance*” in case only diagnostic test results are reported by *local lab* samples and/or reporting of test results for the purpose of surveillance is done.

	No lab surveillance	Paper form	Free text via mail	Data file sent via email(1)	Web form entry or upload
* Carbapenem- and/or colistin-resistant Enterobacteriaceae (C/CRE)					
* Carbapenem-resistant Acinetobacter baumannii (CRAB)					
* Clostridium difficile					
* Meticillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA)					
* Outbreaks of emerging multidrug resistant pathogens /clones/plasmids					
* Outbreaks of newly emerging pathogens/new modes of transmission of known healthcare-associated pathogens					
* West Nile virus					
* Campylobacter jejuni/C. coli					
* Hepatitis A virus					
* Legionella spp.					
* Listeria monocytogenes					
* Salmonella enterica					
* Shiga toxin-producing E. coli (STEC)					

	No lab surveillance	Paper form	Free text via mail	Data file sent via email(1)	Web form entry or upload	Machine to machine upload	Other	Unknown
* Antibiotic-resistant Neisseria gonorrhoea								
* HIV transmitted drug resistance								
* Influenza virus								
* SARS-CoV-2								
* Multidrug-resistant tuberculosis								
* Bordetella pertussis								
* Neisseria meningitidis								
* Streptococcus pneumoniae								

Footnote:

(1) Data file: e.g. Excel or CSV file with structured (tabular) data

22.1 If Other, please describe which. Additional comments can be added as well: **Free text**

23. How timely does the NIPH receive lab surveillance data for the majority (>90%) of the samples after the laboratory has it stored in their systems, for the following pathogens? Choose one per row by putting e.g. an X

Choose “No lab surveillance” in case only diagnostic test results are reported by local laboratories and no dedicated sending of samples and/or reporting of test results for the purpose of surveillance is done.

	No lab surveillance	Real-time	Max delay of 1 day	Max delay of 1 week	Max delay of 2 weeks	Max delay of 1 month	Other	Unknown
* Carbapenem- and/or colistin-resistant Enterobacteriaceae (C/CRE)								
* Carbapenem-resistant Acinetobacter baumannii (CRAB)								
* Clostridium difficile								
* Methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA)								
* West Nile virus								
* Campylobacter jejuni/C. coli								
* Hepatitis A virus								
* Legionella spp.								
* Listeria monocytogenes								
* Salmonella enterica								
* Shiga toxin-producing E. coli (STEC)								
* Antibiotic-resistant Neisseria gonorrhoea								
* HIV transmitted drug resistance								
* Influenza virus								
* SARS-CoV-2								

* Multidrug-resistant tuberculosis								
* Bordetella pertussis								
* Neisseria meningitidis								
* Streptococcus pneumoniae								

23.1 Please provide any additional comments, including if there are substantial differences in timeliness between diseases: **Free text**

*24. Does the *NIPH* store (parts of) the *lab surveillance* data in the cloud? Choose one

- Yes, on EU/EEA territory
- Yes, on non-EU/EEA territory
- No, all storage is on-premises
- Unknown

24.1 If Yes, please describe how or why data is (not) stored in the cloud and if possible which provider you use: Free text

*25. Does the *NIPH* routinely report any data back to the *local laboratories*? Choose one

- Yes, for all pathogens
- Yes, for some pathogens
- No
- Unknown

25.1 If yes, what results does the *NIPH* report back to the *local laboratories*? Free text

26. If you have any documentation about your *lab surveillance* system available online, please share the link(s) here: Free text

Financial aspects

*27. Does the *NIPH* have stable funding source(s) to maintain *lab surveillance* systems?

This does not include funding of local laboratories, which is addressed in the next questions. Choose one

- To a very large extent
- To a large extent
- To some extent
- To little extent
- To no extent
- Unknown

27.1. Please provide details: Free text

* 28. Are the *local laboratories* compensated in any way for the infrastructure needed to contribute to *lab surveillance*, such as laboratory equipment or laboratory information system extensions for extracting or sending through data?

This excludes infrastructure they require in any case for patient care. **Choose one**

- To a very large extent
- To a large extent
- To some extent
- To little extent
- To no extent
- Unknown

* 29. Are the *local laboratories* compensated in any way per sample for performing additional tests that are purely in the interest of public health surveillance (e.g. screening, studies, targeted surveys, characterization etc.)?

This excludes testing for patient care that is covered by health insurance schemes. **Choose one**

- To a very large extent
- To a large extent
- To some extent
- To little extent
- To no extent
- Unknown

* 30. Are the *local laboratories* compensated in any way per sample for sending through samples and/or data to the *NRL* and/or *NIPH*?

This excludes testing for patient care that is covered by health insurance schemes. **Choose one**

- To a very large extent
- To a large extent
- To some extent
- To little extent
- To no extent
- Unknown

30.1. Please provide additional details on how local laboratories are compensated: **Free text**

Thank you for your participation!

Annex 3. Original answers to free text questions of the survey “Needs and Gaps Laboratory-Based Reporting” (Annex 2)

Section numbering aligns with the numbering of the (sub)questions as shown in the questionnaire template (Annex 2). Information provided below refer to answers provided in response to the sections marked in italics.

Section 3.1. Which organization do you work for? *If Other, please describe which:*

Number	Country	Answer
1	Lithuania	National Public Health Center under the MoH. The survey was completed together with National reference laboratory, most of the answers were provided by NRL specialists
2	Malta	The Infectious Disease Prevention and Control Unit (IDCU) within the Health Promotion and Disease Prevention Directorate is the only unit in Malta responsible for the public health management of cases and outbreaks of infectious diseases as well as for surveillance and reporting. IDCU falls under the remit of the Superintendence of Public Health - Department of Health Regulation which is part of the Ministry for Health. Objectives of the unit: https://deputyprimeminister.gov.mt/en/health-promotion/idpcu/Pages/objectives.aspx
3	Romania	Carol Davila University of Medicine and Pharmacy
4	Spain	Ministry of Healh

Section 4.1. Which diseases are notifiable in your country on the national level (out of diseases listed on the list of EU case definitions)? *Please indicate which **other** diseases are notifiable in your country, and/or provide a link to an overview of notifiable diseases:*

Number	Country	Answer
1	Belgium	Prevention of infectious diseases and the consequent list of mandatory notifiable diseases is defined at regional level. The regional list of mandatory notifiable diseases: Flanders (https://www.zorg-en-gezondheid.be/overzicht-infectieziekten-en-bijhorende-richtlijnen), Brussels Capital Region (https://www.ejustice.just.fgov.be/eli/arrete/2022/06/30/2022015236/moniteur) Wallonia (https://matra.sciensano.be/liste_matra.aspx). Therefore there can be differences between regions in Belgium in the lists e.g. Listeriosis is mandatory notifiable in Wallonia and Brussels but not in Flanders, for shigellosis it is the opposite. Case definitions may also differ e.g. for vector borne diseases such as zika must be reported In Flanders when there is a suspicion of autochthonous (local) transmission. The table above have been filled in according to the Flanders region, which is the biggest region in Belgium.
2	Croatia	Paralysis acuta flaccid, Amoebiasis, Sepsis purulenta, Meningitis purulenta, Morbus Brill-Zinsser, Enterocolitis, Enterovirosis, Erysipelas, Erlichyosis, Fasciolysis, New strain influenza, Helminthiasis, Febris haemorrhagica cum syndroma renale, Herpes zoster, Mononucleosis

		<p>infectiosa, Leishmaniasis visceralis, Leishmaniasis cutanea, Lymphogranuloma venerum (Chlamydia), Febris mediterranea exanthematica, Typhus murinus, Ornithosis-Psittacosis, Febris pappataci, Typhus exanthematicus, Febris recurrens, Rickettiosis - other, Angina streptococcica, Scabies, Scarlatina, Toxiinfectio alimentaris, Pneumonia, Pediculosis capitis/corporis, Gastroenterocolitis virosa, Hepatitis virosa D, E, G et nonspecificata, Meningitis virosa, Varicella, Encephalitis</p> <p>* Chikungunya virus disease, Zika virus disease (and congenital) are also notifiable even though they are not on the list of those that must be registered</p>
3	Czechia	By Czech law, generally for all infectious diseases mandatory reporting is in place with the exception of ARI, ILI, conjunctivitis, mastitis and skin inflammatory/mycotic infections that are reported only in case of outbreak.
4	Denmark	<p>Our country is in between two executive orders on notifiable diseases. Data provided under Q4 and Q4.1. pertain to the new executive order on notifiable diseases that is expected to come into force on 7 July 2023.</p> <p>Clinical notifications incl. lab notifications: mpox, infection with HUS inducing Shiga-toxin producing E.coli (STEC), Smallpox, MERS, Nipah, Carbapenemase-producing enterobacteriae (CPE) (infection and colonization), MRSA, Ornithosis, Lepra, Suspected outbreak of diseases, regardless of whether the disease is notifiable, that 1) are serious and unexplained and suspected to be caused by a biological agent, but where the agent has not necessarily been proven or 2) are of known cause, but presenting in an unusual manner that causes concern</p> <p>Only lab notifications: Antimicrobial resistance of potential clinical importance, Bacteria in cerebrospinal fluid, Bacteraemia, Beta-haemolytic streptococci which have caused invasive infection, Burkholderia mallei, and Burkholderia pseudomallei (melioidose), Calicivirus, Candida auris (infection and colonization), Carbapenemase-producing Acinetobacter baumannii (infection and colonization), Carbapenemase-producing enterobacteriae (infection and colonization), Carbapenemase-producing Pseudomonas spp (infection and colonization), Clostridioides difficile, Cytomegalovirus, Entamoeba histolytica, Epstein-Barr Virus (mononucleosis), Hanta, Marine bacteria, Hepatitis E, Leishmania spp., Microorganisms that cause urinary tract infections and deep infections after planned total hip arthroplasty or knee arthroplasty, Mycoplasma genitalium, Mycoplasma pneumoniae, Parasites in cerebrospinal fluid/cerebral tissue, Yersiniosis, RSV infections, Typhus, Taenia solium, Toxoplasmosis (congenital), Trypanosomiasis (sleeping sickness; African and Chagas Disease), Typhus (Rickettsiosis)</p>
5	Estonia	rotavirus infection, leprosy, Scarlet fever, chickenpox, hepatitis E, amoebias, psittacos , other viral and bacterial gastrointestinal infections
6	Finland	The notifiable diseases are categorized in three categories, 1) generally hazardous communicable diseases, 2) communicable diseases to be monitored, and 3) other notifiable diseases. All microbes detected in blood samples are also notifiable. A list of notifiable diseases is available. https://thl.fi/fi/web/infektiaudit-ja-rokotukset/seurantajarjestelmat-ja-rekisterit/tartuntatautirekisteri/ilmoitettavat-taudit-ja-mikrobit
7	France	autochthonous Schistosomiasis, Foodborne infections from gathering ; Diseases selected are the ones for which case notification is mandatory (list available here: https://www.santepubliquefrance.fr/maladies-a-declaration-obligatoire/liste-des-maladies-a-declaration-obligatoire). All other diseases (except Trichinellosis) have a laboratory-based surveillance from their dedicated National Reference Centre.
8	Germany	Clostridioides-difficile, Subacute sclerosing panencephalitis (SSPE) are both notifiable as notifications by physician, https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/ifsg/_7.html

9	Ireland	https://www.hpsc.ie/notifiablediseases/listofnotifiablediseases/List%20of%20Notifiable%20Diseases.pdf
10	Italy	<p>The following diseases are also notifiable: all serotypes of haemophilus influenzae (not only B), Borreliosis, infection by invasive Enterobacterales resistant to carbapenems; Rickettsiosis. There is also a national plan on arboviruses which include the following viruses: Toscana virus; Usutu virus, Hantaviruses, Japanese Encephalitis Virus, Rift Valley Fever Virus.</p> <p>Even if not subject to mandatory notification there is a surveillance on invasive infections by beta-haemolytic streptococci (group A,B,C,G).</p> <p>In this link is possible to find an overview of the notifiable diseases: "Review of the infectious disease reporting system (PREMAL)" available at https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2022/04/07/22A02179/sg</p>
11	Latvia	<p>There is more notifiable diseases in our country than are mentioned in the list above. All notifiable diseases are mentioned in the Annex 2 in Republic of Latvia Cabinet Regulation No. 7 (Adopted 5 January 1999) "Procedures for Registration of Infectious Diseases". Please follow the link - https://likumi.lv/ta/id/20667-infekcijas-slimibu-registracijas-kartiba and https://likumi.lv/ta/en/en/id/20667-procedures-for-registration-of-infectious-diseases</p> <p>*Seasonal Influenza – disease is not notifiable for each individual case, but within the monitoring system aggregated data submitted from sentinel sites once a week. Also, clusters with 5 or more cases outside of a flu epidemic should be notified. Any case of avian flu or pandemic flu should be notified immediately.</p>
12	Lithuania	Monkeypox
13	Luxembourg	https://www.stradalex.lu/fr/slu_src_publ_leg_mema/toc/leg_lu_mema_201903_104/doc/mema_etat-leg-rgd-2019-02-15-a104-jo
14	Malta	<p>The list of notifiable diseases can be found on the following link: https://deputyprimeminister.gov.mt/en/health-promotion/idpcu/Pages/notifiablediseases.aspx</p>
15	Netherlands	MERS-CoV, invasive streptococcus A infection, likely foodborne infection at least two cases with an epidemiological link. Chikungya, Dengue only Caribbean part of NL. Chlamydia only notifiable if from animal origin. Haemophilus B only if invasive.
16	Norway	<p>Norway has a two-path notification system for infectious diseases. The first path involves disease notification by the principal clinician, and the second path involves pathogen notification by the testing medical microbiology laboratory. Notifications from both paths are collected and merged with the Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases (MSIS) at the NIPH</p> <p>In addition to notification of the disease given in the above table, the following infections are also notifiable to MSIS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infection and carrier state of methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus • Infection and carrier state of penicillin-resistant pneumococci • Infection and carrier state of toxin-producing Clostridium difficile • Infection and carrier state of vancomycin-resistant enterococci • Infection and carrier state of microbes with special resistance patterns: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Candida auris, o KPB, o linezolid-resistant enterococci (LRE), o linezolid-resistant staphylococci (LRS), o Transferable colistin resistance in gram-negative bacteria

		A list of notifiable disease/infection are given here: https://www.fhi.no/en/hn/health-registries/msis/notifiable-diseases-msis/
17	Poland	https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/download.xsp/WDU20190002430/O/D20192430.pdf
18	Portugal	Hepatitis E, Visceral leishmaniasis, Ebola (separately from Viral haemorrhagic fevers), Mpox, Scarlet Fever.
19	Romania	chickenpox, Leishmania, Scarlet fever, monkeypox
20	Slovenia	https://nijz.si/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/DEFINICIJE_EU_nonEU_2022_marec.pdf Other notifiable diseases are (according to the above linked document): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Amebiasis (Entamoeba histolytica) - Brill-Zinsser disease - Enterobiosis - Enterocolitis caused by Adenovirus, Astrovirus, Norovirus, Rotavirus, Clostridium difficile, EPEC, ETEC, EIEC - Scabies - Leprosy - Viral hemorrhagic fever caused by Arenaviruses, Nairovirus (Crimean-Congo HF), Kyasanur Forest disease virus, Marburg virus, Ebola virus, Hantavirus (HFRS) - Infectious mononucleosis - Leishmaniasis - Meningitis and meningoencephalitis by causative agent - Microsporidiosis - CA-MRSA - Chickenpox - Foodborne illness caused by S. aureus, C. perfringens, V. parahaemolyticus, B. cereus - Shingles (Herpes zoster) - Psittacosis - Rickettsiosis - Sepsis by causative agents - Infection with Burkholderia mallei - Streptococcal pharyngitis - Erysipelas - Scarlet fever - Taeniasis caused by T. solium and T. saginata, unclassified taeniasis - Toxocariasis - Toxoplasmosis - Trachoma - Trichophytosis - Hepatitis E
21	Spain	Mpox, herpes zoster, chickenpox, leprae, Other Spongiform encephalopathies, Mediterranean spotted fever, Gonococcal disease, Leishmaniasis
22	Sweden	Viral meningoencephalitis, Enterobacteriales (ESBL and CRE), MRSA, VRE, S. pneumoniae with reduced susceptibility to penicillin G, Beta-hemolytic group A streptococci (GAS), rotavirus, rabies, psittacosis, Mpox, MERS, HTLV I and II, Yellow fever, Ebola, Amebiasis (Entamoeba histolytica).

Section 5.1. For which pathogens do you perform subtyping (sequencing, serotyping, etc.) and/or phenotyping (AMR, etc.) for surveillance at the national level (out of pathogens in the ECDC strategic framework for the integration of molecular and genomic typing into European surveillance and multi-country outbreak investigation and supplemented

with SARS-CoV-2? Please indicate if there are any **other** pathogens for which you perform subtyping or phenotyping for surveillance in your country at the national level:

Number	Country	Answer
1	Belgium	The pathogens for which subtyping is performed for clinical/surveillance purposes is related to the list of national reference centers and national reference laboratories. Link list: https://www.sciensano.be/en/national-reference-centers-human-microbiology Some of them may be broader than one pathogen eg. NRC for arboviruses or NRC for sexual transmitted infections.
2	Croatia	Work in progress: Salmonella Future plans: Legionella, Bordetella
3	Czechia	Streptococcus agalactiae, Streptococcus pyogenes, Hemophilus influenzae
4	Denmark	Yersinia, Shigella and EIEC, Enterovirus, Hepatitis E virus, Parechovirus, Adenovirus, Rotavirus
5	Finland	Haemophilus influenzae, Vibrio cholerae, Hepatitis E, Norovirus, Rotavirus, Enteroviruses, Measles
6	France	Subtyping and/or phenotyping is included in the missions of all National Reference Centres.
7	Ireland	Shigella, Vancomycin resistant enterococci, colistin resistant Enterobacterales,
8	Italy	For the following bacteria: Escherichia coli, Klebsiella pneumoniae, Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Acinetobacter species, Streptococcus pneumoniae, Staphylococcus aureus, Enterococcus faecalis, Enterococcus faecium) upon request by the hospital laboratories belonging to the National Health System and for ad hoc studies within the National AMR Surveillance. Vibrio cholerae, Shigella spp, Yersinia spp., Haemophilus influenzae, Streptococcus pyogenes Streptococcus agalactiae, Francisella spp., Brucella spp., Leptospira serogroup/serovar. For the following parasites: Echinococcus multilocularis, Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato, Trichinella spp. Giardia duodenalis, Cryptosporidium parvum, Cryptosporidium hominis, plasmodium falciparum. For the following viruses: human parvovirus B19, Epstein-Barr virus (EBV), Hepatitis E virus, measles, rubella, mumps.
9	Latvia	Haemophilus influenzae, Corynebacterium, Measles, Rubella, Borellia from ticks, Hepatitis C virus and other.
10	Luxembourg	Bacteria : VRE, ESBL producing Enterobacterales - Virus : RSV
11	Malta	HCV genotyping and resistance (sequencing) Strep pneumoniae serotyping (reverse hybridisation) Strep pyogenes (sequencing) Haemophilus influenzae
12	Norway	Subtyping is also performed for HBV and HCV
13	Portugal	Monkeypox virus, Chlamydia trachomatis, Mycobacterium tuberculosis, Brucella melitensis
14	Slovenia	We are monitoring for the purposes of the EARS-Net in addition to Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA), Streptococcus pneumoniae, Enterobacterae (CRE, CPE), Acinetobacter spp also (CRA, CRAb) Pseudomonas aeruginosa (CRPs), Enterococcus faecium and faecalis (VRE).

15	Spain	For Hepatitis A virus, and for Legionella spp. the analysis is associated a outbreaks. Other analysis are performed in Measles, cholera
16	Sweden	Subtyping on Neisseira and HIV is performed at an external reference lab.

Section 6.1. For notifiable communicable diseases, to what extent do you experience legal constraints or challenges (e.g. data cannot be shared or is very difficult to share) with lab surveillance data sharing that is considered critical for the purpose of laboratory-based public health surveillance? Critical importance would mean that the surveillance objectives of for the disease in question cannot (all) be met. *Please provide any additional comments about legal constraints or challenges:*

Number	Country	Answer
1	Belgium	As mentioned above there are some challenges as notifiable communicable diseases are organized at regional level whereas the laboratory surveillance networks (e.g. NRCs) are implement at national level. However there is a good collaboration in general to share data and information with clear legal frameworks at regional and national level.
2	Croatia	There is no legal framework for exchange of laboratory surveillance data.
3	Czechia	technical issues mainly related to storage and transfer of data
4	Denmark	Different entities have different rules and judgements in terms of how to aggregate/ anonymize data to ensure that an individual person cannot be identified. This hampers data-sharing between entities.; Some technical fields develop so fast (e.g. cloud-based technologies), that legal processes tend to lag behind.; Balance between Act on Public Disclosure in Administration (i.e. right for information by the public) and Data Protection Law is skewed. The latter is more stringent, which allows for less detailed data sharing for surveillance purposes compared to data the NIPH is obliged to deliver to citizens requesting access to data; Cross-regional data sharing, e.g. in outbreak situations, is a challenge – regions receive their own data from NIPH, but are not allowed to receive data from other regions for data protection reasons.
5	Finland	Surveillance of respiratory viruses is difficult and very limited, because sampling requires informed consent. This procedure is considered laborious. Legislation will be reviewed, but changes may be difficult to achieve.
6	France	The legal framework of Santé publique France activities (https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/codes/section_lc/LEGITEXT000006072665/LEGISCTA000032403931/#LEGISCTA000032404559) states that the agency can access all data (including lab-based) that are needed to complete its missions.
7	Italy	At the moment data linkage is permitted only for pathogens included in National surveillances. There is ongoing work at National Level to approve a norm that will define data and mechanisms usable for data linkage. Discussions involve Italy MoH, NIPH, Pharmaceutical Agency and others"
8	Latvia	To assess the weight and trends, data on the volume of tests performed are collected. There is no unified database that collects all the performed tests. The law does not define the submission of the volume of tests performed. The scope and format of data provision are defined, but sometimes it is not enough. There is no defined format for testing methods and results for individual pathogens.
9	Luxembourg	We are not NIPH. We are in the process of setting up AMR reporting, but we are not allowed to keep patients data, so we need to pseudonymized data.
10	Malta	IDCU does not only function as a surveillance unit but also as a case management one, investigating cases and outbreaks of infectious diseases.

11	Netherlands	No legal requirement for labs to share lab surveillance data with NIPH. Lab-reported data is considered pseudonymised personal data. Legal grey zone on whether labs are allowed to share such data with the NIPH, but done in practice for over a decade with varying frequency. Cases must be notified to NIPH, but anonymously, and can only be linked to samples reported by labs on a statistical basis, preventing many analyses and reducing timeliness of response.
12	Norway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mandatory submission of samples and test material to the relevant national reference laboratory is regulated by law (MSIS –regulation § 2-4a). However, no regulation currently exists (work initiated) for sharing of Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) data between laboratories and to the national surveillance system. • GDPR restrains us in sharing genetic sequences where the sequence ID is pseudonymised. GDPR demand anonymity, this is not possible as shared sequences need to be able to be traced back for quality controls and for further investigations of a sample. • GDPR issues with sharing of clinical data with gene sequences to public health authority restrains Norway from sharing more than 30 % of all SARS-CoV-2 gene sequences produced at external laboratories
13	Portugal	As notifiable communicable diseases are mandatory in Portugal, some laboratories don't report the diseases and/or don't send samples do NRL to further studies (as subtyping). Once a Public Health threat is detected, the NIPH create a designate taskforce with stakeholders, including National reference laboratory and experts where information is share under the umbrella of public health threat.
14	Slovenia	In our national legislation, which determines the reporting of communicable diseases and their causative pathogens, it is not clearly defined that laboratories also provide data on the patient's identifier (uniform citizen registration number or health insurance number) when reporting data and that the data should be reported in the electronic form. This legislation also does not clearly define the obligation to report the results of additional investigations of communicable disease pathogens that are important for public health (genotyping, sequencing,...). The national legislation in this area is outdated, from a period when some of these microbiological methods (sequencing, ...) did not exist yet and would therefore need to be renewed.
15	Spain	There are not legal constraints for the purpose of laboratory-based public health surveillance in the Regions.

Section 7.1. Under what legal basis (GDPR Art 6.1) does your NIPH process lab surveillance data, including directly identifiable or pseudonymized personal data? *Please provide any additional comments, in particular if you chose multiple options:*

Number	Country	Answer
1	Belgium	<p>Sciensano (the Belgian NIPH) has a broad range of activities and expertise with different stakeholders that may process data under different legal conditions. There is no common legal basis for all these different activities but in general "performance of a task carried out in the public interest" is used as legal ground mentioned in the legislations.</p> <p>Below some examples to illustrate the differences in legal frameworks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The NRC within the Belgian NIPH may process nominative data following the royal degree of 2011, link: https://etaamb.openjustice.be/nl/koninklijk-besluit-van-09-februari-2011_n2011022071.html • The Service healthdata.be may process nominative and/or pseudomonized information

		<p>depending on the legal framework and deliberations of the Information Security Committee (ISC) e.g. COVID-19 legal framework: https://etaamb.openjustice.be/nl/samenwerkingsakkoord-van-25-augustus-2020_n2020010437.html and ISC deliberation: https://www.ehealth.fgov.be/ehealthplatform/file/view/AXW7iSzLI9vUUfvGGe54?filename=20-132-n114-strijd%20tegen%20verspreiding%20coronavirus%20SARS-CoV-2-gewijzigd%20op%2030%20maart%202021.pdf</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The service of epidemiology processes pseudonymized or anonymous data following the law establishing sciensano (NIPH) in 2018: https://www.ejustice.just.fgov.be/cgi_loi/change_lg.pl?language=nl&la=N&cn=2018022502&table_name=wet
2	Croatia	The Croatian Institute of Public Health (CIPH) processes laboratory surveillance data, including directly identifiable or pseudonymized personal data, based on the legal basis of the Law on Protection of the Population from Infectious Diseases.
3	Finland	In general, legislation allows and requires collecting data and samples for lab surveillance. Surveillance of respiratory viruses is cumbersome.
4	France	CNIL, the French institute in charge of ensuring personal data protection, monitors Santé publique France compliance to secure data handling and storage practices. The CNIL standards are higher than EU GDPR.
5	Ireland	https://www.hpsc.ie/notifiablediseases/notifyinginfectiousdiseases/
6	Italy	In addition to GDPR art 6.1, for the personal data collected in the surveillances, it is necessary to identify an appropriate exemption under Article 9 GDPR or to define a rule / norm with the rational and details of data usage. Concerning the exception in particular, this could be identifiable in art. 9, par. 2, lett. g) processing is necessary for reasons of substantial public interest, on the basis of Union or Member State law and in the art.9 par. 2, lett. l) processing is necessary for reasons of public interest in the area of public health.
7	Latvia	As monitoring data are considered to be a special category of data, the processing of such data in Latvia is subject to the sub-points h and l of paragraph 2 of Article 9 of the regulation, together with the relevant national regulations in the field of epidemiological safety.
8	Lithuania	Some isolates of resistant pathogens for reference arrive without personal data
9	Luxembourg	NIPH is allowed to keep data in accordance to GDPR and Public Health Act
10	Malta	<p>IDCU does not only function as a surveillance unit but also as a case management one, investigating cases and outbreaks of infectious diseases. In view of this, patient data is communicated to IDCU to enable case investigation, contact tracing and implementation of the necessary measures to safeguard public health. Aggregate, non-identifiable data is then used for surveillance outputs.</p> <p>Public Health Act of Malta obliges clinicians and laboratories to report notifiable infectious disease to public health authority as part of the prevention and control of infectious diseases CAP. 465 Part IV https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/465/eng/pdf</p> <p>The Health Act defines the role of the Department of Health Regulation including "to prevent communicable and non-communicable diseases and carry out surveillance and control in order to protect the general public from such diseases"</p>

		<p>https://legislation.mt/eli/ln/2013/391/eng</p> <p>Subsidiary Legislation 528.10 on Processing of Personal Data (Secondary Processing - Health Sector), allows the processing of personal data for the purpose of public health surveillance.</p> <p>https://legislation.mt/eli/sl/528.10/eng</p>
11	Netherlands	The NL law on the public health institute mandates the latter to perform surveillance as well as scientific research.
12	Slovenia	<p>In Slovenia we have in place different laws and regulations under which the NIPH is entitled to collect, process and analyze lab surveillance data. These legal acts are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Communicable Disease Law 2. Regulations on reporting infectious diseases and special measures for their prevention and control 3. Act on databases in the field of healthcare <p>To execute epidemiological investigation and outbreak investigation with the aim of preventing spreading of a communicable disease, the laws and regulation mentioned above allow the NIPH to process lab surveillance data with personal data.</p> <p>For sexually transmitted diseases (HIV, chlamydia, gonorrhoea, syphilis) Soundex number is used to protect vulnerable groups. These diseases are reported by case, however their personal data is not shared.</p>

Section 8.1. Indicate for each pathogen the different data elements that local laboratories report to the NIPH (directly or indirectly) along with their test results for a particular sample. *Please indicate if there are any **other** data elements that local laboratories report for surveillance in your country at the national level:*

Number	Country	Answer
1	Belgium	<p>In the table above it has to be noticed that "age" can sometimes be used instead of date of birth. Other data elements that may be transmitted to the NIPH are gender, name of the local laboratory, hospitalization, type of sample. The requested information/pathogen is often in line with the Tessy metadataset used by ECDC.</p> <p>For AMR related organisms the protocol is available at https://www.sciensano.be/fr/biblio/european-antimicrobial-resistance-surveillance-belgium-ears-be-protocol-2021-including-data-call. These NRCs are situated outside the NIPH and therefore less data elements are transmitted in comparison with NRCs that are part of the NIPH.</p> <p>Local laboratories may report test results towards Sciensano ("no lab surveillance") with other data elements gender/technique used for identification/type of sample.</p>
2	Croatia	<p>For influenza - SARI sentinel lab surveillance (name, surname, date of birth, postal code, date of sample collection)</p> <p>For tuberculosis - as a periodical report (name, surname, date of birth, health insurance number, MIRU code, genotyping result, drug susceptibility test)</p>
3	Czechia	death, result concluded by local laboratory
4	Denmark	LabID, Sample material, anatomical sampling site, gender, age, hospitalID, patient type (admitted, outpatient etc.), hospital unit, properties of pathogen, for bacteria: antibiotic and resistance information (SIR)

5	Finland	the municipality where patient is treated, type of sample, microbiological characteristics (depending on microbes)
6	France	Depend on the disease and on the situation (routine surveillance vs signal investigation)
7	Germany	Clostridium difficile is only reported as notifications by physician, no lab results available
8	Ireland	depending on disease, we may also receive test type, specimen type, specimen site, lab authorization date
9	Italy	In addition to the data described in table 8, most of the surveillance system collect information regarding the region where the case occurred. Moreover specific data are required for specific pathogens (e.g. outcome, hospital ward, diagnostic methods).
10	Latvia	The collection of data elements includes referral diagnosis, testing material, sample sender (e.g. GP, hospital, etc.), date of sample receipt in the laboratory, start and finish date of testing, testing method and results, patient's address (excluding postal code), age, telephone number, gender, and the name and specialty of the person who sent the report. Currently, the National Reference Laboratory is responsible for human laboratory testing, while the Institute of Food Safety, Animal Health, and Environment handles environmental testing.
11	Luxembourg	Sample type, genotyping for some pathogens
12	Malta	In Malta we have one main government general hospital (Mater Dei Hospital) and clinical laboratory that caters for all the country. IDCU has access to the test result platform of the hospital and positive infectious disease test results are downloaded daily and investigated. IDCU also receives notifications from private hospitals and GPs in the community. Data from the lab includes national identifier, name, date of birth, address, specimen type, type of test carried out, date of result, test result. Further information on the case such as date of onset, symptoms, travel history, risk exposures, nationality/ethnicity etc are collected by IDCU staff upon contacting the case as part of routine case management investigations.
13	Netherlands	Instead of birth date, age is provided (we indicated that as birth date). Sample origin (e.g. blood) is often provided.
14	Norway	• Sample material
15	Poland	Ad. question 8
16	Romania	If the case is confirmed or not
17	Slovenia	no
18	Spain	Sample, method of diagnoses, outbreak related.
19	Sweden	We have an automated system named Svebar which automatically collects all cultures from participating clinical microbiological laboratories. Only bacteria and fungi are collected. No personal data is collected in the system.

Section 9.1. Is the NIPH legally allowed and able to link lab surveillance data with surveillance data from other sources, e.g. notifications by physicians? *Please provide any additional comments:*

Number	Country	Answer
1	Belgium	No generic legal framework but it is possible for specific situations/projects e.g. COVID-19 (legal framework mentioned above) or surveillance of pediatric vaccine preventable infectious diseases https://www.sciensano.be/nl/surveillance-van-infectieziekten-bij-kinderen-pedisur#informatieveiligheid . So we are allowed in specific situations. Our NIPH appeals to authorizations from specific

		health data protection bodies such as the Information Security Committee (ISC) to be allowed to link datasets such as laboratory and physician data.
2	Croatia	No legal framework and IT infrastructure
3	Czechia	As laboratory surveillance is part of indicator-based national-wide surveillance, physicians and laboratories reports to the national information system of infectious disease through Regional Public Health Authority
4	Denmark	<p>Our country has a long history of national registers such as the the Vaccination Register, Civil Registration System, National Patient Register, Cause of Death Register, Authorization Register, Register for Selected Chronic Diseases and Severe Mental Disorders, Health Insurance Register, Database for Notifiable Diseases etc. Registers can be linked by means of the civil registration number that is assigned to all residents of the country.</p> <p>The following areas constitute gaps for which currently no registers/ structural data sources exist: pregnant women, nursing homes, school absence and residences for vulnerable groups (e.g. persons suffering from mental illness, persons with physical disabilities, social problems or substance abuse problems).</p>
5	Finland	Notifications from physicians and from laboratories are collected to the same register, national infectious disease register. Other information such as home municipality, nationality, country of birth, and information on death can be obtained from linkage to population register. For vaccine preventable diseases, the vaccination status can be later linked from vaccination register.
6	France	Depends on the disease and is in most cases based on an anonymized data identifier and not on the case identity.
7	Ireland	https://www.hpsc.ie/notifiablediseases/notifyinginfectiousdiseases/ in the absence of health identifier, name, dob, address, ref lab ID, etc are used for matching
8	Italy	The link is possible but not for all the surveillances.
9	Latvia	Both healthcare providers and laboratories are involved in reporting, and the received data is combined to ensure comprehensive monitoring and response
10	Netherlands	Only for SARS-CoV-2
11	Norway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Each case notified by laboratories to MSIS is in principle complemented and completed with notification from the clinician. The information is stored in the same database (all relevant information combined). Except for a few diseases, where only information from laboratories are mandatory to report.
12	Poland	We have the possibility to link the lab results data with clinician's notifications, but State Sanitary Inspection has main legal role in this field.
13	Portugal	The legal allowance is under the protection of public health law.
14	Romania	There are no other comments
15	Slovenia	The law on databases in healthcare (see Q7.1) states that the NIPH can link all the databases that are under its jurisdiction and management.
16	Spain	The NIPH according to new legislation (will be issued this year) will be allowed to link lab and epi surveillance data using the ID personal unique identifier. At this moment only is possible for COVID-19 surveillance (SERLAB)
17	Sweden	Both types of information (clinical and laboratory forms are compiled to a case for each patient) is mandatory to report in the surveillance system (SmiNet) for all notifiable diseases.

Section 10.1. With respect to the assessment of the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects that is part of a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA, GDPR Art 35.7.c): has the NIPH assessed the risk of identification of a person based on the lab surveillance data provided to the NIPH? *If Yes, please describe how this risk was assessed:*

Number	Country	Answer
1	Austria	Full names are not provided - only initials unique IDs are assigned to cases
2	Belgium	Yes, per disease/project (see answer question 9). For DPIA we use the support of our GDPR compliance tool, called one trust.
3	Denmark	A DPIA is planned that includes assessing the risk of identification of a person in general.
4	Finland	Processes and registers are regularly audited for data security. For each register, written information/data security assessment is performed before implementation and if major changes are introduced.
5	France	Santé publique France has a Data Protection Officer doing continuous evaluation of identification risks. CNIL, the French institute in charge of ensuring personal data protection, does regular audits.
6	Germany	Is currently prepared for the electronic (machine to machine) surveillance system
7	Ireland	PIAs developed for our data collection systems
8	Italy	The DPIA has been carried out for Clostridium difficile infections while is ongoing for the other diseases. The DPIA is redacted following the regulation ISO/IEC 31000:2018, "Risk Management – Principles and guidelines", which describes the logical and systematic process that leads to risk mitigation and control, and the ISO/IEC 29134:2017 ("Information Technology — Security techniques — Guidelines for privacy impact assessment"), which indicates guidelines applicable to all types of facilities, public and private, in order to create, organize and implement GDPR-compliant projects. Specifically, the formula used to calculate the impact risk of processing on the rights and freedoms of data subjects is to multiply the impact, that is, what may happen if the event occurs, by the probability the event will happen.
9	Latvia	Personal data is only collected for the cases of mandatory notifiable infections or for further investigation of cases notified by healthcare personnel.
10	Netherlands	Done per individual disease or group of similar diseases.
11	Norway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MSIS has performed a Data Protection Impact Assessment for the system, and has a clear legal mandate in infectious disease act, health register act and MSIS-regulation. Changes in infrastructure is made only if deemed necessary and after a risk assessment has been performed
12	Poland	The assessment was concordant with the EU and national legislation.
13	Slovenia	Legislation in Slovenia (Communicable Diseases Law and Regulations on reporting infectious diseases and special measures for their prevention and control) specifically state which personal data should be included when reporting a communicable disease or pathogen.
14	Spain	The NIPH complies with the GDPR and is carrying out the DPIA for the surveillance databases
15	Sweden	Routines for assessment according to ISO 27002 Standard.

Section 11.1. Do you have legal expertise available at the NIPH to assist you with setting up or maintaining lab surveillance? *If Limited or No, please describe in more detail:*

Number	Country	Answer
1	Czechia	For surveillance in general, the responsibility lies on Ministry of Health
2	Denmark	All authorities under the Ministry of Health are separate legal entities with separate agreements with respect to data sharing with regions and municipalities. This creates extra workload for the legal team to assess data sharing issues on a case-by-case basis; Challenging to find legal experts with solid understanding of infectious disease surveillance.;
3	France	Limite human resources (one DPO)
4	Ireland	Onsite DPO and access to legal services
5	Latvia	There are no legal experts with specialized knowledge in laboratory surveillance available at the NIPH. Only general profile lawyers are present, and there is a separate data protection specialist who can offer guidance on the legal aspects of managing data in this context.
6	Lithuania	NPIH participate in preparing legislation
7	Malta	NIPH has no legal expertise specifically assigned to it to assist it with its legal requirements
8	Norway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •NIPH has a department for legal services, which is of assistance when there is a need to evaluate and look into the regulatory issues regarding surveillance of infectious diseases. •However, if there is a need of interpretation of regulation, this service is provided by the legal experts at the Directorate of Health, and if there is a need for a regulatory change, this is done by the Ministry of Health.
9	Portugal	High demand on the legal officers' special during outbreaks.
10	Slovenia	There is a legal department at the NIPH that helps with any legal questions, however they are not specialized in data protection legislation. In accordance with the Slovenian Data Protection Law, NIPH has named a responsible person/board for data protection that provides their opinion regarding handling with personal data.

Section 12. Please provide some examples of how national or international legislation either hampers or facilitates lab surveillance at the national level, and how you have potentially overcome any hampering issues:

Number	Country	Answer
1	Austria	The Epidemic Law enables the NIPH access to and use of data entered for all notifiable diseases
2	Belgium	Important for us is the Royal Decree that defines the role and scope of the NRCs link: https://etaamb.openjustice.be/nl/koninklijk-besluit-van-09-februari-2011_n2011022071.html . ECDC –EC guidance on diseases which are recommend to notify at EU level (https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/all-topics/eu-case-definitions) helps to encourage participation from laboratories to voluntary lab based surveillance (next to the mandatory notification carried out by the regional health authorities). Data linkage can be challenging regarding the legal framework/authorizations from competent data protection authorities. This has been achieved for COVID-19 and we try to create a generic framework for infectious diseases in general in the future to overcome this issue/improve pandemic preparedness.
3	Croatia	Law on protection of the Population from infectious Diseases which is the main legal framework for infectious disease surveillance does not facilitate lab surveillance. All infectious diseases are reported based on clinical

		diagnosis, except for rubeola embryopathy, syphilis, AIDS, HbcAg carriers, HCV antibody carriers, HIV antibody carriers and S. typhi which are reported based on laboratory results. In that legislation all reporting is done based on aggregated data (reports) with no patient identifiers.
4	Czechia	Surveillance is mandatory by law, new online electronic national information system of infectious disease established as of 2018 eased the process.
5	Denmark	¹ In our country, we are currently in between two national executive orders on notifiable diseases. The differences between the two executive orders has led to a grey zone, e.g. that surveillance is already conducted for certain pathogens that are laid out in the new executive order, although the new executive order is not yet in force.; <i>The new executive order has been under development for several years and has entered into force November 1st 2023. It has been challenging to develop the surveillance system, as long as the legal ground was not in place, and when the new executive order came into force, we were not yet able to fully comply, as building surveillance systems takes time.</i> Mismatches in EU and national law: e.g. under the zoonosis directive, our country is obliged to report on certain zoonotic diseases to the EU, however, this is not allowed under the current national executive order on notifiable diseases.;
6	Estonia	The list of notifiable pathogens which require notification to the CD surveillance system together with the personal data set is established by a regulation of the MoSA in 2019
7	Finland	Sending respiratory virus specimen to reference laboratories or any other laboratory is only possible if informed consent is provided for that purpose. Any specimen containing human DNA cannot be sent to laboratories for method development.
8	Ireland	https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/1981/si/390/made/en/print and https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2003/si/707/made/en/print provide for legal basis for the notification of named infectious diseases and of outbreaks/clusters of disease by physicians and lab directors
9	Latvia	National and international legislation both facilitate and impede laboratory surveillance efforts. The legal requirement to report cases is helpful, but obtaining necessary information may be difficult without specific legal mandates. The formalized process for surveillance hinder effective decision-making and limit flexibility. Overcoming these challenges requires careful consideration of both legal requirements and practical considerations to develop effective surveillance strategies. Procedures for Registration of Infectious Diseases https://likumi.lv/ta/en/en/id/20667-procedures-for-registration-of-infectious-diseases
10	Lithuania	We often need bioethics permission to organize temporary laboratory surveillance. Sometimes we have difficulties to collect additional clinical or epidemiological information about patient. Some hospitals send samples without National identifier of patient.
11	Luxembourg	International legislation facilitated COVID reporting and opens new avenues for other pathogen reporting (ex: AMR reporting)
12	Malta	The following acts and legislations greatly facilitate the surveillance of health data for public health: Public Health Act of Malta obliges clinicians and laboratories to report notifiable infectious disease to public health authority as part of the prevention and control of infectious diseases CAP. 465 Part IV https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/465/eng/pdf

¹ Text added in italics has been added during the revision process of the deliverable and is not part of the original survey answer.

		<p>The Health Act defines the role of the Department of Health Regulation including "to prevent communicable and non-communicable diseases and carry out surveillance and control in order to protect the general public from such diseases" https://legislation.mt/eli/ln/2013/391/eng</p> <p>Subsidiary Legislation 528.10 on Processing of Personal Data (Secondary Processing - Health Sector), allows the processing of personal data for the purpose of public health surveillance. https://legislation.mt/eli/sl/528.10/eng</p>
13	Netherlands	<p>National law: physical samples must be sent anonymously unless informed consent is obtained. The latter is in practice very difficult. Lab surveillance data can only be sent for surveillance if labs meet a number of exceptions defined by law, which are unclear if they are always met.</p>
14	Norway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Mandatory submission of samples and test material to the relevant national reference laboratory is regulated by law (MSIS –regulation § 2-4a). However, no regulation currently exists (work initiated) for sharing of Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) data between laboratories and to the national surveillance system. •GDPR restrains us in sharing genetic sequences where the sequence ID is pseudonymised. GDPR demand anonymity, this is not possible as shared sequences need to be able to be traced back for quality controls and for further investigations of a sample. •GDPR issues with sharing of clinical data with gene sequences to public health authority restrains Norway from sharing more than 30 % of all SARS-CoV-2 gene sequences produced at external laboratories •The issue of sequence data sharing has been raised and presented for the Ministry of Health for legislation.
15	Portugal	<p>Portugal has same legislation that facilitate lab surveillance. As example is the Law 81/2009 that establish the public health surveillance system that will serve the legal basis for the mandatory notification of some infections/disease to be reported by lab. The Ministry Act 16548/2009, make the NRL responsible to coordinate the national network for flu lab diagnosis that increase the information shared by lab with the NRL.</p>
16	Slovenia	<p>At NIPH Slovenia, we mostly rely on our national legislation (stated in previous questions) which allows us to acquire and collect personal data with reported communicable diseases. In our national legislation, which determines the reporting of infectious diseases and their pathogens, it is not clearly defined that laboratories also provide data on the patient's identifier (uniform citizen registration number or health insurance number) when reporting. Therefore, for some communicable disease agents, data on their properties (genotypes, sequences, AMR, ...) cannot be linked to epidemiological data or data from clinicians at NIPH.</p>
17	Spain	<p>As has been mentioned lab surveillance is carried out by the Regions. The NIPH only collects the data reported by them and there are not legal constraints for the purpose of laboratory-based public health surveillance in the Regions.</p>

Section 13.1. Does your country have any provisions in national law that further specify how personal data can be processed in the interest of public health, as described in e.g. GDPR Art 6.2 or Art 9.2.i? *If yes, please elaborate on the rationale:*

Number	Country	Answer
1	Austria	In outbreak situations, the NIPH (AGES) is allowed access to personal informations of cases and contact persons there of health authorities are required to comply with tasks.
2	Belgium	This process is ongoing with the creation of a Health Data Agency in 2023. The aim of the agency is to improve the availability of data on health care and related data, and to ensure that available data can be accessed reliably and in a simplified way.
3	Denmark	The Danish Health Act and the Danish Data Protection Act
4	Estonia	Q12 comm
5	France	CNIL sets the national data protection standards (details here: https://www.cnil.fr/)
6	Ireland	Art 9.2.i translted to Irish law
7	Italy	The main regulatory sources describing the way in which personal data can be processed in the interest of public health are found in Legislative Decree No. 196/2003 (Privacy Code) ss.mm.ii. and, specifically, in Article 2f (Guarantee measures for the processing of genetic, biometric and health-related data) and in the Prime Minister's Decree of March 3, 2017 (GU Serie Generale n.109 del 12-05-2017) and, specifically, in Articles 3 (Surveillance systems and registers of national and regional relevance) and 5 (Modalities of data processing), without prejudice to the principles set forth in the GDPR.
8	Latvia	We rely on Article 9.2(i) of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) which permits the processing of personal data for reasons of public interest in the area of public health. There are also specific provisions in Latvian national law that further clarify how personal data can be processed for public health purposes. These provisions specify the circumstances under which personal data can be collected, as well as the type and format of data that can be collected.
9	Malta	<p>Public Health Act of Malta obliges clinicians and laboratories to report notifiable infectious disease to public health authority as part of the prevention and control of infectious diseases CAP. 465 Part IV https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/465/eng/pdf</p> <p>The General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR) and the Data Protection Act (Cap 586) regulate the processing of personal data whether held electronically or in manual form. Data Protection Act (Cap. 586 of the Laws of Malta) https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/586/eng/pdf</p> <p>The Health Act defines the role of the Department of Health Regulation including "to prevent communicable and non-communicable diseases and carry out surveillance and control in order to protect the general public from such diseases" https://legislation.mt/eli/ln/2013/391/eng</p> <p>Subsidiary Legislation 528.10 on Processing of Personal Data (Secondary Processing - Health Sector), allows the processing of personal data for the purpose of public health surveillance. https://legislation.mt/eli/sl/528.10/eng</p>
10	Netherlands	Implementing Act GDPR, Law on public health, Law on public health agency.
11	Norway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Under Article 9.2 i) GDPR there is a general prohibition for the processing of special categories of data, but the prohibition is excluded when certain requirements are met. For MSIS these requirements are met in Infectious Disease Act § 7-9, Health Register Act § 11 and MSIS-regulation.

12	Slovenia	Communicable disease Law and subsequent Regulation of communicable diseases reporting determine what specific information (data sets including personal data) have to be reported to NIPH for the purpose of surveillance. Additionally, the Act on databases in the field of healthcare specifies which data (data sets including personal data) can NIPH store in the national databases on communicable diseases.
13	Spain	The legislation that will be issued in the near future includes some points in order to allow personal data use in the interest of public health

Section 14. *In your opinion, what aspects of the GDPR, if any, would need to be changed or adapted to facilitate performing lab surveillance?*

Number	Country	Answer
1	Austria	n.a.
2	Belgium	Practical clarity around some terms/definitions e.g. when can we consider data as pseudonymized? The answer is not always clear with different interpretations and rules in different countries as a result.
3	Croatia	In our opinion, the EHDS Regulation should include laboratory surveillance data as part of the data shared for secondary use and facilitate their exchange.
4	Finland	Our institute has outlined that microbe identification codes (provided in our institute upon arrival of the sample) are not personal data. This allows us to use same strain ID:s in communication when sharing eg. sequence data outside. However, this ID is not reported back to clinical laboratories.
5	Germany	It is important to have the national legislation to process the data
6	Italy	Reinforce that public health need data linkage with clinical notification: this has to be guaranteed also by putting adequate resources in resolving all the regulatory aspects.
7	Luxembourg	Personal data should be transferable to appointed organization (if different to NIPH)
8	Netherlands	In practice, the pseudonymization of lab surveillance data makes identification of a person impossible except in rare cases through statistical disclosure. When measures are taken to also prevent statistical disclosure, the pseudonymised, or doubly pseudonymized data, could be considered by law to be in effect anonymous data.
9	Norway	• There is a potential for improving the national regulatory framework for surveillance, more than a need for a change in GDPR. This to enable reuse of data from different health registries and other sources. This can reduce burden of manual reporting, increase timeliness, and improve quality of surveillance data.
10	Slovenia	No, we find that it is written sufficiently.

Section 15.1. *What organizational units at the NIPH deal directly with lab surveillance? If "Other", please provide more information:*

Number	Country	Answer
1	Denmark	DK-Vet consortium (https://dkvet.dk/english/about/) ; Biobank
2	France	Laboratory, Microbiology and bioinformatic skills are not present at the NIPH (Santé publique France) but delegated to the respective National Reference Centres.
3	Netherlands	Data science team also receives data from bioinformatics or microbiology team

4	Portugal	The National Reference Lab also has a bioinformatics teams.
5	Slovenia	no

Section 16.1. Do you regularly provide dedicated training on lab surveillance for the teams mentioned in question 15? E.g. scientific aspects, data management, communication, infrastructure etc. *If yes, how and for which aspects (e.g. scientific aspects, data management, communication, infrastructure) do you organize and train teams?*

Number	Country	Answer
1	Denmark	No dedicated lab-surveillance courses are provided by the NIPH as such, but do offer attending courses for data management and analysis (e.g. SAS, Python etc), ECDC courses on epidemiology and other relevant aspects, summerschools, internal regular presentations
2	France	Continous staff training, seminars between Santé publique France and the National Reference Centres.
3	Malta	Only when there are changes to SOPs and when new recruits join the unit
4	Netherlands	EUPHEM, EPIET
5	Norway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific aspects (method development, surveillance and outbreak detection) • Data management (data management and statistical analysis) • Communication (media training)
6	Slovenia	Selected epidemiologists have the opportunity to apply for the EPIET fellowship which gives them broader knowledge and insight into lab surveillance. Others gain knowledge while working, older colleagues transfer their knowledge to younger ones. There is no systematic training organized at NIPH.
7	Spain	The epidemiologist, both at regional and national level, are those who deal with lab surveillance (we mean lab reporting). Epidemiologist coordinate multidisciplinary teams (including microbiologists) for setting and improving lab surveillance. All aspects except for communication

Section 17.1. Do you have training needs for lab surveillance (e.g. scientific aspects, data management, communication, infrastructure) at the NIPH that are difficult to meet? *Please describe training needs in more detail:*

Number	Country	Answer
1	Croatia	The training needs include all four layers of interoperability (legal, organizational, semantic and technical). This training is needed for legal, administrative, laboratory and IT staff, bioinformaticians, epidemiologists, microbiologists, etc.
2	Czechia	We are missing dedicated training, at the moment only partial training activities are performed. Most needed would be training on exhaustive data analysis, data management training, WGS training (bioinformatics), etc.
3	Denmark	As teams are very diverse and have different backgrounds, teams need to be trained in and have a general understanding of all aspects of lab-based surveillance to ensure an interdisciplinary understanding/ cross-learning and to strive for excellence.
4	Estonia	sequencing data management, scientific aspects and practical implementation
5	Finland	We have plans to update our surveillance strategy. Also the infectious disease register and the LIMS of our institute are under reconstruction. After these have been completed, training on all the aspects (scientific, data management, communication, infra) is warranted.

6	Ireland	bioinformatics, etc.
7	Latvia	There are training needs for lab surveillance at the SPKC that are currently not being met. These needs include scientific aspects, data management, communication, and infrastructure. Additionally, lab surveillance are not currently included in the public health education program.
8	Lithuania	Knowledges in statistical methods, data management, communication, molecular epidemiology
9	Luxembourg	Concerning AMR, we will provide training and guidance
10	Malta	More personnel needed to manage and analyze data. Training needed on data management and scientific aspects.
11	Netherlands	Training microbiologists on surveillance and vice versa NIPH epidemiologists on clinical microbiology laboratory
12	Norway	• Need to train a larger pool of dedicated and applied bioinformaticians
13	Portugal	Biorisk management, applied microbiology and laboratory investigation.
14	Romania	common training for epidemiologists and lab specialists
15	Slovenia	Slovenia is a very small country with limited resources, hence our national training needs are met with challenges, because a small number of professionals have to cover multiple expertise areas. Any trainings at the EU level for lab surveillance would therefore be very much welcome for us.
16	Spain	General knowledge on surveillance concepts, legislation, data management and data quality

Section 18. Do you take any specific measures to attract and retain talent in the area of lab surveillance, including people with an IT or data science background?

Number	Country	Answer
1	Austria	No
2	Belgium	Funding...At the service of Epidemiology of infectious diseases we try to give good job conditions with a contract over a longer period, combine "service" (data/IT) and "research" objectives to motivate. At the service of healthdata.be there is an important input from technical data/IT consultants.
3	Croatia	Staff is currently encouraged to participate in international projects and take additional educations in the scope of bioinformatics and infectious disease surveillance.
4	Czechia	No
5	Denmark	Offer flexibility and working from home; stimulating work environment with a high level of knowledge; trust; work-life balance; social activities and collegiate atmosphere; options for professional development; freedom to explore and follow one's own interests within certain boundaries
6	Estonia	yes
7	Ireland	Several in-house epidemiologist have laboratory background. Recently, we have started to more actively recruit data scientists but more recruitment needed in this area
8	Italy	We are recruiting personel with temporary position through the PNRR (Il Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza) and the "Rete Italiana per la sorveglianza virologica, il monitoraggio immunologico, la formazione e la ricerca in Preparazione alla gestione delle Emergenze Infettive – R.I.Pr.E.I." project.
9	Latvia	Cooperation and consultations with NRL and Institute of Food Safety, Animal Health and Environment.

10	Lithuania	We propose remote work
11	Malta	No
12	Netherlands	No
13	Romania	training for medical personnel and IT specialists in bioinformatics
14	Slovenia	It is a big challenge for the public sector to attract and retain talent for this field of profession, especially people with IT and data science background, because the economic sector can offer them higher salaries and a more adjustable working conditions. We are, however, trying our best to create a stimulating working environment, stable working conditions, permanent job positions and including them in international/EU projects.
15	Spain	Little control on this issue in the NIPH. It is clearly an important subject that requires improvement

Section 19.1. Which (international) data standards, such as terminologies and ontologies, are used for lab surveillance in your country? *If "Other, including national standards", please describe which. Additional comments can be added as well:*

Number	Country	Answer
1	Belgium	HL7-FHIR is not used yet, but intended in the future.
2	Croatia	Currently all data from microbiology laboratories are stored centrally in the national system held by the Croatian National Insurance Fund as PDF files which are operationally and informatically unusable for secondary use of data and surveillance reporting. A need for a national standard for microbiology reporting has been recognised and the Croatian Institute of Public Health is currently working on the development on such standard and mapping legal barriers that need to be addressed for a successful implementation.
3	Denmark	SNOMED: work in progress to map the codes of the National Microbiology Database to SNOMED codes; Planned to use FHIR in MiBa in the future; ICD is used in the National Patient Register; ATC is used in the Medicines Statistics Register; NPU codes used in the national Laboratory Database;
4	Finland	Laboratories use common terminology for diagnostics methods: Nomenclature for laboratory analysis requests by Association of Finnish Municipalities (Kuntaliitto) https://koodistopalvelu.kanta.fi/codeserver/pages/download?name=120_1445249924108.xls&pKey=pubfiles0 . For notifications we use microbe coding/hierarchy from the national infectious diseases register (Excel-link: https://koodistopalvelu.kanta.fi/codeserver/pages/download?name=1103_1390999387750.xls&pKey=pubfiles0). ICD coding is used for physician notifications.
5	France	H' (Hprim)
6	Ireland	Data dictionaries established for national data collection, and AMR and other laboratory standards used for diagnostic and typing methods
7	Latvia	LOINC isn't introduced in Latvia yet, but it is in the introducing process and all laboratories will use it.

		Other: WHO, ECDC, CDC, EUCAST (European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing) Laboratories use Diagnostic-Related Groups (DRG) system.
8	Malta	ICD is used for registries of non-communicable disease data, including mortality registries and for hospital activity analysis of discharged patients. ICD coding is not used for routine lab surveillance of infectious diseases. Malta is a small MS with only one main general hospital and laboratory catering for all the country. IDCU has access to the infectious disease test result platform of the main laboratory and positive test results are downloaded on a daily basis. Every case is contacted by IDCU, additional information gathered round every case and cases are classified using the latest EU case definitions https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/all-topics/eu-case-definitions
9	Norway	• Lab reports are sent using both an existing standard (XML) for electronic reporting for laboratories and the national Laboratory Classification System (NLK), which is based on the international NPU coding system
10	Poland	ICD was implemented into the names of questionnaires and glossaries for diseases under surveillance.
11	Romania	EUCAST
12	Slovenia	The laboratories do not have national code tables, so they use local coding tables for pathogens and microbiological analyses in their laboratory information systems. The NIPH has the ability to assign or determine an ICD-10 code once we receive microbiological data and clinical information for a reported case. This is then added to our national database for communicable diseases.

Section 20.1. Does the NIPH technically assist local laboratories with providing the lab surveillance data? *If yes, how does the NIPH technically assist local laboratories with providing the lab surveillance data?*

Number	Country	Answer
1	Croatia	Croatian Institute of Public Health is including all laboratories that are willing to participate in the exchange of knowledge needed for the development of a national standard for microbiology results.
2	Czechia	Quality maintenance including EQA, verifying some samples and ad hoc advices
3	Denmark	NIPH calls for meetings with the local labs, manages, maintains and further develops the National Microbiology Database as the backbone of lab-based surveillance, validates data.
4	Finland	Provide training, NIPH can be contacted and assistance can be asked
5	France	Depends on the disease
6	Germany	Provision of an electronic system for data submission and support in its applicability
7	Ireland	National CIDR team assist with setting up local labs with access the database. HCAI team have SQL database with access by labs. There us helpdesk support and a national user group
8	Lithuania	record other's laboratories data which don't have direct login to the surveillance system
9	Malta	Not applicable as only one main general lab and hospital in Malta with which IDCU has direct communication
10	Netherlands	Set up of sequencing in Caribbean part of NL.
11	Poland	For some diseases NIPH provides possibility of performing broaden/additional/confirmational lab. diagnostics
12	Portugal	The NIPH provide regular or on demand training webinars and have a servicedesk email to help all sort of problems. If some incoherence is detected in introducing data the NIPH try

		to understand the problem and fix reaching out the local laboratories. The NIPH also developed a webservice to facilitate the interoperability between laboratory systems and surveillance systems.
13	Romania	to Public Health Authorities
14	Slovenia	When implementing a digital reporting system for covid-19, NIPH prepared a data model for electronic reporting of confirmed cases, where we determined a set of variables and code books.
15	Spain	We advise them scientifically (lab technics, EQA) and with data management.

Section 21.1. Where do local laboratories report lab surveillance data to in first instance, if not directly to the NIPH? Please provide any additional comments about how lab surveillance data are reported to the national level, in particular if they are reported indirectly:

Number	Country	Answer
1	Austria	Influenza: sentinel and non sentinel system operated at NRL (Not at NIPH)
2	Denmark	SARS-CoV-2: local labs send sequences or primary samples to SSI for analysis and the accompanying information is not standardized TB: nation-wide surveillance conducted since 1992; local labs send primary samples directly to SSI upon a TB suspicion, which then conducts primary diagnostics and resistance testing Enteric pathogens: Physicians send specimens from suspected cases to one of the ten clinical microbiology laboratories. A copy of the results of the diagnostic analysis from regional clinical microbiology laboratory is transmitted to an automatically updated national microbiology database of test results (MiBa). All cases of infections with <i>Campylobacter coli/jejuni</i> , <i>Salmonella enterica</i> , <i>Clostridium difficile</i> and <i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> are extracted from MiBa. MiBa contains unstructured data which is then further processed and to which case definitions are applied by the NIPH for the national surveillance. STEC and <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> are reported to the NIPH directly from the clinical microbiology laboratories via e-mail attachments.
3	France	Regional Health Agency are also informed for diseases with mandatory notification.
4	Germany	Indirectly reported data are reported by name to local health authorities and forwarded pseudonymised to NIPH, directly reported data are notified pseudonymised.
5	Ireland	While the legislation provides for reporting to the regional medical officer of health in the first instance, they are legally required to report nationally. Both national and regional agencies share the same database with different customised views which contains the data for 80 of the 89 notifiable diseases. Typing data are sometimes stored within the same database, but more often stored separately, and collated together during data analyses.
6	Italy	Italian Regions have different organization: so, some regions have a collection database and then they transmit to NIPH, other regions prefer that local labs send data directly to NIPH.
7	Latvia	Laboratories can send samples to the NRL and then NIPH receive subtyping results from NRL. There are important pathogens that need subtyping and if local laboratory can't perform this testing, they send samples to the NRL.
8	Malta	In Malta we have one main government general hospital (Mater Dei Hospital) and clinical laboratory that caters for all the country. IDCU has access to the test result platform of the hospital and positive infectious disease test results are downloaded daily and investigated. IDCU also receives notifications from private hospitals and physicians in the community. Surveillance for healthcare-associated pathogens is carried out primarily by the Infectious Disease Control Unit at Mater Dei Hospital.

9	Netherlands	Influenza als reported to separate part of NIC.
10	Norway	<p>The MSIS data registry is located at NIPH, whereas NRL for the different pathogen are located at NIPH or at another laboratory in the country. Data from local laboratories is reported to MSIS and samples submitted to NRLs. Outbreaks are reported by clinicians in a separate reporting system (Vesuv).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The local laboratories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Report data on positive results of notifiable diseases to the National Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases (MSIS) o Report all test results to the National Laboratory Database (MSIS-lab) o Submit sample/material to the National Reference Laboratory if assigned • The National Reference Laboratories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Report pathogen characterisation results to MSIS
11	Poland	When it comes to lab diagnostics we have different institutions dedicated to different pathogens, and those would be institutions mostly outside NIPH. Our surveillance system is primarily case- based, and laboratory results are only a part of it, and lab diagnostics is done by other institutions e.g. such as hospital labs, (which report results for certain disease to State Sanitary Inpsection), State Sanitary Inspection labs etc. Even when it comes to laboratories that test samples from entire country a division exists for being pathogen/ disease specific, and those are placed mostly outside the NIPH-NIH- for example: clinical samples from Listeria CNS infections, AMR are tested in National Medicine Institute Labs, for MDR TB in Institute for TB and Lung Diseases etc.
12	Portugal	The informatic system informs the local, regional and national authorities at same time.
13	Slovenia	<p>All communicable diseases on the list are reported directly to the NIPH, except for Tuberculosis.</p> <p>For Tuberculosis (TBC) we have one institution in Slovenia (the University Clinic Golnik) that covers treatments of TBC patients, contact tracing and management, as well as laboratory diagnostics and all the recommendations that are needed to prevent the spread of TBC. They are also maintaining the national TBC registry and report all the relevant data to Tessa, ECDC.</p> <p>Tuberculosis cases are not reported to the NIPH.</p>
14	Sweden	All reports goes to both NIPH and regional public health authority since we both own and work in the system used for mandatory reporting (SmiNet).

Section 22.1. In what format do local laboratories report the lab surveillance data to the organisation of question 21? Check all options that apply. *If Other, please describe which. Additional comments can be added as well:*

Number	Country	Answer
1	Belgium	We cannot speak for all NRC, but mostly they work with pdf forms (see https://www.sciensano.be/nl/nationale-referentiecentra-voor-humane-microbiologie#nrc_nrl-block_1-1) that need to be filled in (paper) and sent with the sample/isolate. It is then manually entered into their LIMS system. From the LIMS it can be extracted and send to NIPH via web-upload, SFTP. S2S upload is in development for test results from primary laboratories to the NIPH.
2	Denmark	Machine to machine upload: National Microbiology Database Streptococcus pneumoniae: in the process of transitioning from paper-based reporting to

		electronic reporting (this is not the National Microbiology Database) approximately within the next 6-12 months
3	Finland	Phone. Paper format is used when lab surveillance includes sample referral to the reference laboratory. Sample referral is provided by paper format together with sample.
4	France	Depends on the disease and the corresponding National Reference Center
5	Ireland	sometimes shared by sharefile rather than email
6	Latvia	N.B. We receive special form (paper form or forms sent by email) according to legislation of notification about infectious diseases.
7	Malta	IDCU has access to the main hospital lab data platform from which data from selected variables can be extracted in CSV format. Private laboratories notify IDCU by email or through online notification portal
8	Netherlands	Neisseria meningitidis and Streptococcus pneumoniae: only AMR reporting
9	Norway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local laboratories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Report machine to machine to the National Surveillance System (MSIS) o Report machine to machine to the National Laboratory Database (MSIS-lab) o Submit paper-based metadata with sample/material to the National Reference Laboratory • National reference laboratories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Report machine to machine to MSIS
10	Slovenia	C/CRE, CRAB, MRSA – an excel file is uploaded to a USB stick by the lab and then sent to the NIPH by post N. meningitides – invasive infection present an epidemiological emergency in Slovenia, hence epi investigation and contact tracing have to be performed immediately after receiving notification of a positive case. This is why cases of N. meningitides are initially reported by phone to the regional epidemiology unit at NIPH.

Section 23.1. How timely does the NIPH receive lab surveillance data for the majority (>90%) of the samples after the laboratory has it stored in their systems, for the following pathogens? *Please provide any additional comments, including if there are substantial differences in timeliness between diseases:*

Number	Country	Answer
1	Austria	n.a.
2	Belgium	Data from the NRC towards NIPH - service of Epidemiology for reporting mostly occurs every 3 months/annual frequency.
3	Czechia	Data from laboratory part of surveillance are reported without any unnecessary delay from lab to Regional Public Health Authority who enters the information into electronic national information system of infectious disease from which the information is available for NIPH. In addition, there might be direct communication between local lab and NRL and between NRL and EPI, especially in urgent situations.
4	Denmark	Legionella: data follows the sample; NIPH cannot access data until clinical notification or sample has been received; not all samples are sent to NIPH; all positive results from local labs visible in National Microbiology Database for NIPH; in the future, all positive samples will be sent to NIPH based on the new executive order on notifiable diseases; currently sending samples is on a voluntary basis, but all samples should currently be sent if Legionnaires Disease (pneumonia) is suspected as this is notifiable; New executive order: if PCR positive and local labs don't culture, then they should send to NIPH; multidrug-resistant TB: primary diagnostics and further typing done at NIPH West Nile Virus: NIPH does diagnostics themselves; local labs send samples to NIPH; STEC: anything between 1 week to 1 year; very different between local laboratories;

		HIV: all data available at the end of the year/ early beginning of the next year (corona years not representative)
5	Finland	Laboratory surveillance results consist of analysis results provided by both clinical laboratories and reference laboratory. Clinical laboratories usually notify diagnostic test results to the national infectious disease register within one week. If sample referral is needed, posting of samples and analysis in the reference laboratory requires more time. The time needed varies. When the result is stored in reference laboratory LIMS, it is transferred to the national infectious disease register over night.
6	France	Depends on the disease and the corresponding National Reference Center
7	Ireland	the legislation specifies the same week except for key same day pathogens to be reported locally on same day. There can be longer delays for more detailed typing and sequencing results
8	Italy	For drug resistant tuberculosis: the reporting is annual from local laboratories. For some surveillance diagnostic results are reported contextually to case data in an online platform by regional authorities. Timeliness can be assessed based on date of reporting or date of onset but no on date of sample access to a laboratory.
9	Latvia	There is a regulated interval between laboratory investigation and reporting, which specifies the number of days within which reporting must occur. However, with Covid-19 reporting being done by machine-to-machine communication, the process is faster and more efficient, allowing for more timely reporting of results.
10	Luxembourg	most labs send results several times a day
11	Malta	IDCU has access to the main hospital lab data platform from which data from selected variables can be extracted in CSV format. Positive test results are downloaded daily and cases contacted and investigated. For diseases in which urgent PH action is needed (ex neisseria meningitidis), microbiologists from the main laboratory alert us as soon as a positive result is out. Surveillance for healthcare-associated pathogens is carried out primarily by the Infectious Disease Control Unit at Mater Dei Hospital.
12	Netherlands	HAV: max 1 day delay reporting to local public health authority, then max 3 days delay reporting to NIPH
13	Norway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local laboratories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Report in real time to the National Laboratory Database (MSIS-lab) o Report in real time to the to the National Surveillance System (MSIS) o Submit samples with max 1 day delay to the National Reference Laboratory • National reference laboratory: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Report with max 2 weeks delay to MSIS (i.e the time from reception of sample to the completion of pathogen characterisation)
14	Portugal	It is mandatory to report within 24h of lab result but in some situations this time is not always followed.
15	Slovenia	CRE, CRAB, MRSA – data is provided on a yearly basis. N. meningitidis, S. pneumonia – data from lab is additionally provided (besides the initial notification) to the NIPH on a monthly basis for a double check. Legionella – the NIPH receives additional data (besides the initial notification) for the cases on a yearly basis. These data include isolate typing. Antibiotic-resistant Neisseria gonorrhoea and HIV transmitted drug resistance - data is provided on a yearly basis.
16	Spain	It is difficult to answer because traditional reporting is changing into a more efficient capture of data through health electronic records. So there is not, at regional level, a clear

		reporting period, except for those diseases defined as urgent. For the national reporting to the NIPH, the urgent criteria is maintained (in general) and weekly (for the majority or the diseases) or biannual (HIV infections) or annual (tetanus).
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Section 24.1. Does the NIPH store (parts of) the lab surveillance data in the cloud? *If Yes, please describe how or why data is (not) stored in the cloud and if possible which provider you use:*

Number	Country	Answer
1	Belgium	No, but we are working on a cloud based solution within EU to integrate sequencing data (BE-HERA-WGS project)
2	Denmark	legal constraints/ data security reasons
3	Lithuania	Physical servers were virtualized to VMware based governmental IT infrastructure provider "Information Society Development Committee" with cloud storage capabilities
4	Norway	• Data submitted to The European Surveillance System (TESSy)

Section 25.1. Does the NIPH routinely report any data back to the local laboratories? *If yes, what results does the NIPH report back to the local laboratories?*

Number	Country	Answer
1	Belgium	results of further subtyping/AMR.
2	Croatia	Enteropathogenic Escherichia coli (EPEC)
3	Czechia	NRL report back the confirmation results.
4	Denmark	Regular disease/pathogen specific updates/ short reports are distributed via mailing list; routine reports on diseases/pathogens at least once a year; NIPH website displays surveillance data in interactive interface called "Numbers and graphs"
5	Finland	Depending on microbes: species confirmation, typing results, antimicrobial susceptibility/resistance results
6	France	Depends on the disease, individual results or aggregated data analysis and interpretation.
7	Ireland	routine reports published on national institute website, also formal and informal updates for cluster investigations and upsurge management
8	Italy	In general report with analysis on aggregated data. Moreover information from both classical and genomic characterization of the clinical strains: serogroup, serotype, antibiotic susceptibility test, Sequence Type, cgMLST cluster, etc.
9	Lithuania	The annual reports are provided without the possibility to indicate the laboratory
10	Luxembourg	NIPH report back Flu to NRL, NRL report SARS-CoV-2 variants to local lab and hospitals
11	Norway	• For National Reference Laboratories located at NIPH, confirmatory results and pathogen dependent characterisation results are reported back to the local laboratories
12	Poland	As indicated in question 20 and 20.1 NIPH would send back the results to local state sanitary laboratories.
13	Romania	aetiology, AMR, serotype/serogroup
14	Slovenia	For the purpose of double checking for some pathogens (Streptococcus pneumoniae, Neisseria meningitidis, Listeria monocytogenes, STEC, ...) the NIPH and the labs harmonizes their databases.
15	Spain	The analysis of the surveillance data is published in the NIPH web (Enfermedades A-Z (isciii.es) or sent as epidemiologic reports to the Regions.
16	Sweden	Subtyping, cluster analysis

Section 26. If you have any documentation about your lab surveillance system available online, please share the link(s) here:

Number	Country	Answer
1	Belgium	<p>Sciensano's service Epidemiology of infectious diseases works continuously together with the laboratories via 2 main networks: the sentinel laboratories that send test results (since 1983) and the National Reference Centres that receive isolates from the peripheral laboratories (NRC, since 2011).</p> <p>Both networks are complementary with each other (but also with other monitoring systems) and send us information on diagnostic data on cases of a wide range of infectious diseases.</p> <p>Sentinel laboratories (Test results) https://www.sciensano.be/nl/netwerk-van-peillaboratoria-epilabo https://docs.healthdata.be/documentation/surveillance-infectious-diseases-sentinel-laboratories/general-epilabo-project https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27571203/ https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34706768/</p> <p>National Reference Centres (samples) https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22958353/</p> <p>Example of evaluation of coverage of both surveillance systems for Salmonella: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34437638/</p>
2	Estonia	https://www.terviseamet.ee/et/laborid/laborid/tallinna-labor-ja-nakkushaiguste-labor/kliinilised-analuusid (accompanying note)
3	Finland	https://thl.fi/en/web/infectious-diseases-and-vaccinations/surveillance-and-registers
4	France	A presentation that was made at a WHO meeting is available upon requests
5	Germany	https://simplifier.net/demis
6	Ireland	https://www.hpsc.ie/notifiablediseases/notifyinginfectiousdiseases/ and https://www.hpsc.ie/a-z/microbiologyantimicrobialresistance/antimicrobialresistancesurveillance/
7	Lithuania	https://registrai.lt/management/objects/view/10184 https://registrai.lt/management/objects/view/10429
8	Netherlands	https://www.rivm.nl/bibliotheek/rapporten/2022-0253.pdf , chapter "Current situation"
9	Norway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.fhi.no/nettpub/veileder-for-mikrobiologiske-laboratorieanalyser/ • https://www.fhi.no/hn/helseregistre-og-registre/msis/elektronisk-laboratoriemelding-til-msis-og-laboratordatabasen/
10	Slovenia	no

Section 27.1. Does the NIPH have stable funding source(s) to maintain lab surveillance systems? This does not include funding of local laboratories, which is addressed in the next questions. *Please provide details:*

Number	Country	Answer
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1	Belgium	There is less and less sustainable funding available at national level (from ministries). Therefore other funding becomes very important for to develop and maintain laboratory based surveillance systems (eg. BE-HERA project https://www.sciensano.be/en/projects/national-infrastructure-genomic-epidemiologic-surveillance-infectious-diseases , EU-HIP project https://www.sciensano.be/nl/projecten/interoperabiliteit-van-de-eu-met-het-it-platform-van-hera
2	Czechia	Routine work of NIPH including NRLs is mainly financed from MoH budget
3	Denmark	The Covid-19 pandemic bolstered funding for surveillance in general; future funding situation unclear
4	Finland	Yearly budget for all activity, including surveillance but not specific to surveillance. There has been no major reductions to the budget during recent years.
5	Ireland	For CIDR (main notifiable disease database), maintenance contract, some specific funding for SQL databases, especially in relation to COVID and other respiratory viruses
6	Lithuania	The CD and its agents state information system is currently being modernized
7	Portugal	The national lab surveillance informatic system has direct funding from state budget. The NRL only have public funding for human resources directly to the state budget.
8	Romania	public health programs, projects
9	Slovenia	The NIPH uses some data for surveillance that are generated during patient care (data from microbiological tests that are necessary for direct patient care). Funding for this is provided by the Health Insurance Institute Slovenia (HIIS) directly health care providers who are paying for the tests to the labs. The NIPH receives some funds from HIIS for maintenance of the national registers and databases in the area of communicable diseases. The NIPH is also funded by the Ministry of Health (MoH) who provided special funding for COVID-19 surveillance (testing, waste water surveillance, sequencing of SARS-CoV-2,.....).

Section 30.1. *Please provide additional details on how local laboratories are compensated:*

Number	Country	Answer
1	Belgium	There is no important compensation, it is mostly on voluntary basis. Some compensation may happen ad-hoc for specific research projects.
2	Denmark	ad 28) if it concerns a notifiable disease for which it is mandatory for local labs to send in isolates to the NIPH, local labs can request compensation ad 29) sometimes additional funds are available, e.g. when tests are free to take for the public, but still requires (human) resources at the local lab for packaging etc.
3	Ireland	(1) Payment to labs for residual samples submitted for serosurveillance unit, (2) ECDC funding for COVID WGS equipment, etc, (3) routine testing of contacts would be paid for from public purse.
4	Latvia	Local laboratories are required to send certain samples to the National Reference Laboratory (NRL), and all related expenses are covered by the fees established in the government's price list. Payment for these services is made in accordance with the procedures specified by the government.
5	Malta	The main clinical lab at the government general hospital (Mater Dei Hospital) is funded by public funds. Laboratories and clinicians are legally obliged to notify Public Health of infectious diseases on the notifiable diseases list.

		https://deputyprimeminister.gov.mt/en/health-promotion/idpcu/Pages/notifiablediseases.aspx
6	Netherlands	Only SARS-CoV-2
7	Norway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compensation for local laboratories is regulated by the "Regulation on benefits to cover expenses for examination and treatment in private medical laboratory and X-ray". All laboratory analyses for which reimbursement is required must be documented. This means that the laboratory activity defined by NLK (Norwegian Laboratory Codes) for outpatients must be able to be documented in relevant laboratory information systems.
8	Portugal	No compensation is in place to local laboratories.
9	Romania	public health programs resources, projects
10	Slovenia	<p>The labs are mainly funded directly from the client (healthcare provider), who can then be reimbursed from HIIS, for some of the microbiological tests.</p> <p>The NIPH is funded by the HIIS for some lab surveillance purposes that are not directly needed for the patient management and/or treatment, however they are needed for detailed surveillance (e.g. serotyping, genotyping, AMR...). The labs are subsequently funded by the NIPH for the performing those analyses.</p>
11	Spain	If the samples are associated to outbreak or lab surveillance, they do not have to pay for processed it

Annex 4. Template of the survey “Needs and gaps analysis on automated outbreak detection tools for routine surveillance data” conducted under Task 2

Needs and gaps analysis on automated outbreak detection tools for routine surveillance data

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

Introduction

This survey is conducted within the Joint Action “United4Surveillance” as part of work package 2, task 2 on “Outbreak detection”.

Overall, this task focuses on improving algorithms for automated outbreak detection using routine surveillance data of infectious diseases. Benefits of introducing early outbreak detection tools include earlier detection of outbreaks, the detection of outbreaks that would not have been detected otherwise and thus reducing the further spread and harmful consequences. Yet, automated outbreak detection is only applied for a few of the available surveillance data streams, pathogens or pathogen groups.

This survey **aims** to get an overview of types of surveillance systems and automated outbreak detection methods currently used by EU/EEA member states and to identify gaps and needs for automated tools detecting outbreaks from routine surveillance data. The survey consists of two parts:

1. Public health surveillance system
2. Automated outbreak detection tools

Results will be used to identify common use cases for automated outbreak detection and guide the further development and deployment of tools in the European context.

Instructions

This survey is sent to selected focal points of countries that are part of the consortium of the Joint Action “United4Surveillance”.

- **Focal points are responsible for coordinating** the responses for their country and filling in the survey by **05.05.2023**.
- We encourage to fill out only one survey for each country (EU/EEA member states). If this is not feasible in your context please contact us.
- In case the survey needs to be completed by more than one expert (e.g. epidemiologist and data scientist), we strongly recommend that the focal point fills in the survey with the support of relevant national experts online.
- If you want to save your answers and return to them at a later time, please click on the right top button ‘save as draft’. **Please make sure to save the shown link.**
- Please use Internet Explorer, Mozilla Firefox or Google Chrome to fill out this survey. Using other browsers might cause compatibility problems.
- Once you have finished the survey, please click on ‘Submit’. You can save or print your contribution.
- The survey is also sent to the ECDC NFP Surveillance for information, awareness and facilitation if necessary.
- FAQ for participants on the use of the EU Survey Platform: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/home/helpparticipants>
- For questions about the survey itself and/or content of the survey, please contact vom-FeldeP@rki.de

Data privacy

This survey collects information from focal points of the Joint Action “United4Surveillance”. The name and e-mail address of the participants were provided by the contacted individuals themselves and therefore are already known within the consortium of the Joint Action “United4Surveillance”. Survey results will be evaluated on a country level and no individual personal information will be used.

I have read and understand the above data privacy statement and I consent to participate in this survey.

Terminology

For a common understanding, the following terms used in the survey are explained below.

Automated outbreak detection is the process of comparing the current epidemiological situation to a baseline (usually based on historic and/or geographic data) using some form of outlier detection. It processes surveillance data in a way that demographic and geographic characteristics are considered. The detected outliers or signals are usually summarised in a table or descriptive report.

Case-based vs. aggregated data: Case-based data is surveillance data that is collected and processed in a way that each entry represents one case or report of an infection or disease event, whereas aggregated data summarizes the number of cases or reports in groups, e.g. by regions, age groups or other demographic information.

Historic data are surveillance data that were collected by the same surveillance system which will be used for the automated outbreak detection and that can be used to estimate a baseline against which the current surveillance data can be compared. These data may have to be adjusted for trends or shifts.

Library: A library for automated outbreak detection is a repository of programming code that provides functions for detecting signals (outbreak warnings) in surveillance data and possibly further functionality for reporting these results.

Tool/software: A software or tool for automated outbreak detection that takes surveillance data as input and provides the resulting outbreak warnings in the form of an automatically generated report or summary table. We will use the term “tool” for this survey.

Warning/Signal: A warning or signal is an outlier in a subset (e.g., a region or age group) of the surveillance data. An outlier is an anomalous number of cases or reports compared to a historic or geographic baseline. We will use the term “signal” for this survey.

General aspects

* Which country are you reporting for?

- AT - Austria
- BE - Belgium
- CY - Cyprus
- CZ - Czech Republic
- DE - Germany
- DK - Denmark
- EE - Estonia
- ES - Spain
- FI - Finland
- FR - France
- HR - Croatia
- HU - Hungary
- IE - Ireland
- IT - Italy
- LT - Lithuania
- LU - Luxembourg
- LV - Latvia
- MT - Malta
- NL - Netherlands
- NO - Norway
- PL - Poland
- PT - Portugal

- RO - Romania
- SE - Sweden
- SI - Slovenia

* Which organization do your work for?

- National Public Health Institute /National Public Health Authority
- Ministry of Health
- Other

If other, please specify.

Part 1: Public health surveillance system

We assume that in many EU/EEA member states several public health surveillance systems (e.g. mortality, pathogens, communicable diseases) exist. As it would be too extensive to assess every single surveillance system, we ask you to **choose one of your national public health surveillance systems**, for which an automated outbreak detection tool is already in place or which would be most suitable for automated outbreak detection tools in order to complete this survey.

Please complete the questions **only for the chosen surveillance system**.

* Thereby, the surveillance system can be one of three options. Please indicate which option applies to your chosen surveillance system.

- Surveillance system with existing automated outbreak detection tool/s
- Surveillance system with planned implementation of automated outbreak detection tool/s
- Surveillance system with no automated outbreak detection tool planned or in place, but where such tool/s would provide potential benefit

* What is the official name (full name and acronym) of the surveillance system?

* Approximately in what year was the system established?

The following questions only refer to the chosen national surveillance system you indicated above.

* Which type of surveillance system is it? Please choose multiple options if they are included in the surveillance system.

- Syndromic surveillance system
- Laboratory-based surveillance system
- Hospital-based surveillance system
- GP-based/ Primary care-based surveillance system

- Sentinel surveillance system
- Primary care-based surveillance
- Molecular-based surveillance system
- Event-based surveillance system

* Are the types of surveillance systems mandatory by law or voluntarily?

- Mandatory by law
- Voluntarily
- Not applicable
- Other

If other, please specify.

For which disease group is the surveillance system designed?

	Yes	No	Unknown
* Air-borne diseases (i.e. COVID-19)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Antimicrobial resistance (AMR)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Blood-borne diseases/ STI's (i.e. HIV)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Food- and water-borne diseases (i.e. Norovirus)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Healthcare-associated infections (i.e. Ventilator-associated Pneumonia)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Vector-borne diseases (i.e. Dengue fever)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Zoonotic diseases (i.e. Brucellosis)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If other, please specify.

* Please indicate the source of the data, meaning the institution or entity generating the data which are reported to the (local) public health authorities (i.e. nuclei acid detection (i.e. PCR) of brucellosis in the laboratory and subsequent notification to the local health authority).

- Laboratories
- Hospital/medical personnel
- General Practitioner/primary care
- Blood bank
- Kindergarten/schools
- Care facilities/nursing homes
- Community
- Unknown
- Other

If other, please specify.

* What is the frequency of data reported to the national level?

- Daily
- Weekly
- Monthly
- Unknown
- Other

If other, please specify.

* How is data reported to your national level?

- Case-based
- Aggregated
- Unknown
- Other

If other, please specify.

If case-based, what information is available at national level?

- Anonymous information
- Pseudonymized information
- Personal identifiable data available
- Unknown
- Other

If case-based, please specify.

* Which information is reported routinely to the national level?

- Pathogen
- Disease
- Symptoms
- Date of symptoms onset
- Hospitalisation
- Possible exposure (e.g. epi-link)
- Risk factors
- Age
- Sex

- Geographical information (address/region)
- Laboratory method
- Date of laboratory confirmation
- Molecular and genomic typing
- Date of clinical diagnosis
- Vaccination status
- Death
- Unknown
- Other

If other, please specify.

* What is the geographical resolution of your data?

- Address
- District/neighbourhood
- Village/city
- County/province
- Region/state
- National/country
- Unknown
- Other

If other, please specify.

* How many years of historic data do you have electronically stored up to this point?

* Please briefly describe in a few sentences the most relevant features of the chosen surveillance system.

Part 2: Automated outbreak detection tools

The section "Resources for automated outbreak detection tool" should also be answered if your above described surveillance system does not have automated outbreak detection tools yet or is planning to implement them.

Resources for automated outbreak detection tools

Please answer the following three questions based on the resources that are currently available or can be made available for a foreseen future to implement automated outbreak detection tools.

How would you rate the availability for each of the following resources for running an automated outbreak detection tool for your surveillance system at this moment?

Please indicate from not available (1 star) to fully available (5 stars).

Overall funding	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Funding for personnel	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Funding for IT resources (hardware/ software)	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Funding for research	★ ★ ★ ★ ★

How would you rate the available IT competences to implement the automated outbreak detection tool at this moment?

Please indicate from not available (1 star) to fully available (5 stars).

Implementation/ Initial setup (Research Software Engineering)	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Maintenance/ Automatization (IT Support)	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Research/Development/Extension (Data Science Research)	★ ★ ★ ★ ★

* Which main challenges do you currently have or anticipate to have when developing and implementing an automated outbreak detection tool?

- Data quality issues
- Legal mandate issues
- Sustainable funding/resources
- None
- Unknown
- Other

If other, please specify.

If you have or anticipate to have challenges, please explain them briefly.

Signals and Outbreaks

The following section should be completed by everybody, regardless of whether you have chosen a surveillance system with or without automated outbreak detection tools.

Consider a situation where you have identified an anomalously high number of cases in your surveillance data that commends a signal and triggers public health actions such as verification and outbreak investigation. Please try to answer the following questions irrespective of these signals stemming from an outbreak detection tool or manual inspection.

* Are signals (i.e. from automated outbreak detection tools or manual analysis) followed by or trigger public health actions (i.e. investigation of an outbreak)?

- Yes
- No
- Unknown

If yes, please briefly describe the public health action.

* Is feedback required and given on the public health actions based on the signal?

- Yes
- No
- Unknown

If yes, please describe the form of feedback loop.

* Is the feedback (systematically) collected?

- Yes
- No
- Unknown

* Is the feedback used to evaluate the (automated) outbreak detection signals and the approach (such as tools or manual detection approach) in order to implement changes/improvements?

- Yes
- No
- Unknown

Automated outbreak detection tools

The following section should **only be filled in** in case you have a

- surveillance system with an outbreak detection tool/s

or

- surveillance system with planned implementation of outbreak detection tool/s

Please choose the most advanced and relevant tool used.

What type of tool are you using?

- External software (e.g. SATSCAN)
- Existing open library (e.g. surveillance)
- Self-implemented solution (e.g. R or Stata scripts)
- Unknown
- Other

If other, please specify.

If an external software or an existing library is used, please specify which one.

How complex/ difficult would you rate the use of the tool, i.e. regarding data pre-processing, parameter input, running, output generation?

- Complex/ difficult
- Neither difficult nor simple
- Simple
- Unknown

How demanding is the tool with respect to IT-resources, i.e. servers, memory, computing power, databases?

- Demanding
- Neither demanding nor simple
- Simple
- Unknown

What is the outcome (presentation/communication of the results) of the tool?

- Dashboard
- Situation Report
- List or table
- Excel or CSV file
- Unknown
- Other

If other, please specify.

What statistical method is used?

- Spatial Clustering
- Time Series Outlier
- Fixed Threshold
- Unknown
- Other

If other, please specify.

Is demographic information used for outbreak detection? (i.e. stratifying by age group)

- Yes
- No
- Unknown

How satisfied are you overall with the tool?

Please indicate from very dissatisfied (1 star) to very satisfied (5 stars)	
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Are the generated signals (outbreak warnings) timely enough?

- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Unknown

Are the generated signals (outbreak warnings) precise (regional, demographic, time) enough?

- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Unknown

Is the outbreak detection tool/ system too sensitive (i.e. too many generated signals are no true outbreaks)?

- Agree
- Neither agree or disagree
- Disagree
- Unknown

Please share your ideas how your tool can be improved.

Annex 5. Workshop Report – Workshop on outbreak detection use cases

Workshop Report

Workshop on
Outbreak Detection Use Cases

Work Package 2 Task 2: Outbreak & Signal Detection

30 - 31 May 2023
Berlin, Germany

TABLE OF CONTENT

TABLE OF CONTENT	2
1. INTRODUCTION	3
2. WORKSHOP DESIGN	3
3. SUMMARY OF PRESENTATIONS AND DISCUSSION	4
4. EVALUATION	6
5. RECOMMENDATIONS AND NEXT STEPS	7
6. CONCLUSION	8
7. ACKNOWLEDGMENT	8
8. LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS/GLOSSARY	8
ANNEX 1. WORKSHOP AGENDA	9
ANNEX 2. LIST OF PARTICIPANTS	10
ANNEX 3. PINBOARDS COUNTRY PRESENTATIONS	13
ANNEX 4. POSTERS OUTBREAK DETECTION TOOL	14
ANNEX 5. FLIPCHARTS EVALUATION OF PILOTS	18
ANNEX 6. MENTIMETER RESULTS	21

1. Introduction

The workshop on outbreak detection use cases took place under Work Package 2 Task 2 (WP2/T2) as part of the Joint Action (JA) Union and National Capacity Building 4 IntegraTED Surveillance (UNITED4Surveillance).

UNITED4Surveillance aims to strengthen infectious disease surveillance systems at the national and European level by providing capacity-building with improvement of integration, interoperability, and digitalization of data sources. The JA will develop a roadmap to implement an integrated surveillance system for effective disease surveillance at member state and Union level.

The JA is funded under the EU4Health programme, which was adopted as a response to the COVID-19 pandemic. On the national level, epidemiological data on COVID-19 that has been shared with the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) was often delayed, not comparable between Member States (MS) and lacking information. The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the urgent need to develop and sustain resilient population-based integrated surveillance systems and for improvement in public health preparedness and pandemic response at the European level. One of the major lessons learnt from this pandemic is that there is a need for integrated, real time disease surveillance systems to enable early detection and effective response.

Early detection of infectious disease outbreaks can help reduce the further spread and reduce harmful consequences. The goal of automated outbreak detection tools is to foster automated data analysis and identify specific events of concern. This is especially useful in the context of growing availability of surveillance data and limited human resources. WP2/T2 aims to develop and deploy tools for the timely and accurate detection of outbreak in surveillance data and thus to increase the capacity of MS running an automated early warning system.

In collaboration with the Department of Data Integration & Analysis at the Statens Serum Institute (Denmark), the surveillance unit at the RKI is leading the work package for automated outbreak detection, with a focus for the RKI's work on automated signal detection based on infectious disease surveillance data.

In line with the foreseen tasks the workshop's objectives were to:

- 1) meet active partners and other interested participants
- 2) review existing outbreak detection systems and discuss gaps and needs,
- 3) identify relevant use cases for outbreak detection and
- 4) discuss next steps and the pilot phase.

1. Workshop Design

The workshop on outbreak detection use cases was held on 30 and 31 May 2023 at the RKI in Berlin. The event was attended by 30 participants from national public health institutes of 16 countries including Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal and Slovenia (see Annex 2). It brought together a diverse group of experts and gathered expertise in public health, epidemiology and data-science.

Throughout the workshop, the integration of automated outbreak detection tools into national surveillance systems within the EU was discussed. Designed to address the workshop's objectives, the agenda, outlined in detail in Annex 1, included a series of presentations, panel discussions and breakout sessions. Building upon the experiences and expertise shared through country presentations and discussions during the first day, the second day was designed to foster greater interactivity and to delve deeper into the upcoming piloting phase and tool development. Additionally, participants had the opportunity to network and connect with fellow professionals during a joint dinner and a visit of the RKI museum.

Figure 1. Group picture of the workshop participants

The workshop was organized and hosted by the WP2/ T2 lead, the surveillance unit at the Robert Koch-Institute (RKI). All WP2/T2 active partners were requested to attend in person. Piloting countries and tool development countries were asked to prepare a presentation on piloting aim and automated outbreak detection methods. The entire consortium of the JA was invited to participate in the workshop in person or online, if interested. Due to limited capacities participation was limited to two persons per institution. Online sessions were offered for the first four presentations on the first day. Prior to the workshop one meeting with active partner institutions took place to prepare and exchange expectations. In April 2023 the "needs and gaps analysis on automated outbreak detection tools for routine surveillance data" was conducted among the participating countries in the JA and the workshop was used to discuss and assess the results of the survey.

2. Summary of Presentations and Discussion

The workshop was inaugurated by Dr Ute Rexroth, deputy head of the Department of Infectious Disease Epidemiology at RKI, who gave an introduction to the RKI and work of the department with an emphasis on surveillance systems and automated outbreak detection. She elucidated that the Department of Infectious Disease Epidemiology is responsible for the collection, analysis and epidemiological assessment of data communicated to the RKI according to the national infection protection act and that the German surveillance systems is a single-case-based electronic notification system including over 60 pathogens and 20 diseases under surveillance. She emphasized the importance of having an automated outbreak detection system, which has been implemented at the RKI since 2016. The generated weekly reports are used by experts to detect possible outbreaks of various pathogen timely and to initiate investigations at local health authorities. During the COVID-19 pandemic analytics, reports and dashboards were provided for the timely assessment of the pandemic.

The first session of the workshop started with a presentation on the foreseen work under WP2/T2. Aiming to increase the capacity of member states (MS) of running an automated outbreak detection, the activities are carried out by four subtasks from 2023 to 2024: Review of outbreak detection activities, benchmarking of outbreak detection methods, tool development and piloting and training. Beginning of 2024 the tools will be available and provided to the pilot countries for implementation into national surveillance systems. The experiences and evaluation of the pilots will be compiled into a final report that will form the main deliverable of task 2.

Beyond the activities of the JA, Auss Abbood informed about the Topic Group “Outbreaks” under the Focus Group AI for Health (FG-AI4H), an initiative of the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) and the World Health Organization (WHO). The TG Outbreaks addresses the benchmarking of outbreak detection algorithms. Abbood highlighted that AI algorithms can increase the timeliness and accuracy of outbreak detection, and further have the potential to improve an understanding of the warnings and the disease spread itself. Different syndromic surveillance systems and valuable external data sources (google trends, health apps) can be incorporated. The gain of additional information on the underlying causes, by using explainable AI approaches, further enables for more specific actions to be taken for prevention. The presentation was well-received and garnered positive feedback from participants.

The results of the survey on existing and planned automated outbreak detection were presented and complemented by country presentations and panel discussions aiming to (i) gather information about the types of surveillance systems with existing automated outbreak detection including methods or surveillance systems with a potential for implementation and (ii) to identify gaps and needs for automated outbreak detection tools from routine surveillance data of infectious disease. Out of the 25 countries invited to take part in the survey, 21 countries responded, whereof only Germany and Finland stated to have an active automated outbreak detection system in place and ten countries indicated to plan the implementation of tools. During the presentations, participants were asked to note down similarities and differences (see Annex 3). Across all countries, the surveillance systems are mainly lab-, hospital- and GP-based with daily and case based reporting. All systems include additional information on cases and most have sufficient historic data available. A few countries reported to have many personal information including the address available at the national level. However, during the discussion it was revised that this information is only visible at lower level such as local or county.

Throughout the presentations, many similarities between the pilot countries were apparent, especially on the aim and how and what kind of data is collected and often based on similar registries. In response to the growing availability of surveillance data, all countries aim to implement automated outbreak detection methods to strengthening surveillance systems, enable a timelier detection of potential outbreaks and to compensate for staff shortages. For instance, more and more pathogens with whole-genome sequencing (WGS)-surveillance are available in the Netherlands emphasizing the necessity for automated outbreak detection. It is also evident that countries react on signals, whether generated manually or automated and initiate investigation when needed. Yet, systematic reporting and evaluation is missing in all countries. While there are a lot of similarities among surveillance data, the presentations displayed the heterogeneity of the national surveillance systems placed in different organizational structures and population sizes as well as a quite diverse set of different use cases. Additionally, deviating from legislative requirements, cases are often reported with a delay in time and at varying speeds across countries.

Tool development countries gave a brief overview on different algorithms and approaches used for outbreak detection. Germany and Finland have established an automated outbreak detection system. Austria and Denmark have a surveillance system with planned implementation of automated outbreak detection tools. Tools are mostly self-implemented scripts and some established statistical methods like SATSCAN, the MEM-method or methods provided in the surveillance R-package providing potential for making methods usable for others. Currently, dashboards, lists, tables and SitReps are used indicating the need for flexible outputs. The participants agreed on the importance of considering the different users of the tool during the development phase. Yet, evaluation of the tools is much up to discussion and outbreak detection system are currently not being systematically evaluated.

During the ensuing discussion, funding and IT resources were the main challenges identified for the piloting countries when developing and implementing automated outbreak detection tools. Maintenance and running the system once it has been implemented are considered to be more feasible. Piloting countries stressed the lack of qualified IT personnel being available and addressed the need for support. It was argued from the tool development side that without being on the system and having knowledge of the IT systems, technical support would be challenging. The tool and methods countries have, however, promised to help in case of issues with the actual tool and site visits are considered if needed. Additionally, a few participants would prefer to do it themselves with assistance. Arising from the discussion on data sharing between pilot and tool countries, a defined minimum set of variables shall be provided by tool countries.

Discussion among the tool countries, evolved around the questions how to define an outbreak, when to give a signal and how to prioritize signals. Often a limited number of outbreaks can be managed due to personal shortage. Ireland and the Netherlands use a defined set of questions when it would be reasonable to initiate an investigation. As the guidelines are highly qualitative, it was questioned how these could be adopted into an algorithm. Nonetheless, binary questions would be feasible to implement. A few participants mentioned WGS surveillance as an emerging method that can enhance outbreak detection and integration with epidemiological data and thus should be considered for automated outbreak detection.

On the second day, participants engaged in breakout sessions. Piloting countries worked on “what an ideal outbreak detection tool looks like” and tool countries focused on “outbreak detection tools we want to provide”. Results of the sessions were documented and presented in poster format (see Annex 4). Through the discussions and collaborative exercises with a transnational perspective, it became apparent that there are different needs and priorities in the piloting countries. Desired use cases for automated outbreak detection ranged from gastroenteritis to respiratory diseases. One group suggested that the tool should not only detect outbreak but also any change in variables like change of hospitalization rate leading to the question of defining a baseline for what the tool should actually do. The conversation unfolded with the question of how signals should be reported and whether a dashboard should display one disease group or several as well as differentiating between internal and external dashboards. Underlying issue of the discussion are that signals are managed by different experts in the countries with varying IT competences emphasizing the necessity of user-friendly, easy to use and adaptable tools. In the context of evaluating the pilot, a brainstorm session yielded several proposals, considering the specificity, sensitivity, timeliness, usefulness, satisfaction, ease of use of the tools and comparison to manually detected outbreaks, allowance for public health interventions (see Annex 5).

This is also reflected by the vision of the tool countries who aim to provide an effective solution for early detection of outbreaks and enable the monitoring of clusters. Thereby, case-based, routinely collected, historic and if possible, regional data should be the basis of the tool. The envisioned generated output data should be capable to be granulated by local level and be user-friendly for national level experts. Ideas of evaluating the tools also include sensitivity, specificity, timeliness and user feedback. In order to serve the needs of the pilot countries, it was expressed that these have to share surveillance and historic data.

3. Evaluation

Overall, the workshop on outbreak detection use cases was an informative and engaging event, which provided valuable perspectives and concepts for integrating automated outbreak detection tools into national surveillance systems within the EU. The workshop received positive feedback from participants, who found it very well organized and valuable. However, feedback also reflected the wish for a more concrete definition of next steps.

An evaluation form as part of work package 5 of the JA was answered by 16 workshop attendees. Organization, opportunities to participate, content of presentations and time for networking and contribution were very well-perceived. The usefulness of the meeting in terms of follow-up work and task in the WP2/T2 was only rated to be

average and it was mentioned that the next steps are not perfectly clear yet. Participants also provided suggestions for future workshops, such as a hybrid option for the entire event and a more steered work discussion.

In line with this feedback are also the Mentimeter results on “name three things that will make this work package successful” (Annex 6) which was conducted at the very end of the workshop. Participants highlighted the need for concrete tasks, close collaboration, common goals and to “keep it simple and focused”.

4. Recommendations and Next Steps

Drawing from the discussions and feedback received, the following recommendations and subsequent actions are defined:

To Pilot Countries

1. Decide on pathogen group/ syndrome for piloting automated outbreak detection tools
2. Provide description of pilot including
 - a. Aim
 - b. Pathogens/ Syndromes
 - c. Surveillance System
 - d. Relevant variables in surveillance data
3. Provide sample surveillance data
 - a. Use the provided data format
 - b. Ideally for the relevant pathogens/ syndromes
4. Provide sample outbreak data
 - a. Use the provided data format
 - b. Ideally for the same time and pathogens/ syndromes as surveillance data

To Tool/ Method Countries

1. Setting a data format for epi data
 - a. Define a list of basic variables that are necessary
 - b. Add variables that are relevant and might be common but not necessary
 - c. Define formats for each variable
 - d. Provide example data set
2. Setting a data format for outbreak data
 - a. Define the list of necessary variables
 - b. Define the format for the outbreak information (outbreak id + status)
 - c. Provide an example data set
3. Select methods for evaluation and tools
 - a. List of methods that are available in external R-library or R-script
 - b. List of methods that are available as unpublished R-code or implemented in other programming languages
 - c. List of methods that are peer-reviewed but not yet available as implemented R-code

To WP2/T2 lead (RKI)

1. Coordination of meetings and tasks
2. Suggesting concept for evaluation of pilots
3. Concept for tool evaluation
4. Concept for tool development
5. Suggestions of free online R-courses

5. Conclusion

Based on the experiences gained during the COVID-19 pandemic, the need to further develop automated outbreak algorithms beyond COVID-19 and their integration into existing surveillance systems and public health structures was endorsed by all workshop participants. National surveillance systems in pilot countries with sufficient historic data and expertise have the potential for implementing new automated outbreak detection methods. Moving forward, a close collaboration and engagement of both pilot and tool development countries is crucial to bring the tool together for a common format across institutes in different countries.

6. Acknowledgment

We would like to thank all participants who attended the workshop. Their active engagement, expertise and shared experiences greatly enriched the discussions and contributed to the success of the workshop.

7. List of abbreviations/glossary

ECDC	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
FG-AI4H	Focus Group AI for Health
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
JA	Joint Action
MS	Member States
RKI	Robert Koch-Institute
UNITED4Surveillance	Union and National Capacity Building 4 IntegraTED Surveillance
WGS	Whole-Genome Sequencing
WHO	World Health Organization
WP2/T2	Work Package 2 Task 2

Annex 1. Workshop agenda

Tuesday, 30 May 2023

09:00 **Arrival and coffee**

9:30 **Welcome & Introduction**

Ute Rexroth

Robert Koch-Institute

10:00 **Overview work package (Hybrid session)**

Paulina vom Felde

Robert Koch-Institute

10:15 **Presentation of survey results (Hybrid session)**

Alexander Ullrich

Robert Koch-Institute

10:45 **Presentation of outbreak detection within AI4Health (Hybrid session)**

Auss Abbood

Robert Koch-Institute

11:00 Coffee break

11:20 **Country presentations: Method/ tool development**

AGES (Austria); *SSI* (Denmark); *THL* (Finland); *RKI* (Germany)

12:25 **Plenary discussion**

12:45 Lunch & Group picture

14:00 **Country presentations: Pilot I**

THL (Finland); *NPHC* (Hungary); *MFH* (Malta)

15:00 **Plenary discussion**

15:15 Coffee break

15:45 **Country presentations: Pilot II**

NIH (Poland); *NIJZ* (Slovenia); *RIVM* (The Netherlands)

16:45 **Plenary discussion & Wrap up**

20:00 **Joint dinner**

Wednesday, 31 May 2023

8:30 **Arrival and coffee**

09:00 **Introduction day 2**
Robert Koch-Institute

09:15 **Breakout session**
Group 1: Method/ tool countries
Group 2: Pilot countries

11:15 Coffee break

11:30 **Plenary discussion**

12:00 Lunch

13:00 **Plenary discussion**
Way forward

14:00 **Wrap up**

15:00 **Visit of the RKI Museum**
Nordufer 20, 13353 Berlin
Barabara Gunsenheimer-Bartmeyer

Annex 2. List of participants

No	Name	Institution	Function
1	Aleksiene, Giedre	National Public Health Centre under the MoH (NVSC), Lithuania	Epidemiologist
2	Bach, Moritz	Robert Koch-Institut (RKI), Germany	Data scientist
3	Borg, Maria	Health Promotion and Disease Prevention Directorate (MFH), Malta	Public health medicine consultant
4	Chalupka, Alena	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES), Austria	Data scientist
5	Coipan, Claudia	Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu (RIVM), The Netherlands	Data scientist
6	Csizmadia, Péter	National Public Health Center (NPHC), Hungary	Project manager
7	Danielisz, Agnes	National Public Health Center (NPHC), Hungary	Epidemiologist
8	Diercke, Michaela	Robert Koch-Institut (RKI), Germany	Epidemiologist
9	Dockx, Yinthe	Sciensano, Belgium	Data scientist/ Epi
10	Friesema, Ingrid	Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu (RIVM), The Netherlands	Epidemiologist
11	Garvey, Patricia	Health Protection Surveillance Centre (HPSC), Ireland	Epidemiologist
12	Hicketier, Andreas	Robert Koch-Institut (RKI), Germany	Data scientist
13	Ivanko, Pero	Croatian Institute of Public Health (CIPH), Croatia	Data scientist
14	Juutinen, Aapo	Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL), Finland	Statistician
15	Kairiene, Brigita	National Public Health Centre under the MoH (NVSC), Lithuania	Adviser
16	Leite, Pedro	Ministério da Saúde - Direção-Geral da Saúde (MIN SAUDE), Portugal	Director of Services
17	Liskova, Ilona	The Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (CDPC), Latvia	Deputy Director Epidemiological Safety
18	Luomala, Oskari	Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL), Finland	Statistician
19	Markus, Inessa	Robert Koch-Institut (RKI), Germany	Epidemiologist
20	Martin-Bertelsen, Tomas	Statens Serum Institut (SSI), Denmark	Data scientist
21	Polanski, Piotr	National Institute of Public Health NIH, Poland	Epidemiologist
22	Richter, Lukas	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES), Austria	Data scientist
23	Rjabinina, Jelena	Health Board, Estonia	Epidemiologist
24	Savrasova, Larisa	The Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (CDPC), Latvia	Epidemiologist
25	Schaal Moreno, Guillem	Robert Koch-Institut (RKI), Germany	Research associate
26	Schulze, Heike	Robert Koch-Institut (RKI), Germany	Research associate
27	Sejling, Amalie	Statens Serum Institut (SSI), Denmark	Data scientist

28	Ullrich, Alexander	Robert Koch-Institut (RKI), Germany	Data scientist
29	vom Felde, Paulina	Robert Koch-Institut (RKI), Germany	Research associate
30	Vuzem, Sanja	Slovenian National Institute of Public Health (NIJZ), Slovenia	Epidemiologist

Annex 3. Pinboards Country Presentations

Annex 4. Posters Outbreak Detection Tool

WHAT AN IDEAL OUTBREAK DETECTION TOOL LOOKS LIKE...

GROUP: Gastro
Yinthe, Patricia, Ingrid

What should the ideal outbreak detection tool look like?
Think about a specific, realistic use case where signals are useful for outbreak detection from routine surveillance data of infectious diseases.

Specific
Measurable
Achievable
Reasonable
Time-bound

AIM (What should the tool be able to do?)

to detect outbreaks taking seasonality into account
- using threshold
- taking into account time window
- stratification possible on age/gender/geographic area

DATA USED (Which data will be the base; in what form)

age & sex extra: hospitalization / death / HUs
geographical - travel
time variable(s)
serotype

PATHOGEN/SYNDROME/DISEASE

STEC
Salmonella
Listeria
Shigella
Campylobacter

HANDLING (How is the tool operated, by whom etc.)

Shiny is easier and good for visualisation
R-scripts are more flexible, but you need (internal) IT resources.
Internal use → from there you could communicate to 'lower' levels

(IT) RESSOURCES

- Epidemiologist(s) working with it
- Back-up of IT-person(s) for changes/problems

OUTPUT/COMMUNICATION

Check the signal(s)
Outbreak investigation
Place it into EpiPulse
Communication (when relevant) to epi/infection field country.
Dashboard

WHAT AN IDEAL OUTBREAK DETECTION TOOL LOOKS LIKE...

GROUP: Respiratory diseases
 Hapo Justinek
 Peter Christmann
 Hapo Davelos

Specific
 Measurable
 Achievable
 Reasonable
 Time-bound

What should the ideal outbreak detection tool look like?
 Think about a specific, realistic use case where signals are useful for outbreak detection from routine surveillance data of infectious diseases.

AIM (What should the tool be able to do?)

Define baseline - continuously changing baseline
 Improve the surveillance; decrease manual work; provide more feedback (public; HICs)
 Detect change of the clinical feature of the infection (based on hospitalization, death, etc.)
 Increase reporting compliance

DATA USED (Which data will be the base; in what form)

Care-based data (age; address; infection)
 Passive, compulsory notification system

PATHOGEN/SYNDROME/DISEASE

Influenza
 COVID-19
 Varicella (Chickenpox)
 Scarlet fever
 RSV

HANDLING (How is the tool operated, by whom etc.)

National level
 Epidemiologists; IT experts; statistician - together
 Daily / weekly
 Automatic report (data; graphics)

(IT) RESSOURCES

Shortage in IT human resources (in some countries) → help from the project (other countries)
 Knowledge of R

OUTPUT/COMMUNICATION

Interpretation of data and detections by epidemiologists; communicate to public and to health governance
 Evaluate detections by local public health institutes
 Dashboard
 Early knowledge about an outbreak / change epidemiological situation → prevention measures

OUTBREAK DETECTION TOOLS WE WANT TO PROVIDE...

GROUP:

Specific
Measurable
Achievable
Reasonable
Time-bound

What outbreak detections can we provide in the next 12 months?
Think about specific requirements that should be fulfilled but are also realistic to achieve, i.e. already exist in some form or you have enough prior knowledge to implement it quickly.

Vision (What are we planning to provide)

TO PROVIDE AN EFFECTIVE SOLUTION FOR EARLY DETECTION AND MONITORING OF CLUSTERS OF DISEASES AND/OR SYNDROMES FOR PUBLIC HEALTH INTERVENTION

SHOW THRESHOLD OVER TIME ON TEST

↳ Output should support explainability

- Two modules
- signal detection
- minimum reports/visualisation
- easy to use

DATA (Which data will be the base; format (input + output))

Standardised format

- data that is routinely collected + HISTORIC DATA
- cases-based (Date, diagnoses). If possible region data
- inputs historic (time/test) vars: date, region, #cases, (disease/diagnosis, labelled outbreak)
- output signal (1/0), strength (Case-based or aggregated)

HANDLING (How is the tool operated, by whom and how, user interfaces, reporting)

outputs: granulated by local level
user: national level experts
↳ useful for all levels

- Repackage
- Self-contained app (Desktop)

adaptability: # warnings/day, parameter tuning?
reasonable defaults

Evaluation (automatic and by pilots)

- SENSITIVITY / SPECIFICITY, scoring metrics
- TIMELINESS
- USER FEEDBACK
 - ↳ usability of report/dashboard
 - ↳ user satisfaction w/ # and quality of warnings

Questions to piloting countries

summary of available data

CDM - common DATA MODEL

- case-based data available?
- reporting delay? How much?
- input prioritization between diseases in the tool?
- time frame available: daily, week, biweekly?

Annex 5. Flipcharts Evaluation of Pilots

- (3)
- EASE OF USE
 - HOW MANY REAL OUTBREAKS DETECTED FROM SIGNALS? (specificity)
 - TIMELINESS
 - HOW MANY OUTBREAKS WERE MISSED? (sensitivity)
 - COMPARE # OUTBREAKS DETECTED THROUGH ROUTINE SYSTEM
 - COMPARE # WGS data
 - USEFUL?
 - ↳ HELPED US DETECT O/Bs THAT WOULD HAVE BEEN MISSED / DETECTED LATE
 - ↳ ALLOWED FOR PH INTERVENTION

Annex 6. Mentimeter Results

Annex 6. Free text answers of the survey “Needs and gaps analysis on automated outbreak detection tools for routine surveillance data”

The survey “Needs and Gaps Analysis on Automated Outbreak Detection Tools for Routine Surveillance Data” contained open-ended questions and free-text fields for multiple choice-questions when the option ‘other’ was selected. The free text answers per country are compiled in the following.

Part 1: Public health surveillance system

What is the official name (full name and acronym) of the surveillance system?

Country	Answer
AT	Elektronisches Meldesystem - EMS
BE	National surveillance system of Salmonella via the National Reference Centre (NRC)
CZ	The Information System of Infectious Disease
DE	Meldewesen gemäß Infektionsschutzgesetz/ German statutory surveillance system for infectious diseases
DK	HAIBA - Healthcare-Associated Infections Database
EE	Estonian Information System for Infectious diseases (NAKIS)
ES	Outbreak surveillance system
FI	National Infectious Diseases Register (NIDR)
HR	National Public Health Information System (NAJS)
HU	Országos Szakmai Irányítási Rendszer, OSZIR
IE	Computerised Infectious Disease Reporting (CIDR) System
LT	The State Information System of Communicable Diseases and its Agents
LU	System of mandatory notifications of infectious diseases
LV	The full name of the existing infectious disease registration system is the State Infectious disease Surveillance and Monitoring System (VISUMS). In terms of outbreak detection, the system was supposed to detect outbreaks automatically, linking diseases that are grouped by address and time. There was also planned to display outbreaks on the map. However, the development of such functionalities was not complete. The existing VISUMS outbreak functionality allows the epidemiologist to combine cases into outbreaks manually. The creation of the new system is planned as the existing one is technically outdated.
MT	Disease Surveillance Manager (DSM) and National Electronic Disease Surveillance System (NEDSS)
NL	STEC surveillance
PL	Ogólnopolski System Nadzoru Epidemiologicznego
PT	SINAVE Sistema Nacional de Vigilância Epidemiológica/ National System of Epidemiologic Surveillance
RO	RUBT
SE	SmiNet
SI	COVID-19

Approximately in what year was the system established?

Country	Answer
AT	2007

BE	The NRC was officially created in 2011, but the reference activities of this laboratory exist for > 30 years
CZ	1993
DE	2001
DK	Developed between 2011-2014. Launched in 2015
EE	since 2009
ES	1980
FI	1995
HR	2013
HU	2014
IE	2003
LT	2010 (the system is currently being modernized)
LU	2018
LV	1997
MT	2010
NL	1999
PL	that depends for which disease
PT	Electronic system were established in 2015
RO	2007
SE	1997
SI	2020

For which disease group is the surveillance system designed? If other, please specify. (Other than air-borne diseases, antimicrobial resistance, blood-borne diseases/STI's, Food-and water-borne disease, healthcare-associated infections, vector-borne diseases, zoonotic diseases)

Country	Answer
BE	The current survey will be filled in with Salmonella surveillance as example and activities/answers could be extrapolated to other FWD pathogens (Shigella, Yersinia, STEC, Norovirus). Potentially also for other non FWD diseases with outbreak potential where laboratory-based surveillance via a NRC is the main surveillance system used
DK	AMR is expected to be included in future.
ES	Notification of outbreaks of any etiology (including those caused by toxins) and any setting is mandatory.
IE	Some HCAI are included but mostly maintained separately in EARSS data bases
LT	Vaccine preventable diseases (e.g. tetanus)
LV	There is a separate HIV/AIDS patient's register, where is not possible to detect outbreaks
MT	<p>The Infectious Disease Prevention and Control Unit (IDCU) within the Health Promotion and Disease Prevention Directorate is responsible for the surveillance of infectious diseases as well as the public health management of cases and outbreaks in Malta.</p> <p>Objectives of the unit: https://deputyprimeminister.gov.mt/en/health-promotion/idpcu/Pages/objectives.aspx</p> <p>IDCU is responsible for the surveillance of 73 statutory notifiable infectious diseases: https://deputyprimeminister.gov.mt/en/health-promotion/idpcu/Pages/notifiablediseases.aspx</p> <p>The NEDDS system is an upgrade from the previous system used at the unit and it is currently rolled out only for food and water-borne diseases including some zoonotic ones. However the system will eventually encompass all the 73 notifiable diseases</p>

PT	The system is designed to AMR but the digital platform is not yet prepared to collect AMR information.
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If case-based, please specify.

Country	Answer
BE	At the level of the NRC personal identifiable data can be used. At the level of the service of epidemiology and public health pseudonymized or anonymized data are used.
EE	using ID number
HU	The personal data are available for most of the diseases, but only pseudonymized data are available for some diseases/entities: e.g. HIV, STI, health care associated infections.
LV	A case identifier is available and if colleagues at national level needs additional information on a case, then the case identifier will be the link in communication with the regional epidemiologist.
MT	Being a small MS, IDCU does not only function as the national infectious disease surveillance unit but it is also the only unit responsible for the public health management of infectious disease cases and outbreaks in Malta. In view of this, patient data is communicated to IDCU to enable case investigation, contact tracing and implementation of the necessary measures to safeguard public health.
PL	variety of information is available/ many variables

Which information is reported routinely to the national level? If other, please specify. (Other than Pathogen, disease, symptoms, date of symptoms onset, hospitalization, possible exposure, risk factors, age, sex, geographical information, laboratory method, date of laboratory confirmation, molecular and genomic typing, date of clinical diagnosis, vaccination status or death)

Country	Answer
BE	Request form NRC to be send with isolate: https://www.sciensano.be/sites/default/files/aanvraagformulier_salmonella_en_shigella.pdf
CZ	Symptoms reported just in some diseases, molecular typing only in some specific cases - usually WGSs and similar methods not done in CZ yet, vaccination status in VPD
ES	For all outbreaks: transmission mode, dates of symptoms of the first and last case of the outbreak, setting of the outbreak, location of the outbreak, cases in foreign people (yes or no), imported/indigenous outbreak, and food laboratory method For waterborne and foodborne outbreaks: symptoms, contributing factors of the outbreak, place of consumption, incubation period, duration of illness, water/food contamination setting and measures implemented
IE	Not all of these variables are available for all disease -only those that have PH management - and completeness is variable
LT	The amount of the data depends on the investigation of the case
MT	info on pathogen, disease, age, sex, lab method, date of lab confirmation and death are readily available. The other info is collected by IDCU upon calling the case as part of routine investigation. WGS data is only available as from October 2022 for Salmonella and Campylobacter isolates only.
PT	Not all information is reported for all diseases, some disease have some information and others have another information. Not all information is mandatory.
SI	Date of reporting, unique identifier, country of residence

Please briefly describe in a few sentences the most relevant features of the chosen surveillance system.

Country	Answer
AT	It is a real time surveillance system for mandatory notifiable diseases in Austria. It can be accessed by the local and national PH-authorities. A case comprises of a clinical notification, a lab notification and the epidemiological description.
BE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Important foodborne pathogen (2500 – 3000 cases/year reported) ➤ High outbreak potential ➤ Historical existing surveillance system with high coverage that could be used for automated outbreak detection tool/s (ref: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34437638/) ➤ Importance of automated outbreak detection and more metadata (questionnaires) to better understand the epidemiology of this pathogen, also taking into account new developments in WGS, AMR aspects. ➤ Potentially reusable for other pathogens (e.g. Shigella, Yersinia, Listeria, STEC)
CZ	The system is since 2018 electronic, all data are case-based, most of infectious diseases is mandatory reported in CZ, different levels of data access for different users is established. STIs, TBC, ARI/ILI have separated registries.
DE	The Infection protection act defines the disease/pathogens (disease priority list), the entity that has to report and the content/data that needs to be reported. The report is sent to the competent local public health authority (LPHA). LPHA investigates additional relevant information and sends the data daily to regional public health authorities where it is forwarded to the national public health authority. On national level no personal data (name, address) exists. Pseudonymised case-based data (demographical, geographical and disease-specific) is for most pathogens within 24-48 h on national level available.
DK	HAIBA provides data on incidence of healthcare-associated infections, publicly available at https://www.esundhed.dk/Emner/Patienter-og-sygehuse/HAIBA . HAIBA is a fully automated surveillance system, which uses data from the Danish Microbiology Database (MiBa), Danish Patient Registry and the Civil Registration Registry. HAIBA identifies the following types of infections: Blood stream infections, urinary tract infections, infections with Clostridioides difficile, surgical site infections after total hip and knee alloplasty. Data are actively used in infection control in the hospitals. Some users have developed process control diagrams to identify signals. These diagrams are now widely used in infection control and there is a wish to implement them nationally in the HAIBA system.
EE	<p>Indicator-based surveillance:</p> <p>56 CD and 97 agents under Governmental regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • mandatory • comprehensive system • routine case-based surveillance • passive system • based on double notification – from HCW and laboratories • in use EU case definitions and ICD 10 code <p>Since 2009 Web-based informational system (NAKIS);</p> <p>Since 2021 started connection process NAKIS with Health Information System (TIS)</p> <p>Event-based surveillance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • epidemic intelligence: domestic media monitoring and monitoring of websites of neighboring countries, WHO outputs, ECDC outputs (EpiPulse) • priority list of CD and ASAP/immediate reporting by phone or NAKIS is required for indicated serious infectious diseases on suspicion and clusters with water- and food-borne transmission or unknown origin

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> information from agencies (Agriculture and Food Board, State Agency of Medicines, municipalities etc.)
ES	The notification of outbreaks of any aetiology (including those caused by toxics) is mandatory. All the physician must notify every detected outbreak, including public and private health centers.
FI	Data are collected to the surveillance system using communicable disease notifications filed by doctors and laboratories and this is based on the Communicable Diseases Act and Decree. Notifications made by the doctors includes more disease specific information and they complete the patient's clinical picture. The surveillance system includes a lot of information and around 40 different diseases, but automated surveillance has been implemented only for few diseases (COVID-19 for example).
HR	National coverage, mapped to ICD-10. General: to monitor diseases burden and epidemiology of disease and identify outbreaks and new pathogens. Specific: to define priority interventions (f.e. vaccination, prophylaxis); to reduce the incidence of diseases and/or to retain the elimination of certain disease disease, to early detect, respond and prevent outbreaks
HU	The OSZIR is the online system for reporting the notifiable diseases in Hungary. The health care providers (HCP) have to report. the system is uniform throughout the country. HCPs can report using an interface by connecting their own database and OSZIR. The majority of hospitals report via interface. Most of the GPs does not report through interface, but their assistants types the data into the online platform. We plan to make reporting on the interface general.
IE	Integrated web-based platform shared between local and ref labs and local and national PH with role based access. Nearing end of life. Limited integration of laboratory typing data -at variant level, and presence/absence of selected genes.
LT	Information about 108 communicables diseases and 59 agents ir recorded to the surveillance system. The list of communicable diseases and its agents is updated according to the needs.
LU	Most notifications come from labs. For some diseases (SARS-CoV-2, Mpx) we also have negative results.
LV	To monitor trends in infection diseases, to detect outbreaks. VISUMS allows to combining cases into outbreaks if certain parameters match (place, time, pathogen), as well as outbreak can be identified during the epidemiological investigation of individual cases, including contact person testing. The system allows to select and analyze outbreaks individually.
MT	The chosen surveillance system is the database of IDCU where details of the 73 statutory notifiable diseases are recorded. IDCU staff call and investigate every notified case. In Malta there is only have one main general government hospital that caters for all the country. Apart from receiving notifications from the community, IDCU has access to the test result platform of the clinical pathology lab of the general hospital and test results positive for the infectious diseases under surveillance are downloaded on a daily basis. All the notifications received, are inputted into the system (DSM)
NL	combining case- and molecular- information on the selected pathogen; promotes early outbreak detection.
PL	Case based surveillance system, with information on lab results, real-time, interlinked with foodborne outbreak system (for selected foodborne diseases)
PT	Automatic notification by medical doctors to health authorities in local, regional and national level. When the patient has a Health National Number, a automatic linkage is made by the

	system between medical and laboratory information for the same disease and for the same patient. The health authorities are able to create clusters between the clusters. When a notification is provided by a medical doctor or by a laboratory the health authority receive a email to alert of a new disease in the system.
RO	It allows the knowledge in real time and for a multiannual evidence/analysis/evolution
SE	Case reports for all notifiable communicable diseases. Laboratory reports and clinical information for all cases. The system is owned by PHAS and the Departments of Communicable Disease Control and Prevention.
SI	The COVID-19 surveillance system is the first and only automated surveillance system for CD in Slovenia at this moment. It is based on laboratory data (PCR) or data from clinicians (RAT), that are entered into the eHealth platform. Other CDs are currently still reported to the regional units of the NIPH manually (on a paper form) and then entered into our surveillance system (named SURVIVAL).

Part 2: Automated outbreak detection tools

Which main challenges do you currently have or anticipate to have when developing and implementing an automated outbreak detection tool? If other, please specify. (Other than data quality issues, legal mandate issues or sustainable funding/resources)

Country	Answer
CZ	IT technology and specialists, PH senior specialists (from national and also local levels), connection of electronic laboratory and PH entries/records.
ES	priority of politicians
FI	Outbreak detection tool development is not prioritized high enough. Very capable personnel exist currently but are tied to other projects.
HR	Capacity building for personnel is needed which is overloaded with routine tasks
IE	I would be particularly interested in an algorithm which worked from epidemiological data. WGS data is not on this surveillance system and cluster detection is currently undertaken in ref labs.
LT	lack of data, risks of functional issues between systems, delay of the data
LU	Low number of notifications due to being a small country.
LV	surveillance system does not have automated outbreak detection tool yet and we are planning to implement them. Main challenges regarding legal mandate issues - not all cases in outbreaks which is identified by epidemiologists have turned to a GP. So the current solution is that epidemiologist can create a probable case in the system without GP's or laboratory's notification. Main challenges regarding Sustainable funding/resources - there is no stable long-term funding for IS development.
MT	Having a proper supportive IT infrastructure in place and data managers and research analysts dedicated to perform surveillance
NL	personnel shortage
SE	Automated detection tool was implemented earlier in SmiNet. SmiNet was upgraded in 2022 and the tool has not yet been reimplemented.
SI	Training of personnel.

If you have or anticipate to have challenges, please explain them briefly.

Country	Answer
BE	Data Science/IT support towards the NRC may be challenging because of legal mandate differences within our public health institute.

	Resources (data science/statistics) are available but for surveillance / epidemiology of all infectious diseases. Sustained financing for enhanced molecular surveillance is lacking
CZ	The data are not reported in real-time, there is space for improvement (eg. automatic electronic reporting from GPs, labs, hospitals etc. - planned in CZ), One Health platform needed (including veterinary and CAFIA data),
FI	More urgent development areas compete with the resources. However in future situation might be better.
MT	Being a small MS we have limited resources especially with HR and funding. There is an increasing need to develop a proper surveillance database and that is why NEDSS is being rolled out as it is a web based platform compared to DSM which is an access database. NEDSS is currently not complete yet (rolled out only for food-borne illness) we are awaiting more funding to continue developing the surveillance system. IDCU would benefit from dedicated IT support as well as permanent staff who have expertise in analytics and programming
PT	Although the notification is mandatory by law some medical doctors and laboratories do not notify the cases. For a syndromic surveillance we need to better prepared the health electronic information, for example, the codification of reasons to use healthservices presents some delay that will undermine the timeliness of data and to detect outbreaks. On the other hand the interoperability through different electronic systems is not always possible.
SI	No sustainable funding is yet guaranteed for development of such tools and there is a challenge of sensibilizing decision makers of the importance of such approach for future CD surveillance and control. We would also need in-depth training of personnel to become skilled in automated outbreak detection tools. European network resources in trainings would be very beneficial for us, since we are a small country with limited resources.

Signals and Outbreaks

Are signals (i.e. from automated outbreak detection tools or manual analysis) followed by or trigger public health actions (i.e. investigation of an outbreak)? If yes, please briefly describe the public health action.

Country	Answer
AT	investigation of an outbreak
BE	Yes, but not on a regular basis. Ad-hoc on specific situations in collaboration with the regional health authorities who are in charge of conducting outbreak investigations
CZ	Investigation of the outbreak (local PH level have main responsibility), cooperation with State Vet Auth of Food safety if needed, communication with stakeholders and international (if needed), etc.
DE	Signals are investigated by public health experts for their relevance and in some cases local health authorities are contacted and outbreak investigations initiated.
EE	clarification and verification of signals, epidemiological investigation, risk assessment and PH intervention in case of necessity
ES	Outbreak investigation and control measures
FI	Local health authorities are contacted, contact tracing begins, more samples will be collected (identifying cluster, variant etc)
HU	The local public health authority has to check the validity of the data/signal. If there is an outbreak (or suspicion of an outbreak) the authority has to investigate it and the measures if necessary.
IE	Can trigger: advisory to local PH department of clustering of cases in their area; request for WGS/typing (if not already available); request for collection of data in addition to that usually

	captured; alerts to partner agencies such as Dept of agriculture/food safety authority (if suspected foodborne/zoonotic) and/or EpiPulse alert
LT	the data analysis will be performed and investigation of an outbreak will be organized information about suspected outbreak, recommendations and prevention measures to the public
LU	Depending on the disease, outbreak investigations (e.g. Salmonella, mpox) or prevention measures are started (e.g. targeted vaccination campaigns for measles, meningitis, varicella or Mpox).
LV	Public health action description: epidemiological investigation of the outbreak, including identification of a contactperson and laboratory investigation. As well as organization medical surveillance of contact's and including organisation of control measures.
MT	As IDCU functions as both a surveillance unit and a case/outbreak management unit, such an alert would be investigated promptly to identify if it is a true increase and public health actions will be instituted accordingly.
NL	outbreak investigation: questionnaire and contact with food safety authority
PL	epidemiological investigation aiming at identifying source, neutralizing it as soon as possible
PT	The public health action will be proportional to the impact, magnitude and transcendence of the alert. If small the local authorities will apply the public health actions, if medium the regional authorities coordinated the action, if major event a taskforce is coordinated by the National Health Authority with the support of the Public Health Emergencies Operations Centre that will call all the stakeholders that are needed.
SE	Start an outbreak investigation, communication with the Department of Communicable Disease Control and Prevention of concern as well as other agencies.
SI	Signals are verified with the institution that is reporting a higher number of cases. If an outbreak is confirmed, an investigation is triggered and control measures are suggested. Close connection with the institution is established on a regular basis and if needed, communication with media is activated (i.e. a press conference).

Is feedback required and given on the public health actions based on the signal? If yes, please describe the form of feedback loop.

Country	Answer
AT	regular videoconferences of all parties involved
CZ	Local PH Authorities are preparing reports from each investigated outbreak - the report is sent to NIPH and in some cases to MoH. Since last two years the outbreak data are reported also to surveillance system electronically (that means, that case-based data reported to electronic surveillance system are marked as belonging to the concrete "outbreak").
DE	In case of outbreak investigations, reports are written.
EE	Comment in NAKIS /or emergency CD notification /or outbreak investigation report
ES	communication between stakeholders and dissemination of reports
HU	The local health authority has to send reports about the outbreak investigation to the county level and the county level reports to the national level. The report goes in the system (OSZIR) and through e-mail.
IE	No feedback required from regional offices if they are alerted of cluster. But partner agencies/departments would be included in email communications and updates if HPSC-led national cluster investigation
LV	Usually a feedback is required form the GP's regarding medical surveillance of contact', from Health inspectorate and Food and Veterinary service regarding organization of control measures at affected objects.

MT	As Malta is a small MS and all surveillance and outbreak investigation is done by the same Public Health Unit, no formal feedback is necessary. The detection tool will be assessed by the same team investigating the cases and outbreaks.
PL	incidence is being monitored in real time by the State Sanitary Inspection, local environmental/ setting inspection/ checking and sample taking is being done
PT	Every alert and the action taken should be report to the national health authority.
SI	Institution with an ongoing outbreak reports to the epi investigation team at the regional unit at NIPH. Regional unit reports to the Communicable Diseases Centre at NIPH, which reports to EWRS (if needed). Regional unit also reports to inspectorates (health, food) which reports back on their findings (if they perform any investigation).

Automated outbreak detection tools

What type of tool are you using? If other, please specify. (Other than external software, existing open library or self-implemented solution)

Country	Answer
DK	Not decided yet. A pilot has been made in R/Shiny.
IE	Bionumerics used by lab for WGS cluster detection. No detection tool routinely used at HPSC for exceedences.in notified cases but R scripts being explored
LU	None, outbreak detection is currently "manual" either by the laboratory who conduct sequencing or by inspectors who deal with all notification.
LV	Part of E-health system

If an external software or an existing library is used, please specify which one.

Country	Answer
DE	The Farrington Flexible function in the Surveillance library is used.
FI	Self implemented solution on top of R-library mem https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/mem/index.html

What is the outcome (presentation/communication of the results) of the tool? If other, please specify.

Country	Answer
FI	Graphs - visual interpretation, results can be seen here: https://thl.fi/fi/web/infektioaudit-ja-rokotukset/audit-ja-torjunta/audit-ja-taudinaiheuttajat-a-o/influenssa/ajantasainen-influenssakatsaus/influenssakaynnit-terveyskeskuksissa
IE	exploring use of power BI dashboard

What statistical method is used? If other, please specify.

Country	Answer
FI	Moving epidemic method
IE	The intention would to use time series outlier. Fixed threshold used for flu season. We are in the process of recruiting a geospatial analyst and may explore spatial clustering in the future
LV	Clustering and Fixed Threshold, trends which show possible outbreak
PL	It depends for which diseases/ pathogens. Generally there are rules for spatial clustering, number of cases threshold, time interval

Please share your ideas how your tool can be improved.

Country	Answer
DE	Resulting signals should be better summarized and tested through other information channels in order to reduce the number of signals. Reporting could be more flexible so as to reflect the different objectives of the users.
FI	We have not studied the tool enough to fully embrace it's potential or options.
HR	We are in the planned implementation phase
IE	For WGS clustering for foodborne pathogens, we have created guidelines/criteria about when it would be reasonable to initiate an investigation. We have refined these based on experience in the early years of WGS availability.
LV	Our automated outbreak detection tool is under the development of a descriptive stage, so why we put unknown for 5 questions before

Annex 7. Data description of input variables

Surveillance Data Variables

Variable	Mandatory	Description
case_id	YES	Unique identifier for a specific case, but nothing that can be used to identify the case or patient within the national surveillance system
date_report	YES	Date when the case was reported in ISO 8601 format YYYY-MM-DD
date_onset	If available	Date when symptoms started in ISO 8601 format YYYY-MM-DD
date_hospitalization	If available	Date when the case was admitted to the hospital in ISO 8601 format YYYY-MM-DD
date_death	If available	Date when the case died in ISO 8601 format YYYY-MM-DD
date_vaccination	If available	Date when the case was vaccinated in ISO 8601 format YYYY-MM-DD
country	YES	Name of the country in which the case was reported
country_id	YES	Id of the country in which the case was reported, Id should be NUTS-0 or ISO-alpha3 code
state	NO	Name of the state/major region in which the case was reported
state_id	NO	Id of the state as NUTS-1 code
county	NO	Name of the county/basic region in which the case was reported
county_id	NO	Id of the county as NUTS-2 code
community	NO	Name of the community/small region in which the case was reported
community_id	NO	Id of the community as NUTS-3 code
age	NO	Age of the reported case at the time of reporting as integer between 0-125
age_group	YES	Age group of the reported case at the time of reporting as interval, e.g. 05-14 for cases with an age between 5 and 14 years
sex	YES	Sex of the reported case, one of male, female, diverse, unknown
occupation	NO	Occupation of the reported case, one of the following options: care, kindergarten, food production, ???
place_of_infection	NO	Name of the region in which the case was likely infected if that place is different from the reporting region
place_of_infection_id	NO	Id of the region in which the case was likely infected as NUTS-code
pathogen	YES	Name of the pathogen/diagnosis that was identified
pathogen_id	NO	Id of the pathogen/diagnosis
subtype	NO	Name of the subtype/serovar/variant that was identified
subtype_id	NO	Id of the subtype/serovar/variant
hospitalization	NO	Indication whether the case was hospitalized, YES, NO or unknown
death	NO	Indication whether the case has died, YES, NO or unknown
vaccination	NO	Indication whether the case was vaccinated before infection, YES, NO or unknown
symptoms	NO	List of symptoms that were observed ???
risks	NO	List of risks that the case had before the infection

Outbreak data (Option 1: case-based)

Variable	Mandatory	Description
case_id	YES	Unique identifier for a specific case, but nothing that can be used to identify the case or patient within the national surveillance system
outbreak_status	YES	Indication whether the case is known to be part of an outbreak, YES, NO, Unknown
outbreak_id	NO	Unique identifier for the specific outbreak to which the specific case belongs to, but nothing that can be used to identify the case or patient or outbreak within the national surveillance system

Outbreak data (Option 2: aggregated)

Variable	Mandatory	Description
date_report	YES	Date when the case was reported in ISO 8601 format YYYY-MM-DD
count_cases	YES	Number of reported cases for the respective aggregation
outbreak_status	YES	Indication whether for the respective aggregation there is an outbreak, YES, NO, Unknown
count_outbreak_cases	YES	Number of reported cases that belong to the outbreak
outbreak_id	NO	Unique identifier for the specific outbreak, but nothing that can be used to identify the cases or outbreak within the national surveillance system
country	YES	Name of the country in which the case was reported
country_id	YES	Id of the country in which the case was reported, Id should be NUTS-0 or ISO-alpha3 code
state	NO	Name of the state/major region in which the case was reported
state_id	NO	Id of the state as NUTS-1 code
county	NO	Name of the county/basic region in which the case was reported
county_id	NO	Id of the county as NUTS-2 code
community	NO	Name of the community/small region in which the case was reported
community_id	NO	Id of the community as NUTS-3 code
age	NO	Age of the reported case at the time of reporting as integer between 0-125
age_group	NO	Age group of the reported case at the time of reporting as interval, e.g. 05-14 for cases with an age between 5 and 14 years
sex	NO	Sex of the reported case, one of male, female, diverse, unknown
pathogen	YES	Name of the pathogen/diagnosis that was identified
pathogen_id	NO	Id of the pathogen/diagnosis
subtype	NO	Name of the subtype/serovar/variant that was identified
subtype_id	NO	Id of the subtype/serovar/variant

Annex 8. Evaluation results report for outbreak detection algorithms

Last edited: 12.12.2023

This document is a continuously extending report on the evaluation results of different outbreak detection algorithms applied to surveillance data with outbreak information from multiple countries on different geographical levels. The evaluation results are shown on the geographical levels country level, state and county level. The outbreak detection algorithms are applied to the last 52 weeks of each timeseries. The generated alarms are compared to the known outbreaks and several performance metrics such as sensitivity, specificity, fpr are computed for each timeseries (ts).

Furthermore we compute characteristics for each timeseries to gain more information about the ts. Examples of these characteristics are the number of cases in the ts, number of outbreaks in the ts, number and proportion of weeks with cases, number and proportion of weeks with outbreaks, length of the ts, pandemic included in the ts and more.

Metrics

Currently only the metrics sensitivity and specificity are shown but more metrics will be shown in the future.

On country level one value for each metric is obtained as there is only one timeseries for each country.

On state and county level we apply the outbreak detection algorithms to the timeseries of each state or county of one country. Thus we obtain n values for each metric with n being the number of counties or states.

In this report we visualise the overall value and the distribution of these metrics.

For the overall metric the results for the generated alarms and true outbreak status from the n timeseries are combined and then the overall metric value is computed (i.e. sensitivity overall counties).

The figures about the distribution of the metrics use the computed value of the metric for each timeseries. The distribution of these n values is visualised using boxplots or scatterplots.

Country Level

Results for sensitivity and specificity for each timeseries on country level are shown. These figures use geom_jitter in the x axis direction so that points do not overlap.

Poland had no weeks without outbreak in the last 52 weeks thus the specificity is missing.

State Level

Overall sensitivity and specificity are shown.

Distribution of the metrics are shown using boxplots.

Distribution of sensitivity against proportion of weeks with outbreaks. The x and y axis have different limits for the individual plots.

Table with results on state level

Table with sensitivity results.

country	category	method	sensitiv y_overal l	sensitiv y_mean	sensitiv y_media n	sensitiv y_q25	sensitiv y_q75
GER_ca m_14-19	state_id	cusum	0.54	0.55	0.57	0.40	0.68
GER_ca m_14-19	state_id	ears	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.05
GER_ca m_14-19	state_id	farringto n	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.01	0.07
GER_ca m_17-23	state_id	cusum	0.19	0.31	0.27	0.00	0.40
GER_ca m_17-23	state_id	ears	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
GER_ca m_17-23	state_id	farringto n	0.11	0.18	0.05	0.00	0.31
GER_sa l_14-19	state_id	cusum	0.41	0.37	0.41	0.14	0.54
GER_sa l_14-19	state_id	ears	0.05	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.09
GER_sa l_14-19	state_id	farringto n	0.17	0.15	0.14	0.00	0.22

country	category	method	sensitivity_overall	sensitivity_mean	sensitivity_median	sensitivity_q25	sensitivity_q75
GER_sail_17-23	state_id	cusum	0.38	0.32	0.25	0.17	0.52
GER_sail_17-23	state_id	ears	0.08	0.14	0.07	0.04	0.11
GER_sail_17-23	state_id	farrington	0.58	0.65	0.65	0.48	0.83
HU_varicella_21-22	state_id	cusum	0.82	0.81	0.74	0.73	0.85
HU_varicella_21-22	state_id	ears	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.07	0.11
NL_STEC_17-23	state_id	cusum	0.75	0.83	1.00	0.83	1.00
NL_STEC_17-23	state_id	ears	0.12	0.25	0.00	0.00	0.25
NL_STEC_17-23	state_id	farrington	0.38	0.42	0.33	0.00	0.75
malta_sail_15_23	state_id	cusum	0.57	0.54	0.54	0.44	0.65
malta_sail_15_23	state_id	ears	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
malta_sail_15_23	state_id	farrington	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Table with specificity results.

country	category	method	specificity_overall	specificity_mean	specificity_median	specificity_q25	specificity_q75
GER_cam_14-19	state_id	cusum	0.67	0.70	0.66	0.57	0.83
GER_cam_14-19	state_id	ears	0.97	0.98	0.98	0.97	1.00

country	category	method	specificity_overall	specificity_mean	specificity_median	specificity_q25	specificity_q75
GER_cam_14-19	state_id	farrington	0.96	0.96	0.97	0.94	1.00
GER_cam_17-23	state_id	cusum	0.89	0.89	0.94	0.78	1.00
GER_cam_17-23	state_id	ears	0.97	0.97	0.98	0.97	0.98
GER_cam_17-23	state_id	farrington	0.91	0.92	0.96	0.87	0.98
GER_sali_14-19	state_id	cusum	0.88	0.84	0.88	0.71	0.97
GER_sali_14-19	state_id	ears	0.98	0.98	1.00	0.98	1.00
GER_sali_14-19	state_id	farrington	0.95	0.94	0.94	0.91	1.00
GER_sali_17-23	state_id	cusum	0.87	0.86	0.86	0.75	0.98
GER_sali_17-23	state_id	ears	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.96	1.00
GER_sali_17-23	state_id	farrington	0.78	0.77	0.72	0.67	0.88
HU_varicella_21-22	state_id	cusum	0.19	0.22	0.07	0.03	0.32
HU_varicella_21-22	state_id	ears	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.96	0.98
NL_STEC_17-23	state_id	cusum	0.62	0.62	0.60	0.48	0.75
NL_STEC_17-23	state_id	ears	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.96	0.98
NL_STEC_17-23	state_id	farrington	0.82	0.82	0.86	0.75	0.94
malta_sals_15-23	state_id	cusum	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98

country	category	method	specificity_overall	specificity_mean	specificity_median	specificity_q25	specificity_q75
malta_s al_15_2 3	state_id	ears	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.96	0.97
malta_s al_15_2 3	state_id	farrington	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.97	0.99

County Level

Overall sensitivity and specificity are shown.

Distribution of the metrics are shown using boxplots.

Distribution of sensitivity against proportion of weeks with outbreaks. The x and y axis have different limits for the individual plots.

Time Series Characteristics

We visualise the proportion of weeks with outbreaks and the proportion of weeks with cases here. More time series characteristics can be shown in the future.

As with metrics we obtain one value for the features on country level but n values for the features on state and county level. The distribution of these values is shown.

Country Level

State Level

County Level

